

Report of the Second Carbon Farming Summit, June 2025

D4.2

Project CREDIBLE: “Building momentum and trust to achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU”.

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CREDIBLE
EU carbon farming

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Executive summary

Purpose

The Second European Carbon Farming Summit, held in Dublin from 4–6 March 2025, was organised as part of the EU-funded project *CREDIBLE: Building momentum and trust to achieve credible carbon farming in the EU* (Grant Agreement 101112951). As the second of three annual summits, it aimed to strengthen Europe’s emerging carbon farming ecosystem by scaling conversations from pilot projects to systemic transition pathways. The summit focused on practical challenges and opportunities for making carbon farming credible, equitable, and effective, while deepening multi-stakeholder trust and collaboration.

Intended audience

This deliverable is intended for EU and national policy makers; public agencies involved in land-use and soil governance; researchers in agroecology, carbon accounting, and MRV innovation; farming networks and rural advisory services; private sector actors along agri-food and carbon market value chains; NGOs working on biodiversity and environmental justice; and practitioners designing carbon certification or finance schemes. It serves those who are developing, regulating, implementing, or scaling carbon farming solutions in Europe.

Description of the main activities

The 2025 summit hosted over 1,050 participants (550 in person, 500+ online), with 100+ organisations represented across three days of programming. Designed through two open calls for contributions, the agenda was intentionally co-created to ensure that

content addressed the most urgent and relevant topics. This participatory approach yielded 5 high-level plenary sessions, 48 breakout sessions, and numerous informal exchanges involving farmers, scientists, policymakers, businesses, and civil society actors.

Sessions covered the evolution of EU policy (notably the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework – CRCF), farmer motivation and advisory support, MRV innovation, finance, and the broader co-benefits of carbon farming. Deliberate session merging and co-facilitation strategies created dynamic, multi-perspective dialogue. Digital participation and real-time polling (via Mentimeter) helped shape discussion and surface shared concerns.

Key results

- **Result 1: Carbon farming must go beyond carbon.**

While carbon sequestration remains a key goal, the summit confirmed that an overly narrow focus on soil carbon risks sidelining broader benefits. Attendees called for a shift toward landscape-level approaches that integrate biodiversity, water management, rural livelihoods, and ecosystem resilience. Carbon farming must be designed as a tool for systemic transformation, not just climate accounting.

- **Result 2: Finance and advisory support are the linchpins of scale.**

Participants agreed that blended finance – combining public and private capital – is essential to make carbon farming viable and scalable. However, financial innovation must be accompanied by robust advisory networks to help farmers navigate complex requirements and access funding. The summit highlighted the implementation gap around farm-level support, which risks leaving many farmers behind.

- **Result 3: Co-creation and local leadership are essential for legitimacy.**

The summit itself demonstrated the power of participatory design, from its open-call structure to the central role of innovating farmers. Farmers must be treated not just as beneficiaries, but as co-designers and leaders of the transition. Building systems that reflect on-the-ground realities will be key to credibility and uptake.

Research and practice implications

The summit underscored the need for further research into multi-benefit carbon farming metrics, locally tailored MRV methodologies, and governance models that support flexibility while maintaining integrity. There is a pressing need to operationalise farmer-centric innovation systems, encourage peer-to-peer learning, and link practices with ecosystem-level monitoring. These insights suggest a rich research agenda that integrates social science, agronomy, remote sensing, and systems thinking.

Practitioners, meanwhile, are encouraged to adopt modular and inclusive approaches – designing schemes that can adapt to different geographies and farm types while aligning with evolving EU policy frameworks. The summit also made visible the need for new platforms to share success stories, coordinate initiatives, and prevent duplication of effort.

Policy implications

The summit highlighted the importance of policy coherence and integration. The CRCF was welcomed as a step forward, but participants stressed that it must align with CAP, biodiversity, climate, and soil strategies. National governments and the European Commission were urged to reduce fragmentation, support multi-benefit schemes, and ensure carbon farming is embedded not only in food system transitions, but also in broader landscape strategies that include forestry, rewilding, and non-food bioeconomy sectors – such as the alternative use of rewetted organic soils. These insights are relevant across all eight Mission Soil objectives, particularly those addressing sustainable soil management, ecosystem services, and robust monitoring frameworks. At all levels, policies must enable long-term investment, differentiated approaches, and inclusive engagement with those managing Europe's land.

Conclusion

The 2025 summit was a demonstration of how Europe's carbon farming transition can and must be designed: inclusively, systemically, and in partnership with those who steward the land. It brought the realities of farmers, the insights of scientists, and the levers of policy and finance into active dialogue. As Europe moves forward with carbon farming regulation and soil strategy implementation, the summit's outcomes will serve as a foundation for action, feeding directly into CREDIBLE's final year of activity and the shaping of a durable, post-project roadmap.

List of acronyms and abbreviations

AFOLU: Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use

AI: Artificial Intelligence

CAP: Common Agricultural Policy

CF: Carbon Farming

CO₂: Carbon Dioxide

CRCF: Carbon Removal Certification Framework

CSRD: Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive

DG AGRI: Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development

DG CLIMA: Directorate-General for Climate Action

DG ENV: Directorate-General for Environment

DoA: Description of the Action

EC: European Commission

EEF: Enhanced Efficiency Fertilizers

EIP-AGRI OG: European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability Operational Group

EO: Earth Observation
ESABCC: European Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change
EU: European Union
EU ETS: European Union Emissions Trading System
EUSO: European Union Soil Observatory
FSC: Forest Stewardship Council
FTOP: Funding & Tenders Portal
GA: Grant Agreement
GHG: Greenhouse Gas
ICVCM: Integrity Council for the Voluntary Carbon Market
LTM: Long-term Monitoring
LULUCF: Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry
MRV: Measurement, Reporting and Verification
NbS: Nature-based Solutions
NGOs: Non-governmental Organisation
PACM: Paris Agreement Crediting Mechanism
PEFC: Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification
PO: Project Officer
RS: Remote Sensing
SCF: Smart Carbon Farming
SO: Specific Objectives
Soil Carbon IRC: International Research Consortium
VCM: Voluntary Carbon Market
VVBs: Validation and Verification Bodies
WP: Work Package

1. Project summary

This deliverable is part of the EU-funded project under the topic HORIZON-MISS-2022-SOIL-01-06, titled: Building momentum and trust to achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU (project acronym: CREDIBLE, Grant Agreement #101112951).

The main goal of the CREDIBLE project is to build momentum and trust for the implementation of carbon farming in the EU. This will be primarily achieved by setting up and moderating a network of initiatives/projects/stakeholders for favouring transparency, environmental integrity, and methodology standardisation in soil carbon accounting. Such a network will be responsible for pushing forward multiple discussions (articulated around three main themes: which practices; what standards; how to monitor) and is expected to evolve from a mostly technical/scientific network at the onset of the project, into a process catalysing policy making and business innovation toward its end. The transparent, open access, multi actor dialogues required to build trust and co-create solutions will be orchestrated around three annual European Carbon Farming Summits, which will present opportunities for the network to interact with the broader stakeholder

community and grow to the point it would attract further fundings for long term sustainability. Through the action, four specific objectives (SO) will be achieved:

SO1) to build and disseminate a practical toolbox for promoting carbon farming, capable of taking into account local land uses, best practices, and multi-actor interests;

SO2) to identify options for benchmarking and selecting standards, certification mechanisms, and policy instruments for carbon farming;

SO3) to favour the establishment of a network of soil carbon data collectors and repositories to improve measuring and monitoring carbon dynamics;

SO4) to build up processes and tools to drive conversations for the upscaling of carbon farming. CREDIBLE's ambition is to support the European Commission and the Expert Group on Carbon Removal in the identification and upscale of solutions for soil carbon farming. Tables 1 and 2 provide further information on the structure and composition of the project.

Table 1 - CREDIBLE's work package structure.

WP#	WP Name	Lead
WP1	Practical knowledge and fit-for-region blueprint for carbon scheme development	11-BSAG
WP2	Navigating and selecting carbon standards and policy instruments	12-EEB
WP3	Existing monitoring capabilities as enablers of soil data collection and sharing	8 - UFZ
WP4	Networking and communication actions to drive Carbon Farming in the EU	15-CKIC
WP5	Project management and coordination	1 – SAE

Table 2 - CREDIBLE's consortium composition.

Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
Soluciones Agrícolas Ecoinnovadoras SL	SAE	ES
Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore	UCSC	IT
European Conservation Agriculture Federation	ECAF	BE
Association des Chambres d'Agriculture de l'Arc Atlantique	AC3A	FR
Greifswald University	UG	DE
Ecologic Institute	ECO	DE
European Association of Remote Sensing Companies	EARSC	BE
Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung GmbH	UFZ	DE
Centre de Recerca Ecològica i Aplicacions Forestals	CreAF	ES
Cooperativas Agro-alimentarias de España U de coop sociedad cooperativa	COOP	ES
Baltic sea action group	BSAG	FI
European Environmental Bureau	EEB	BE
European agroforestry federation	EURAF	FR
BioEconomy Cluster	BEC	SK
Climate KIC Foundation	CKIC	NL

University of Helsinki	UH	FI
Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food	ILVO	BE
Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria	CREA	IT
Agricultural Applications Private Company (AgroApps)	APPS	GR
Institute for Climate Economics	I4CE	FR
Ellinikos Georgikos Organismos - DIMITRA	ELGO	GR

1.1 Introduction To The 2nd European Carbon Farming Summit

The 2nd European Carbon Farming Summit took place from 4–6 March 2025, at the historic Dublin Castle in Ireland. Organised by Project Credible in partnership with the Government of Ireland’s Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine, the summit brought together over 1,000 participants, including farmers, foresters, policymakers, researchers and businesses, to shape the future of carbon farming across Europe.

Following the success of the inaugural summit in Valencia, the 2025 edition shifted from theory to practice by involving a large array of stakeholders, including farmers. Its primary goal was to operationalize carbon farming by moving beyond high-level theory and focusing on practical strategies, tools, and frameworks that enable credible, scalable, and inclusive uptake of carbon farming across diverse European contexts.

As a multi-stakeholder event, the summit was designed around co-creation and dialogue. An open call for sessions and contributions allowed participants to shape the agenda, which featured five plenaries and over 40 breakout discussions covering topics such as monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV), financing, policy alignment, landowner engagement, and biodiversity.

A defining feature of this year’s summit was its farmer-centred approach. Farmers and land managers were invited to actively contribute and co-lead sessions. This reflected a clear recognition that those working directly with the land must be at the heart of the carbon farming transition. From peer-to-peer learning and lived experiences to practical barriers and incentives, the summit made space for their voices, challenges, and innovations.

Hosted in Ireland, a country emerging as a leader in regenerative agriculture, the summit also showcased the development of a national carbon farming framework that integrates carbon sequestration with broader environmental and social benefits. It provided a valuable case study for the rest of Europe and reinforced the importance of aligning EU policy, national action, and local practice.

1.2 The Second Summit In Numbers

Over **1,050** participants engaged with the summit, including **550** in-person attendees and more than **500** joining online from across Europe and beyond. This impressive

turnout underscored the growing momentum and urgency around carbon farming as a key climate and land-use solution.

The summit drew representation from more than **100** organisations, spanning EU institutions, national ministries, farmers' associations, research institutes, NGOs, and private sector actors. Across three full days of programming, participants engaged in a rich agenda featuring **five** high-level plenary sessions, **48** parallel sessions, and multiple poster presentations and networking opportunities. These sessions covered a wide range of topics, from monitoring and verification frameworks to policy coherence, farmer engagement, and innovative financing models.

In total, the summit was shaped by over **190** session organisers and contributors, reflecting the strength and breadth of Europe's agri-food and climate ecosystem. Their contributions helped ensure that the event was not only informative but participatory, grounded in real-world perspectives and cross-sector collaboration.

Geographically, the summit welcomed participants from more than **15** EU Member States, with particularly strong representation from Ireland, France, Germany, Spain, and the Netherlands – highlighting a shared European commitment to scaling credible carbon farming practices.

Importantly, the programme was co-created through **two** open calls issued prior to the event. These calls invited stakeholders to propose session ideas and speakers, ensuring that the summit addressed the most relevant, high-impact, and timely topics.

Image: Participants during one of the poster presentation sessions

2. Summary of the plenary sessions

2.1 Plenary 1: Opening by the Government of Ireland's Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM) and the state of affairs in policy related to carbon farming (and beyond)

Organisers: DG Clima/AGRI/JRC/CKIC

Objective:

To highlight the current policy landscape for carbon farming in Europe and explore how evolving agricultural and climate frameworks – particularly the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) – can support an inclusive and credible transition toward regenerative land management.

Panellists:

- **Christian Holtzleitner:** Head of Unit for Land Economy and Carbon Removals at the Directorate-General for Climate Action (DG CLIMA), European Commission. Since 2022, he has led the EU's work on sustainable carbon cycles and the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF). He has worked in the European Commission since 2012 in various policy development roles including ETS and state aid.
- **Eric Soubeiran:** CEO of Livelihoods Venture, which mobilises industrial investors to support rural energy, mangrove restoration, agroforestry, and smallholder farming projects in the Global South. Former Chief Sustainability Officer at Danone, Eric also serves on boards such as Gold Standard and The Carbon Trust.
- **Bill Callanan:** Chief Inspector at Ireland's Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM). He oversees scientific advice on agriculture and environment, including climate change, biodiversity, livestock breeding, horticulture, pesticide regulation, and nutrient management.
- **Jocelyn Gainche:** Farmer and manager of GAEC des Belles Filles, a collaborative farm in western France producing cereals, pork, and beef. Jocelyn uses the farm as a testing ground for innovative practices aligned with carbon farming. He also brings international farming experience, including time spent in Poland.
- **Daniel Zimmer (moderator):** Director of Sustainable Land Use at Climate KIC. Daniel is a climate policy expert and researcher focusing on sustainable land use and long-term resilience. He leads major initiatives such as the Climate Smart Forest Economy Programme, which aims to scale up sustainable alternatives to fossil-based materials.

Summary of session

The first plenary session of the summit opened with remarks from Tristano Bacchetti De Gregoris (Project CREDIBLE), who provided a short look back on the past year of the CREDIBLE project. After this, Saskia Keesstra introduced the logistics and began with some general questions to the in-person and online audience using Menti.

The following questions were asked:

1. Which country are you from [wordcloud]?
2. Which stakeholder category do you identify yourself with:
 - CF practitioner
 - Policy maker
 - Industry
 - Farmer/forester
 - Researcher
 - Other

These were the results:

The keynote address was delivered by Christian Holzleitner (DG CLIMA), who provided an overview of the EU’s strategic direction on agriculture in the climate transition and shared updates on the CRCF, designed to reward land-based carbon removals through

- **CRCF is an important step, but must be grounded in reality:** While the framework introduces much-needed legitimacy and consistency to carbon farming, its success will depend on simplicity, flexibility, and local alignment.
- **Farmer engagement is both essential and fragile:** Without trust, fairness, and support, farmers are unlikely to engage in carbon farming schemes – particularly given current frustrations with bureaucracy and market volatility.
- **The agri-food sector must balance multiple pressures:** Climate ambition must go hand-in-hand with economic viability, especially for small-scale producers. This requires clear incentives, transparent governance, and value chain support.
- **Policy coherence is vital:** Fragmentation across EU and national policies risks undermining impact. Effective integration – between CAP, CRCF, and biodiversity strategies – is needed to enable a joined-up, systemic approach.
- **Advisory and knowledge systems are key enablers:** Capacity-building, technical advice, and farmer networks must be resourced and strengthened if carbon farming is to move from policy concept to widespread practice.

This session effectively set the tone for the summit, reinforcing carbon farming as not just a climate mitigation tool, but a lever for wider agricultural transformation – grounded in collaboration, trust, and practical implementation.

2.2 Plenary 2: Technological pathways and user engagement approaches to a European MRV system

Organiser: Hannes Mollenhauer – UFZ

Objective:

To explore technical, financial, and practical challenges in building a robust and harmonised European MRV (Monitoring, Reporting and Verification) system for carbon farming—while identifying solutions that reduce complexity, ensure credibility, and align with certification needs across ecosystems, scales, and stakeholder groups.

Panellists:

- **Tessa van der Voort:** Tessa van der Voort is a project manager at NMI, where she specializes in soil carbon, data analysis, and sustainability. She earned her PhD in soil science from ETH Zurich and combines biogeochemistry with data science to advance carbon sequestration research.
- **Greet Ruyschaert:** Greet Ruyschaert is a Senior Researcher at ILVO. She holds a PhD in agricultural sciences and specializes in sustainable soil management, carbon sequestration, and soil health monitoring. She also coordinates ILVO's MARVIC project on GHG balance and carbon farming systems.
- **Edouard Lanckriet:** Édouard Lanckriet is Strategy Director and Head of the Low-Carbon Agriculture Division at Agrosolutions, spearheading their

carbon-farming and MRV initiatives. An agronomist-engineer with a Master's in Environmental Management and a PhD in development socio-economics, he has led international projects (China, Brazil, Africa) and plays a key role in EU initiatives like MARVIC.

- **Ahmad Al Bitar:** Ahmad Al Bitar is Head of Development at CESBIO (CNRS), leading the AgriCarbon-EO tool. A remote sensing specialist with a PhD in environmental modelling, he has contributed over 95 scientific publications and plays a key role in satellite-based agricultural and hydrological monitoring.
- **Liv Toonen:** Liv Toonen is the Technical Project Lead at Space4Good, leveraging her aerospace engineering background to apply remote-sensing and geospatial technologies for social and environmental impact, including deforestation monitoring and ESG reporting.
- **Véronique Chauvin:** Véronique Chauvin is Head of the Trees & Biodiversity Service at the Chambre d'Agriculture Pays de la Loire. Since 2018, she has overseen energy-environment missions and biodiversity initiatives, including agroforestry and hedgerow programs.
- **Roberta Mac Donald:** Roberta Mac Donald is the Head of Programme at Agreeena, where she leads the development of high-integrity soil carbon certification projects. With a PhD in agricultural science and a background in sustainability leadership, she drives Agreeena's strategy for Verra-verified carbon farming.
- **Marco Alves:** Marco Alves is the Programme Modelling Lead at Agreeena, where he develops models to quantify soil carbon and greenhouse gas emissions. He holds a PhD in agricultural sciences and has a background in climate impact research and regulatory affairs.

Keynotes:

- Monitoring, Reporting and verification in Europe – In the framework of the CRCF regulation
 - By Tessa van der Voort – *NMI Wageningen*
- Agreeena's Approach: Calculation Soil Carbon Change
 - By Roberta McDonald & Marcos Alvez – *Agreeena*

Summary of session:

This panel discussion brought together experts from remote sensing, agricultural consultancy, data science, and farming practice to examine how carbon flows can be effectively tracked and verified within the European context. Moderated in a dynamic, solutions-oriented format, the session delved into approaches for addressing current data gaps, reducing the burden of MRV on farmers, and harmonising methodologies across land types and use cases.

Discussions highlighted the complexity of implementing advanced monitoring systems while ensuring they remain affordable and usable by farmers and cooperatives. There was also strong emphasis on aligning MRV tools with certification frameworks like the EU's CRCF, so that data gathered can serve multiple purposes—compliance, incentives, transparency, and long-term ecosystem monitoring. The speakers emphasised the importance of cross-sector collaboration to break silos between

researchers, practitioners, and policy implementers.

Key learnings from plenary 2:

- **Data quality and accessibility remain a critical challenge:** Speakers agreed that meaningful carbon accounting begins with robust, ground-truthed data – but that such data is often inconsistent or unavailable across regions and ecosystems.
- **MRV systems must be scalable and cost-effective:** Overly technical or expensive systems are unlikely to see uptake, particularly by smallholder farmers. Simplification, user-friendliness, and local context were identified as key design principles.
- **Standardisation without rigidity is essential:** While different ecosystems require tailored approaches, stakeholders need harmonised protocols that enable comparability, transparency, and integration with broader EU policies.
- **Co-benefits tracking is gaining momentum:** Carbon sequestration alone is no longer enough. MRV systems are evolving to include metrics on biodiversity, soil health, and water retention to reflect the broader value of carbon farming practices.
- **Scenario modelling can complement measured data:** Validated, science-based models can help forecast carbon outcomes and inform planning but must be used in conjunction with reliable field data.
- **Integration with certification frameworks is vital:** To minimise duplication and maximise value, MRV tools should be interoperable across schemes and geographies – enabling “measure once, report many times” functionality.
- **Farmer-centric design and training are needed:** Farmers must be equipped and supported to engage with MRV systems. Without adequate advisory support and digital literacy, even the best-designed systems risk underutilisation.

This session underscored that the future of MRV is not just technological, but also deeply social and systemic. Trust, usability, and collaboration will be just as important as sensors and algorithms in building a functioning carbon farming ecosystem in Europe.

2.3 Plenary 3: Paving the Way Towards Climate Positive Agriculture: The Role of Innovating Farmers

Organiser: Tristano Bacchetti De Gregoris, SAE Innova, Spain

Objective:

To spotlight pioneering farmers who are leading the transition toward climate-positive agriculture, unpack their motivations, challenges, and experiences, and explore how they can act as “lighthouses” to inspire broader systemic change.

Panelists:

- **Sheila Damos:** Sheila Damos is a third generation farmer and a social entrepreneur in the agri-food sector and civic engagement field in Greece. Her key focuses lie within her lived physical and social environment, namely the farming and rural communities, and thus a systemic approach to enable transitions towards regeneration in a holistic way. Her dedication to soil and ecosystem restoration translates into her dedication to transforming the farming sector in Greece through the initiative “Regenerative Farming Greece”.
- **Mateusz Ciasnocha:** Mateusz Ciasnocha is a farmer from Poland on the mission of building a farmer-centric bridge between agricultural and climate policy. He lives his call to action through two businesses: the European Carbon Farmers and the Farm of Francesco. Mateusz is an Advisory Board member for the Foundation of the Economy of Francesco, the Laudato Si Action Platform at the Holy See and the EU Soil Mission.
- **Iain Tolhurst:** Iain Tolhurst has been at the forefront of the UK organic farming movement for almost 50 years. His 8-ha farm has won many awards, for its innovative approach to crop production utilising biodiversity at its heart to develop soil health and fertility. Long term monitoring of carbon and soil has shown the benefits of this system. The integration of crops, a systems approach to pest and disease management and biodiversity makes for a fascinating and durable agricultural system.
- **Rob Smith (Moderator):** Rob Smith is a hugely experienced broadcaster and host, having worked as a journalist and presenter on TV and Radio with the BBC in the UK for over 25 years. He is a passionate advocate for environmental protection, hosting the Talk on the Wild Side podcast that explores how we can balance human needs with sustainable practice.

Summary of session:

This energising roundtable placed farmer voices at the centre of the summit, amplifying real-world perspectives on regenerative agriculture. Moderator Rob Smith steered a grounded, values-led discussion between three innovative farmers from across Europe who each shared not only their practices but also their personal journeys into climate-positive farming.

Mateusz Ciasnocha (Poland) stressed the need for decision-makers and researchers to “visit the farmer,” underlining the gap between policy discourse and on-farm realities. He argued that every farmer is already a carbon farmer by nature of their role in the carbon cycle, and pointed to soil health – not carbon metrics – as the true heart of transformation.

Sheila Damos (Greece) reflected on the disconnect between farmers and institutional structures. She emphasised that impactful change often happens outside of EU programmes and schemes, and called for a deeper immersion into rural life to identify authentic leverage points. The term “carbon farming,” she noted, is largely unintelligible or irrelevant to many farmers in her region – advocating instead for a holistic, ecosystem-centred framing.

Iain Tolhurst (UK), a veteran of agroecological practice, championed biodiversity as both a guiding principle and a source of learning. “Let yourself be infused by biodiversity,” he

urged – recounting how his long-term relationship with soil life, such as earthworms, shaped his understanding of sustainable farming. For him, biodiversity is not a co-benefit – it’s central to the system.

The panel also explored their experiences with carbon footprint tools, reflecting both the empowering potential and the current limitations of such systems. Complexity, lack of farmer input in design, and insufficient advisory support remain barriers.

Finally, the session engaged with the Law of Diffusion of Innovation, noting that carbon farming is still in the innovator phase. Early adopters – like the farmers on stage – are not primarily driven by market signals or carbon pricing, but by a philosophy of stewardship and a desire to “do what is good for the planet.” Any system that fails to meet these innovators on their terms risks losing momentum before mainstream uptake can begin.

Key learnings from plenary 3:

- **Farmers are change agents, not policy recipients:** Their leadership, lived experience, and experimentation must be recognised, resourced, and reflected in policy and market frameworks.
- **Motivations go beyond money:** For innovators, regenerative practices are driven by ecological values, community health, and long-term resilience – not just financial return.
- **Language matters:** Terms like “carbon farming” may alienate some farmers. Communication should reflect the diversity of motivations, and place ecological integrity at the centre.
- **Early adopters need targeted support:** Innovators often operate without safety nets. Systems must value their risk-taking and contributions – not just through subsidies, but through visibility, validation, and peer learning.
- **Biodiversity and soil health are core to transformation:** These are not side benefits but fundamental drivers of successful regenerative agriculture.
- **We’re still early in the adoption curve:** Policymakers and designers must build systems attractive to innovators first – price alone won’t drive uptake.

This session powerfully illustrated that climate-positive agriculture begins not in Brussels boardrooms or satellite data, but in the hearts, hands, and fields of farmers. Their courage, insight, and commitment are already laying the path – now the rest of the system must follow.

2.4 Plenary 4: Policy Areas Relevant to Carbon Farming – Synergies and Tradeoffs

Organiser: Mathieu Mal, European Environmental Bureau (EEB)

Objective:

To examine the effect of the introduction of a new policy, the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming regulation, and its interactions with different policy areas that intersect with carbon farming in the EU, including climate, agricultural, and nature policy, as well

as financing and business regulation. The session aimed to explore how the different policies and instruments can learn or borrow from each other to maximise synergies and avoid tensions, resulting in a coherent policy mix that is conducive for robust carbon farming at scale.

Panellists:

- **Lucia Perugini:** Lucia Perugini is Expert on Carbon farming Certification and LULUCF at the European Environment Agency. PhD in forest ecology with scientific background in forestry and climate change. She worked at CMCC, Italy (2013-23), and was involved in several national and European research projects related to the LULUCF sector, carbon markets and relevant links between the scientific and policy communities. She was the Italian delegate at the UNFCCC negotiations (2003-23) dealing on issues related to CDM, agriculture, LULUCF and REDD+.
- **Hugh McDonald:** Hugh McDonald is a Senior Fellow at Ecologic Institute, applying an environmental economics lens to carbon farming and climate policy. His work focuses on nature-based climate mitigation, market-based instruments, and biodiversity finance. Within the CREDIBLE project, his work has focused on carbon farming and sustainability.
- **Andrew Voysey:** Andrew Voysey is Chief Impact Officer at Soil Capital, the agronomy firm that launched a regenerative agriculture transition programme certifying its climate impact in 2020. It is the longest running such programme in Europe and is designed to enable food and beverage firms to deliver proven Scope 3 reductions and more resilient supply chains. Concurrently, Andrew is on the Supervisory Board of the Cool Farm Alliance and a Strategic Advisor to the Sustainable Soils Alliance in the UK. Previously, he led the sustainable finance practice at the University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership and was an advisor on climate change to the Bank of England.
- **Alan Matthews:** Alan Matthews is Professor Emeritus of European Agricultural Policy at the University of Dublin Trinity College, Ireland. He is a former President of the European Association of Agricultural Economists and has been a member of Ireland's Climate Change Advisory Council.

Summary of session:

This high-level panel brought together leading voices in policy, science, and sustainable agriculture to unpack the interconnections, and sometimes tensions, between various legislative and market-based instruments relevant to carbon farming. As carbon farming gains traction in EU climate and agricultural policy, the need for policy coherence becomes increasingly urgent.

The session opened with a keynote speech by Alan Matthews who presented the potential for carbon farming under the current Common Agricultural Policy, the EU's leading land management policy that drives agricultural practices across the continent with about a third of the total EU budget.

Hugh McDonald stressed the need for mandatory sectorial climate targets to catalyse action, cautioning that voluntary action will only take us so far. He added that the potential of carbon farming to a large extent lies in making supply chains more resilient.

Lucia Perugini warned that the land sink has been on a downward trajectory for the past years, driven by increased harvesting and the effects of climate change that impede forests' capacity to absorb carbon. This stands in stark contrast to the ambitious LULUCF objective of increasing carbon sequestration, which many EU Member States are struggling to achieve. She raised the importance of the CRCF reaching a scale where it can feed into the national greenhouse gas inventories and improve monitoring of land carbon sequestration at national level.

Alan Matthews reiterated the need expressed by Perugini to increase the level of detail in the national inventories so that carbon farming can contribute to national targets. He also reflected on the questions around the potential and appropriate combined use of public and private finance.

Andrew Voysey provided insight on the blended finance question by referring to the fact that many countries, through their CAP strategic plans, only provide partial compensation to farmers for certain actions. In those cases, where for example only the capital expenditure has been covered by public funds, private sector funding could complement by covering for operating costs. Andrew also reflected on the promise of digitisation in farming, and the need for special attention for the properties of the units generated by the CRCF, ensuring that they would be suitable for use through different avenues.

Collectively, the panel emphasised that carbon farming must be embedded in a broader strategy that aligns policies and instruments by harmonising indicators and exchanging data between systems, making best use of public and private finance, while maintaining ambition and practical deliverability.

Key learnings from plenary 4:

- **A binding climate target** for the agriculture sector will allow farmers and the agri-food sector to plan ahead.
- **Carbon farming must serve a wider agenda:** It should be seen not only as a climate mitigation tool but as a mechanism for holistic change that regenerates landscapes, supports food systems, and strengthens rural economies.
- **Policy coherence is non-negotiable:** Misalignment across CAP, CRCF, LULUCF, Nature Restoration Regulation, Soil Monitoring Law, etc. risks undermining the environmental integrity and credibility of carbon farming efforts.
- **Carbon pricing is necessary but insufficient:** Financial incentives must be paired with safeguards to ensure practices deliver long-term climate and environmental benefits. Price premiums for additional sustainability can motivate farmers to take up more activities.
- **We need to build an interoperable system:** Standardisation, data transparency, equitable benefit-sharing, and effective use of public funding must guide how the private sector engages with carbon farming.

2.5 Plenary 5: The way ahead from a systemic transition approach with speakers from science, policy, farmers organisation and industry.

Organisers: Climate KIC and BSAG

Objective:

To reflect on the key outcomes of the summit from multiple stakeholder perspectives – including policy, science, industry, and farming – and to identify strategic priorities for enabling a systemic transition to climate-positive agriculture across Europe.

Panellists:

- **Kirsten Dunlop:** CEO of Climate-KIC. Kirsten brings over 30 years of experience in catalysing systemic transformation across academia, consulting, banking, and insurance. She is deeply committed to building a climate-resilient society and serves on multiple advisory boards, including the European Commission's ESIR expert group on the Economic and Societal Impact of Research and Innovation.
- **Saara Kankaanrinta:** Philanthropist, entrepreneur, and environmental activist. She is former Chair and Co-Founder of the Baltic Sea Action Group (BSAG) and Chair of the Carbon Action platform, Vice Chair of Natural Resources Institute Finland (LUKE), and Co-Founder of Soilfood Ltd and Q Power Ltd. She owns Qvidja Research Farm and Gullkrona Harbour in Finland. A nature columnist and co-author of two books, she was awarded an honorary doctorate in science by the University of Turku in 2022.
- **Gustavo Palerosi Carneiro:** Senior Vice President of BASF Agricultural Solutions for Europe, Africa, Middle East, and CIS. With over 20 years of experience across multiple continents, Gustavo is focused on digitalisation, sustainability, and value chain integration. He oversees BASF's Global Carbon Farming Program, which connects farmers, partners, and certification bodies. He holds an MBA from the University of São Paulo and a Bachelor's in Business from Fundação Armando Alvares Penteado.
- **Bill Callanan:** Assistant Secretary at Ireland's Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM). He leads on scientific advice for agriculture and the environment.
- **Thomas Duffy:** Irish farmer and former President of Macra na Feirme. An advocate for youth involvement and innovation in agriculture, with a strong focus on sustainable rural development.
- **Valeria Forlin:** Deputy Head of Unit at DG CLIMA since 2024, focusing on the land sector's contribution to climate action – including emission reductions, carbon sinks, and sustainable food systems. Previously worked at UCLouvain, where she completed a PhD in environmental economics and taught in the same field. She also worked on European space policies, particularly Copernicus.
- **Saskia Keesstra:** Senior Researcher at EIT Climate-KIC and Wageningen University & Research. Her expertise spans soil systems, landscape dynamics,

sustainable land and water management, and policy advice. She contributes to EU-level projects including the Horizon Europe Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe.”

Summary of session:

During the session, we asked the audience and the panellists several questions. The first question was: Do you think carbon farming will deliver on the needs of different stakeholder categories?

The second question was: As we can see at this summit, there is huge interest in this topic from a wide range of stakeholders. What is the main barrier to deliver carbon farming at scale?

Overall, the final plenary of the summit brought together a diverse group of high-level speakers to reflect on the three-day event and consider the road ahead. Moderated by Saskia Keesstra, the session framed carbon farming not as a stand-alone intervention but as part of a broader systemic transformation in agriculture, value chains, and land use.

Two Mentimeter polls helped guide the conversation. First, participants were asked whether they believed carbon farming could meet the needs of all stakeholder groups. This prompted reflections from the panel about the importance of designing carbon farming systems that are inclusive, credible, and responsive to ground-level realities.

The second poll asked the audience to rank the greatest barriers to scaling carbon farming, distributing 100 points across issues such as policy incoherence, financial risk, lack of advisory support, and data complexity. These results framed a rich discussion on the challenges, and possibilities, of moving from pilot projects to mainstream adoption.

Panellists echoed one another on the need for collaboration beyond silos, emphasising that change must involve actors who don't typically work together. From policy makers and researchers to corporations and farmers, all must contribute to – and benefit from – the transition. Kirsten Dunlop underscored the urgency of systems thinking, while Saara Kankaanrinta and Thomas Duffy brought attention to the on-the-ground realities for farmers and land stewards, including their desire for fair market prices over dependency on subsidies.

Gustavo Palerosi Carneiro highlighted the growing commitment of agri-business to support regenerative practices, while Valeria Forlin reassured the audience that the European Commission is taking stakeholder feedback seriously in shaping the future of land-use and climate policy.

Key learnings from plenary 5

- **Systemic thinking is essential** – Tackling carbon farming in isolation won't work. Stakeholders must collaborate across sectors and disciplines to drive meaningful transformation.
- **Low-hurdle, fast-action pilots to learn and scale faster, and partnerships to accelerate change** – Engaging large industries and aligning public and private action can scale innovation and impact.
- **Policy is evolving, but needs real-world anchoring** – Institutions like the European Commission are listening, but coherence, clarity, and flexibility are needed to ensure implementation works for farmers.
- **Farmers want value, not dependency** – Panellists stressed that many farmers would prefer fair and stable market prices over increasingly complex subsidies.
- **Trust and legitimacy are non-negotiable** – The carbon farming transition must be transparent, fair, and rooted in shared understanding between all actors.

This closing session affirmed the summit's core message: carbon farming is a catalyst for change – but success depends on embracing complexity, listening across boundaries, and designing for impact at scale. A recurring theme throughout the summit, particularly in sessions on farmers, food chains, and MRV, was the critical question of who pays: how to finance carbon farming and its associated monitoring systems, and how to justify and allocate those investments. The path forward must therefore be inclusive, science-based, grounded in shared responsibility – and underpinned by clear, fair, and sustainable funding mechanisms.

3. Content and recommendations from the sessions

3.1 Session 1: Scaling up Resilient and Inclusive Agricultural Value Chains - from policy to financing adoption of new practices

Main organisers: Livelihoods funds, Social Carbon Foundation, Treevaluation

Session description

This session explored strategies to advance resilient, sustainable agricultural value chains by addressing challenges in financing and adopting regenerative farming practices. With several industry leaders from Livelihoods, Equilibrium Lab, the International Platform for Insetting and Social Carbon Foundation identified key barriers, including financial risks for farmers, limited technical support, and unclear market incentives. The session highlighted the importance of systemic change through policy adjustments, financial innovation, and collaborative efforts across the agrifood sector to create inclusive, nature-positive value chains.

Key issues

Overcoming Barriers to Adoption, addressing challenges faced by farmers, agrifood companies, and consumers in adopting regenerative practices.

Innovative Financing for Sustainable Agriculture, including insetting strategies and payments for ecosystem services integrated into business strategies.

Strengthening Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) Defining key steps to implement scalable, high-integrity MRV systems across value chains - a case for Nature Stewardship approach

Session recommendations

The discussions yielded several key recommendations for policymakers, the financial sector, agrifood companies, and farmers:

1.1. Policy & Governance:

- Establish a long-term policy vision to encourage farmer investment in regenerative practices.
- Stabilize public funding and shift Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) payments to an outcome-based reward system.
- Integrate EU agricultural and environmental policies to minimize project and company risks.
- Drive adoption of the EU Carbon Farming Certification Framework to stimulate demand for insetting.

1.2. Field & Farmers:

- Ensure farmers have a voice in policy and industry decisions.
- Showcase proven business cases to overcome adoption barriers.
- Expand technical support tailored to local farming conditions.

1.3. Financial and Insurance Sector:

- Recognize land and nature as critical infrastructure and investment opportunities.
- Reduce crop- and climate-related portfolio risks by transitioning to nature-positive inputs and practices.
- Implement risk-sharing mechanisms across agrifood value chains.

1.4. Agrifood Sector Companies:

- Integrate regeneratively grown crops into core business models.
- Build long-term supplier relationships for resilient value chains.
- Engage suppliers in long-term sourcing relationships.
- Pool resources for high-integrity insetting initiatives.

1.5. Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV):

- Expand MRV frameworks beyond carbon to reward holistic land stewardship.
- Develop pragmatic, digital MRV systems that improve value chain cost-efficiency.
- Ensure data collection provides direct value to farmers.

3.2 Session 2: Low hanging (tree) fruit – reaping forest-based carbon removal potential, identifying challenges and gaps to open doors to forest management solutions

Main organisers: I4CE, Climate KIC

Session description

The carbon removal potential in our managed forests is important, and the full picture only emerges by integrating forests in a landscape approach among other land uses such as agriculture. We already have almost all the tools needed to realize this potential, and the CRCF regulation is a great opportunity to share a common and high-quality EU

standard. However, forestry projects imply specific characteristics (long time horizons, slow growth of trees, strong exposure to natural disturbances...) and so specific concerns in terms of carbon certification. By discussing pioneering projects across the EU, this session strives to bring together the voices of practitioners and carbon markets experts to highlight the forest side critical points to align the supply of forest carbon credits with market demand.

Key issues

Baselines are the main risk for carbon finance credibility and the main sources of over-crediting for forest projects come from a bad baseline definition. We need to ensure the robustness of baselines, while being able to adapt to different local contexts. Specific and generic baselines have been discussed a lot.

Forest long term horizon and non-permanence risk : which tools to use and how to ensure a robust market? How to ensure there is demand for forest credits?

Diversity of Improved Forest Management practices in Europe require adapted and tailored certification criteria (baseline...).

Recommendations

2.1: Proposal to improve CRCF

Context: Baseline is the key element for a robust certification framework: It represents the primary source of over-crediting risks and has been at the heart of past controversies in forest carbon certification. Baselines set the context for data requirements and thus for the administrative burden. A key question arises: to what extent can a standardised baseline provide specific parameters to match local conditions?

Recommendation: Methodologies should be prescriptive and standardised enough in terms of baseline and data management to limit the inputs from project developers, while ensuring the use of local data whenever possible.

A key take-away from the session is the need for semantic clarification, where “specific” or “standardised” can refer to different realities according to the stakeholders involved. If the main parameters of baseline are set within the methodologies, it allows to limit bias (information asymmetry between the regulator and project developer) and reduce costs, as it limits the work required from project developers and simplifies audits. However, it still needs to be as adapted to local conditions and rely as much as possible on local data, when they are available, and fulfil necessary criteria such as minimum precision, science based/ sourced from acknowledged third parties. High tier project based local data can always be used within a "standardised" way to meet local consistency while ensuring project developers can not pick and choose what/how data is used or making arbitrary assumptions.

There is already very robust data available with strict MRV and 3rd party-verification, in some countries like Austria, Germany, Slovenia or Sweden. Beyond ground-based inventories, some Member States also provide remote sensing data, such as airborne LiDAR which offers detailed three-dimensional information on forest structure. Finally, the inherent risk of windfall effect associated with standardised baselines needs to be addressed. Discount could be applied when useful to limit the overall risk of

over-crediting.

To whom: CRCF and EC

2.2: Open question

Context: Temporary credits raise doubt about certificates' attractiveness on the market.

Recommendation: Ensure the **attractivity of “temporary credits”**, by **1) changing the name and 2) exploring avenues beyond voluntary funding**.

The risk of non-permanence is a crucial risk for forest credits, and CRCF should be transparent about it. However, temporary is not the only criteria to define those certificates, which also have other benefits that permanent certificates might not have: positive impacts on biodiversity, soils, water, lower costs than technological removals. Forest certificates also have a value in terms of carbon: climate change has to be mitigated now, and positive impacts on 30-40 years still have value, even though we cannot guarantee it will last 1000 years. A positive terminology **and a communication strategy** need to be defined to be transparent about permanence but highlighting other benefits, to ensure nature-based projects are actually financed.

High integrity credits provided; appropriate use cases have to be facilitated in corresponding regulations. For example, the new contribution paradigm can be used to stream private funding to Nature based certificates if clearly stated in the Green Claim Directive.

Finally, we doubt that voluntary demand alone will allow to scale those removals, especially nature-based ones, so we need to focus on other sources of funding for natural removals: public funds, compliance demand. As proposed in the recent report published by ESABCC, specific targets for “Temporary Carbon Credits” should be established.

To whom: CRCF and EC in methodologies development

2.3: Proposal to improve CRCF

Ensure funding opportunities adapted to forest projects:

1) Address the time lag between investment in forests (e.g., plantation costs) and long-term climate benefits by allowing and encouraging **up-front financing** for the practices that requires it (e.g. afforestation, reforestation, forest restoration). Given the long timeframes inherent to forestry, pre-financing mechanisms should be structured over several decades.

2) Ensure the **most performant projects** on sustainability criteria (biodiversity, water, soils...) actually **benefit from a premium carbon price**, to encourage them.

To whom: CRCF and EC

2.4: Proposals to improve CRCF

Support a **variety of management options**, especially no regret strategies which provide long-term benefits but also do not imply a huge carbon debt, as well as present benefits for other ecosystem services. Given the diversity of contexts in Europe, there is **no one-size-fits-all methodology for improved forest management**. Biophysical parameters but also socio-economical (active vs inactive forestry and size of properties) are parameters to consider to build targeted methodologies. Options to support methodologies that reward risk-mitigation strategies (e.g., fire prevention, pest control) should be explored, even if they do not result in immediate carbon gains, to enhance long-term forest resilience. Forest methodologies need to take into account the specificities of harvested wood products in order to 1) promote the creation and use of long-life wood products 2) ensure coherence with the methodology ‘carbon storage in buildings’.

To whom: CRCF and EC

2.5: Proposal to improve CRCF

Ensure attractiveness of CRCF for small forest owners (average private parcel in Europe is 12.7 ha, with many owners with parcels below 1 ha), by providing understandable and easy-to-apply methodologies: a balance is needed between scientific robustness and go-to-market strategy to make it attractive and profitable for forest holdings. Supporting the integration of carbon markets with broader land-use policies to maximize synergies between climate action and sustainable forest management will also help the involvement of stakeholders. There is no need to reinvent the wheel: sustainability criteria already exist in existing regulations (Taxonomy, Nature Restoration Law...) and in sustainable forest management standards (PEFC, FSC).

To whom: CRCF and EC

2.6: Recommendation for action

Context: Forest-based carbon certification in Europe faces diverse biophysical, socio-economic, and institutional challenges. Continuous, cross-sectoral dialogue is essential to co-develop solutions that reflect this complexity. The Carbon Farming Summit demonstrated the value of multi-actor discussions and highlighted stakeholders’ desire for ongoing engagement beyond singular events.

Recommendation: Establish a dedicated and recurring forum for forestry stakeholders—public and private forest owners, certifiers, researchers, policymakers, and carbon market actors—to co-develop and test methodologies, share best practices, and align efforts. This space should be structured yet flexible, with thematic working groups (e.g., on smallholder access, buffers, fire resilience) and regular feedback loops to feed into CRCF guidance and methodology development. Such a forum can foster trust, improve implementation, and ensure that forest carbon solutions are grounded in real-world forest management contexts.

To whom: CRCF and EC

3.3 Session 3: Income Opportunities from Peatland Rewetting: Carbon Credits, Ecosystem Service Payments and Paludiculture value chains

Main organiser: Greifswald Mire Centre

Session description

This interactive session explored the income opportunities available to farmers after rewetting or during restoration of drained peatlands on agricultural lands. Farmers, value chain actors and other interested stakeholders were invited to dive into the topic of paludiculture, carbon farming ecosystem services payments, and landscape regeneration. Participants explored practical strategies to boost peatland rewetting and paludiculture, to leverage carbon credits and international carbon schemes, and to address challenges and market demand for paludiculture products.

Issues:

- Income Opportunities from Peatland Rewetting
- Challenges in Market Development for Paludiculture Products
- Practical Implementation of Carbon Farming and Policy Support

Recommendations

3.1: Establish Financial Support Mechanisms for Farmers

- Governments and financial institutions should provide targeted funding (subsidies, low-interest loans, grants) to support farmers transitioning to paludiculture and carbon farming.
- Develop risk-sharing mechanisms, such as insurance for yield losses to provide farmers with confidence in rewetting investments.
- Use early carbon credit revenues to bridge financial gaps until markets mature. For paludiculture to succeed, demand must be stimulated, and farmers need long-term security that someone will buy the biomass.
- Support exploratory rewetting, allowing farmers to reverse decisions after trial periods. This approach has proven effective in increasing participation and helping farmers recognize the long-term benefits.
- Facilitate farmer collaboration of farmers/landowners with private sector peatland restoration project developers who register the project under a carbon standard to generate carbon credits and create payments to the farmers/landowners.
- Provide financial support for testing the viability of Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES) schemes (it takes about 4 years to implement 1 pilot scheme)

To whom:

1. National governments and EU policymakers (Common Agricultural Policy, Green Deal initiatives).

2. Ministries of Agriculture, Environment, and Finance.
3. Banks and financial institutions supporting green investments.
4. Private sector through payment for ecosystem services and peatland restoration project developers

3. 2: Strengthen Market Development for Paludiculture Products

- Invest in developing paludiculture value chains, ensuring stable demand for paludiculture crops such as cattail, reed, peat moss, and wetland biomass for bioenergy.
- Offer price guarantees and long-term contracts (minimum 10 years) to de-risk investments.
- Support pilot projects that connect farmers with value chain actors to demonstrate the economic viability of paludiculture products.
- Develop standardized peatland baselines to reduce costs, ease the burden on farmers and project developers, and thus support CRCF uptake.
- Encourage the use of existing farming machinery with modifications rather than requiring entirely new equipment, reducing transition costs.

To whom:

1. Agribusinesses, food processors, and bioeconomy industries.
2. Retailers and consumer goods companies.
3. Policymakers working on sustainable agriculture and bioeconomy strategies.

3.3: Improve Capacity Building and Knowledge Sharing for Farmers

- Establish farmer training programs to provide hands-on guidance on peatland rewetting, carbon credit certification, and paludiculture best practices.
- Provide subsidies for training of the trainers to teach about paludiculture crops and techniques. Agricultural consultants play a crucial role in supporting the farmers, providing expert advice and services.
- Establish regional knowledge hubs for farmer-to-farmer learning and technical assistance. As there is a lack of practical experience among farmers, good information on best practices is essential for a faster uptake of paludiculture crops.
- Develop decision-support tools to help farmers assess the financial viability of different paludiculture options.
- Strengthen networks between farmers, researchers, and policymakers.
- Increase practitioner involvement in policy discussions to ensure real-world relevance.
- Develop full-scale demonstration farms (e.g., 40 ha) to show paludiculture at commercial scale while also supporting smaller-scale, diverse models.

To whom:

1. Agricultural extension services and advisory bodies.
2. Ministries of Agriculture, Environment, and Finance.

3. Research institutions and universities.
4. Farmer associations, cooperatives, and NGOs.

3.4 Session 4: Exploring carbon farming approaches: integrating circular solutions from biomass production & treatment to soil health and carbon sequestration

Main organisers: Agrimercarb, European Compost Network, Re-Cord, TGO AG, TierraSphere

Session description

The session presented different innovative and best-available techniques for transforming organic biomass and biowaste materials into valuable products (insect frass, compost, biochar), while locking carbon into the soil for the long term. The session also highlighted examples of how to integrate recycled materials into sustainable carbon farming practices to improve soil health and generate financial benefits for farmers. The discussion focused on the challenges to scale up innovative processes and to reach higher acceptance of the use of these waste-derived materials by farmers and consumers. A critical view of monitoring and verification methods for carbon credits was considered, covering both established and emerging approaches. Based on the discussion, the session provided recommendations on how biomass and biowaste-derived recycled materials can be sustainably used and how their use can be taken into account for restoring carbon under the Certification Framework for Carbon Removals.

Issues:

- How to transform organic waste materials into valuable organic products used by farmers?
- How to promote the beneficial use of recycled bio-based materials in carbon farming?
- How can these recycled products and processes be integrated into carbon removals practices?
- How can carbon removals be properly accounted for, ensuring the development and implementation of solid carbon credit markets?

Recommendations

4.1. Concrete step for implementation

The black soldier fly (BSF) frass is a nutrient-rich organic fertilizer that improves soil fertility. It also increases soil organic matter and microbial activity. Its rapid decomposition cycle and nutrient retention capabilities make it a viable alternative to synthetic fertilizers. The BSF frass can be integrated into carbon farming frameworks by:

- Incentivizing adoption by farmers in the form of some tax exemptions or breaks etc.,

- Focussing on quantifying and certifying the carbon sequestration potential of BSF to increase its recognition in the carbon credit market and importantly,
- Demonstrating farmers how BSF frass can enhance soil organic matter and nutrient cycling.

To whom: Farmers, policymakers and researchers

4.2. Concrete step for implementation

- Incentivise the use of compost by farmers (ensuring that farmers currently using organic fertilisers will not be penalised by the future EU carbon farming certification)
- Increase communication on its benefits (communication and transparency from compost producers about the safety of their product despite deriving from waste, and need of support from policy makers to ensure product's compliance with national or EU regulations).
- Setting up quality assurance labels for compost.

To whom: Policy makers, compost producers, farmer advisories.

4.3. Concrete step for implementation

- Create market conditions to stimulate biochar production and use, in combination with compost, by farmers.
- Address both voluntary and obligated (EU ETS) markets.
- Implement solid monitoring actions to ensure product characterization and third-party verification of actual deployment in soil
- Create market instruments balancing offer and demand, ensuring value of BCR (Biochar Carbon Removals)

To whom: Policy makers and regulators

4.4. Lessons learnt

To establish carbon farming as a viable, profitable, and scientifically verified climate solution, a holistic Smart Carbon Farming (SCF) model that integrates precision monitoring, scalable sequestration strategies, and financial viability for farmers is proposed:

- Validated Carbon Farming Models for Scalable CO₂ Sequestration
- Precision Carbon Monitoring & Transparent Verification (MRV)
- Monetizing Carbon Farming for Farmers & Market Integration
- Building Trust Through High-Quality Certification & Open-Source Data

To whom: Farmers (Implementation of precision carbon farming methods), Carbon markets & financial institutions (Secure long-term value for removals), EU policymakers & CRCF certifiers (Aligning Smart Carbon Farming with EU regulations), Tech & research institutions (Further development of MRV automation).

4.5. Open questions

- Include inorganic carbon in CRCF discussions.
- Incentivize novel, holistic approaches that store carbon durably using residual biomass & waste, beyond current methods.
- Foster open communication to balance trade-offs in biomass use across sectors and carbon methodologies.

To whom: Policy makers

3.5 Session 5: Bringing carbon farming from science to organic and regenerative farms: Challenges and solutions across research, markets, farmer-led models and policy.

Main organisers: FIBL, Justus Liebig University Giessen, ReGeneration, National Association of Producers for Organic and Regenerative Agriculture, IFOAM Organics Europe

Session description

As carbon farming gains momentum in the fight against climate change, translating carbon farming into practical farm-level applications and financing mechanisms remains challenging. This session explored the complexities of carbon farming through the lenses of research, market-driven carbon credit systems, and farmer-led initiatives. The organisations presented their work related to carbon farming in particular on organic and regenerative farms. In the second part, a panel discussed the challenges ahead for carbon farming and potential solutions to support farmers in adopting climate- and eco-friendly farming.

Issues

1. Methodological challenges and the way forward, considering differing farming systems, e.g.:
 - Practice-based vs. measuring-based
 - Alignment of requirements for insetting / offsetting: Full farm approach
 - Methodological inclusion of other
2. Considering 1. from a scientific, market and political point of view
3. Alternative solutions to a carbon credit market

Recommendations

5.1. Proposal to improve CRCF

Alignment with the most robust international methodologies to establish a strong framework that meets market expectations and maximizes value for farmers, supporting their transition. This includes:

- **Baseline:** Guarantees equal treatment of project-specific baselines to the standardised baseline, with the inclusion of a provision allowing operators the flexibility to choose between standardised baselines and activity-specific baselines in all circumstances.
- **Offset & Inset Use Cases:** Provide clear guidance for both intervention and inventory accounting to allow carbon unit issuance for various end uses.
- **Activity & Monitoring Period:** The developing methodology should require a minimum permanence period of 40 years (activity and monitoring period combined). Ensure the quality and permanence of carbon credits and allow sufficient time for regenerative farming transitions to deliver tangible benefits.

Other important aspects to consider in the regulatory framework:

- **Co-benefits:** Biodiversity and water (infiltration and pollution) should have their own methodologies and certification to properly value the overall environmental contributions of regenerative farmers.
- **Early adopters:** Create incentives to reward farmers for continuing to store carbon over time, even after sustainable practices have been in place for a long period and carbon storage has reached its maximum capacity.

To whom: EU Commission / Policy Makers

5.2. Proposal to improve CRCF

Move towards practice-based compensations (e.g. reduced tillage) instead of result-based compensation (e.g. SOC sampling as baseline and improved practice) which have cross-benefits to other sustainability dimensions (e.g. for biodiversity, reduction of nutrient leakage) to acknowledge the efforts of climate-friendly soil pioneers.

To whom: EU Commission, Policy Makers, Voluntary carbon market actors

5.3: Proposal to improve CRCF

Integrate other aspects (such as biodiversity, water management, production and socio-economic aspects) into the CFCR regulation as a tool for farm assessment and monitoring, in addition to soil carbon sequestration. This will allow farmers to have a complete picture of their farms, enabling them to build a solid and robust transition plan towards more climate resilient farming. Sole focus on sequestration can be detrimental to other farm-focuses.

The CRCF should ensure that carbon farming contributes to biodiversity and ecosystem protection and ensure that no practices are applied that harm other environmental dimensions. The mandatory co-benefit for biodiversity should either be assessed by several clear indicators for above and below ground biodiversity or by outlining a list of practices and farming systems for which there is clear scientific evidence for the contribution to biodiversity and ecosystem health and exclude practices that harm biodiversity.

To whom: EU Commission / Policy Makers

3.6 Session 6: Carbon Farming, assured profitability? How to ensure the long-term sustainability of Practices

Main organisers: ECAF, EURAF, University of Cordoba, University of Greifswald

Session description

The adoption of carbon farming practices is an important tool to combat climate change, improve soil health and promote agricultural sustainability across Europe. However, its long-term success depends on overcoming significant challenges, including economic feasibility, technical complexity, cultural acceptance and policy alignment. The session identified key strategies to ensure the sustainable implementation of carbon farming practices across Europe, bringing together different stakeholders (farmers, researchers, scientists, policy makers, NGOs and companies) to co-create actionable strategies to address these challenges.

The session was a co-creation workshop addressing specific issues, such as the lack of clear economic incentives, the complexity of measuring the benefits of carbon sequestration and the lack of technical knowledge among farmers. By bringing together practical experience, scientific evidence and policy perspectives, concrete solutions were discussed on the following topics

- Models for adapting carbon farming practices to the diversity of European pedoclimatic zones to ensure their success.
- Economic and environmental strategies to ensure the viability of the implementation of carbon farming practices.

Issues

1. Long-term success of carbon farming practices
2. Lack of clear economic incentives
3. The complexity of measuring the benefits of carbon sequestration

Recommendations

6.1. Lesson learnt

Incentivising long-term commitment to carbon farming

Reversing carbon farming practices can quickly undo their environmental and climate benefits. The long-term success of these practices requires financial stability, clear long-term benefits, and consistent support policies. Incentives should not only target new adopters but also reward early adopters and long-term practitioners to avoid disincentivizing those already engaged.

To whom: Policy makers, public administrations, and farmers and end users

6.2. Lesson learnt

Support economic sustainability through diversified incentives and fair market access

Carbon farming practices can only be sustained long term if they are economically viable for farmers. Beyond environmental benefits, policies must help build resilient economic models by supporting early adopters, facilitating access to local and regional markets (e.g. for paludiculture or agroforestry products), and combining public subsidies with blended finance mechanisms. Recognising the time and risk investment involved in system change is essential to maintain farmer engagement and ensure long-term sustainability.

To whom: Policy makers, public administrations, and farmer organisations

6.3: Concrete step for implementation

Develop tailored methodologies and remove legal barriers to ensure long-term carbon farming adoption

The successful implementation and long-term maintenance of carbon farming practices require methodologies adapted to different land uses and regional conditions. Standardized approaches may fail to capture the variability in pedoclimatic zones, land tenure systems, or farming structures. Policies should promote flexible frameworks that allow for local adaptation while ensuring reliable monitoring, reporting, and verification systems. Additionally, legal barriers—such as restrictions on agroforestry integration, land tenure constraints, or limitations on peatland rewetting—must be addressed to enable farmers and landowners to adopt and sustain these practices without complex bureaucratic obstacles.

To whom: Policy makers, regulatory bodies, and land management authorities

6.4: Open question

Establish fair baseline methodologies to accurately measure carbon sequestration and soil health benefits

Measuring the benefits of carbon sequestration for soil health and productivity remains a major challenge. Reliable monitoring, reporting, and verification systems should not only quantify carbon stocks but also assess improvements in soil fertility, water retention, and resilience to climate stress. Additionally, ensuring a fair baseline is critical to avoid disadvantaging farmers who have already implemented sustainable practices. Current methodologies often compare landowners to their own historical data, which can penalize early adopters. A standardized yet flexible approach is needed to provide equitable incentives and facilitate the integration of carbon farming into market and policy frameworks.

To whom: Academia, research institutions, and policy makers

6.5. Concrete step for implementation

Improve access to technical knowledge and tools, and strengthen advisory services and peer-learning

The lack of technical knowledge and guidance remains a major barrier to the adoption and long-term maintenance of carbon farming practices. Farmers and landowners need continuous support, not only during the implementation phase but throughout the transition process. Policies should ensure the availability of advisory services that assist end users in decision-making, help resolve challenges, and provide technical guidance tailored to regional conditions. Additionally, peer-learning mechanisms should be promoted to facilitate knowledge exchange among farmers, enabling them to learn from both successes and failures in similar contexts.

To whom: Academia, advisory services, and agricultural training institutions

3.7 Session 7: CRCF business models

Main organisers: Agroinsider, Agrosolutions, Carbone Farmers, Reframe, Eleks

Session description

To effectively advance carbon farming, business models should be central to the discussion. Farmers can focus on food production, CO₂ retention, fostering nature, or pursuing all the objectives. However, without clear and objective guidelines defining the value of CO₂ or/and nature, meaningful behavioural changes among farmers are unlikely, potentially jeopardizing the success of the European carbon farming strategy.

The session aimed to explore the tangible impact of the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation on farm business models. How much compensation will farmers receive for the environmental services they provide? Will this value be sufficient to drive motivation, foster behavioural change, and support the transition of farms? What challenges might arise across Europe, considering variations in farm size, location, and production systems?

Issues

1. When comparing current food production business models to those centred on CRCF environmental services (CO₂), what strategies can effectively motivate farmers to shift their behaviour toward prioritizing these services?
2. How can farms of varying scales (large and small), production systems (dryland and irrigated, organic and conventional), and climates (Temperate and Mediterranean) develop sustainable business models that align with CO₂-related environmental services?
3. **Innovative farming business models** are essential to address trade-offs between food production, CO₂, and biodiversity. For example, could selling food with a reduced environmental footprint (in terms of CO₂, biodiversity, and other

metrics) at a premium price be a more viable alternative to selling CO2 credits in the market?

Recommendations

7.1. Lesson learnt

After analysing hundreds of soil samples and conducting tree measurements in an agroforestry system as part of a European project, the following conclusions were drawn:

- i) On average, soil carbon sequestration services can store between 0.5 and 1.0 tons of CO2 per hectare per year in a Mediterranean climate and between 1.0 and 2.0 tons of CO2 per hectare per year in a temperate climate, provided that best agricultural practices are implemented.
- ii) On average, forest carbon sequestration services can capture between 2.0 and 5.0 tons of CO2 per hectare per year.

Considering the current international CO2 price of 5 to 10 €/ton, farmers could generate 10 to 20 €/ha annually from soil carbon services and 20 to 50 €/ha annually from forest carbon services.

However, when compared to the minimum baseline revenue from food production, which is approximately 300 €/ha annually, it is evident that the current CO2 price is insufficient to make carbon farming and agroforestry systems (CRCF) economically attractive.

To bridge this gap, the CO2 price would need to rise to approximately 150 €/ton to provide competitive incentives for farmers to adopt these practices.

7.2. Open questions

Small-scale farms face real barriers in entering the Carbon Credits market, from high costs and administrative hurdles to low interest from carbon platforms due to smaller volumes. Often, traditional systems that reward carbon footprint reductions overlook essential regenerative practices, like promoting biodiversity and enhancing soil health, which are core to sustainable farming but rarely credited. We want to explore the limitation of the **Carbon Credit Market as an incentive for small scale farmers to transition to more regenerative practices**, based on the Case Study of Juntos Farm located in Ibiza, and discuss pathways to change.

7.3 Concrete steps for implementation

Clear and verifiable criteria for carbon farming practices are required that will qualify for the “Carbon Farming Badge”.

A robust and transparent **certification process** is crucial to build consumer trust and ensure the integrity of the label. This standardisation should also consider variations in climate, farming practices, and regional contexts across Europe.

It is **important to educate consumers** about the benefits of supporting carbon farming through their purchasing choices. **Marketing and outreach campaigns** are needed to highlight the environmental and social benefits associated with products carrying the badge.

Training programmes for the farmers, providing technical assistance and ensuring access to relevant information and resources, are important to ensure that farmers have the knowledge to implement carbon farming practices. Additional support might include accessing financial resources to cover upfront costs associated with adopting carbon farming practices.

Governments must create a **supportive policy environment** for carbon farming, utilising financial incentives and robust regulations to ensure fairness, transparency, and consumer trust.

3.8 Session 8: Making carbon farming work for regions – outlining adaptation needs and opportunities

Main organisers: Baltic Sea Action Group, BEC Bioeconomy Cluster

Session description

This session drew from regional carbon farming initiatives and regional cases through stakeholder discussions and aimed to outline considerations for the European carbon farming framework that fits in different regional contexts and supports regional objectives. It emphasized the integration of multiple objectives of food production in the regional context, aiming to connect regional authority, industry and farmer views and interests. Regional initiatives and emerging Living Labs were introduced to provide both priority issues and lessons, as well as concepts and platforms for developing and piloting approaches that align both with local needs and the EU policy frameworks (e.g. CRCF). The session covered the opportunities using the EU EIP-AGRI Operational Groups, project networks and living labs to collect tested best practice knowledge.

Issues:

- Best ways to ensure that carbon farming schemes take into account and adapt to agronomic and landscape perspectives at regional level and contribute to local and regional objectives.
- Added values from publicly (government) lead initiatives to develop carbon farming capacities and knowledge on carbon farming scheme development and implementation so that specific regional contexts and needs are incorporated;
- Need to concretize values (economic, agronomic and environmental) for actors and secure needed knowledge and technical capacities.

Recommendations

8.1. Lesson learnt

CFS and national initiatives for carbon removal certification through carbon farming must adopt a multi-objective framework that supports sustainability transformation across various environmental, social, and economic dimensions. To achieve these targets, robust implementation and advisory structures are important, providing farmers with the guidance and resources needed to adopt sustainable practices successfully. A good idea is to encourage pioneers who started with CF early to become sample/pilot farms (lighthouses) and develop the mechanism to compensate these farmers for lessons-sharing, demonstration and advice. Learning from existing regional initiatives is essential for refining carbon farming strategies. An inclusive approach that engages food processors, retailers, and policymakers alongside farmers can create sustainable pathways for carbon farming that benefit all stakeholders.

For whom: authorities, agricultural AKIS, food industry

8.2. Concrete step for implementation

Instruments like EIP Operational Groups and Horizon Europe Living Labs create valuable opportunities to develop and test pilots that can address specific regional challenges, fostering innovation and collaboration within the agricultural community. They can be used to synthesize knowledge on regionally tested context adapted practices. These can also serve as a starting point for the development of group projects.

For whom: authorities, farmers' associations, research institutes

8.3. Concrete steps for implementation

Leveraging the public, government lead initiatives to develop carbon farming scheme capacities can help navigate sub-regional and regulatory diversity and tap into needed implementation and governance capacities. Empowering the local governments and stakeholders to innovate within a supportive national framework is essential for accelerating progress. It is essential to translate the EU Framework into actionable strategies for the regions.

For whom: farmers, carbon farming programme developers, carbon market actors, authorities

8.4. Lesson learnt

Communicate with farmers and foresters clearly and transparently the implications of carbon certification contracts and other commitments, such as sustainability incentive programs with the food industry. Selling carbon credits for compensation or to an external buyer voids any contribution to value chain or regional climate targets. Carbon credit markets present a significant risk, especially in the context of supporting local and regional needs and value chains. Very important is to maintain a holistic perspective (regions' and farmers' perspective) and clarify boundaries of the CRCF and define its incremental value.

For whom: farmers, carbon farming programme developers, carbon market actors, authorities

8.5. Concrete steps for implementation

Concretize the values (economic, agronomic, environmental, risk mitigation) for the land owners and practitioners to increase interest. Developing standardized methods for assessing carbon sequestration and biodiversity impacts across various agricultural contexts would facilitate greater transparency and trust in carbon farming initiatives. Understanding the socio-economic conditions that influence farmers' willingness to engage in carbon farming is crucial for designing effective incentive structures. Knowledgeable and holistic farm management advice can help find optimal way to incorporate carbon farming practises in order to maximize their agronomic and economic value.

For whom: agricultural AKIS, advisory services, project developers

3.9 Session 9: Farmers' prospect: How does carbon farming affect crop production, and farm biodiversity and profitability?

Main organisers: CREAM

Session description

It has often been said that carbon farming is at odds with crop and pasture productivity. However, many innovative farmers have taken the plunge of modifying their management strategies to embrace sustainability by sequestering carbon in soils and vegetation. Changes from intensive to sustainable agriculture can be more or less far-reaching, and ranges from adopting single practices (e. g. tillage reduction/elimination, cover crops) or combinations of several of them to modifying drastically the economics, organization structure and social ethics at a scale that exceeds that of the farm. This session dedicated to farmers' view of this debate was organized with farmers and farmer associations to explain their experience with farm productivity and profitability and with conserving or enhancing environmental services in their farms.

Questions brought to the discussion where (a) in which direction science and technology should progress to support farmers in optimizing global environmental and monetary benefits while adopting C farming strategies, (b) what kind of partnerships are needed to optimize the benefits of carbon farming for farmers and which stakeholders should be involved? (c) which realistic indicators can be proposed to evaluate success in carbon farming adoption at the farm scale?

Issues

- The indicators currently used to evaluate farmer's satisfaction and willingness to adopt C farming are not satisfactory
- Environmental constraints to adopt carbon farming are region-specific, as is the effort required to obtain a carbon credit
- Shortage in biomass of good quality can limit carbon farming at the European level and, in particular in dry regions
- Carbon farming practices can be at odds with biodiversity protection at the landscape scale if current demand for animal food remains stable.

Recommendations

9.1. Choose correct indicators to evaluate farmer's satisfaction and willingness to adopt C farming

- Farm profitability (instead of crop yield) and farm global resilience are crucial for farmers to adopt carbon farming.
- Profitability must be evaluated under an integrated WEFE Nexus concept. Short term valuations can produce high costs vs long-term evaluations, hopefully profitable (Timeline – local specificity)
- Our focus group strongly advocates for a holistic management plan, covering the period necessary for the adaptation of crops to the new form of management, before the implementation of carbon projects. A correct economic valuation of the farm profitability during this period (including inversions, and yield decline but also savings associated with reduced use of agrochemical and commercial fertilizers will prevent misunderstanding about extra costs in the mid- and long-term.
- It is necessary to finance the transition period from conventional to regenerative management in which losses can occur.
- Carbon sequestration should not be pursued without taking into consideration the effects of the integrated management on biodiversity and environmental services (e.g. water quality, soil protection, etc.) provided by farmlands, that must be evaluated based on specific indicators
- Carbon programs must contribute to increased economic sustainability, not through further spread of subsidies, but through consolidation of the farm business.
- Income security and longer contracts must be guaranteed

To whom: Decision makers, researchers, farmers' advisors

9.2. Consider selective compensation for Carbon farming depending on constraints

- Farmers implementing C farming under adverse conditions (such as aridity, or soils) incur greater production losses during the period of crop adaptation, and this period lasts longer, than farmers operating under better conditions. In the same line, achieving the same increase in soil C will cost more effort under adverse conditions than under more favorable conditions. This will suggest negative discrimination for farmers operating under adverse conditions if we reward based on outcomes only. C credits should have different values depending on this difference
- Design region-based supporting actions to take into account spatial differences and reinforce training in the most threatening areas.
- It is not enough just to pay for C sequestration; compensations for increased resilience, environmental services (i.e. biodiversity, water retention) should also be used as levers. Actions aimed at C sequestration that have negative consequences on biodiversity and environmental services should be penalized, under the “Polluter pay” principle

To whom: Decision makers

9.3. Be sure that we have enough biomass of good quality to implement carbon farming practices on the European scale

- Support policies that facilitate the closing of organic matter loops at the farm and local level, ensuring sufficient biomass availability for carbon farming. Incentivize crop rotations, cover crops, animal integration, and agroforestry, with specific training programs for farmers.
- Support the transition to Mixed Farming Systems as a key strategy for organic matter cycling, ensuring a balance between crops and livestock. Develop financial and advisory support to assist farmers in transitioning towards sustainable mixed farming systems.
- Enhance agricultural sustainability and circularity. Invest in technologies for better organic matter management, such as composting innovations and precision nutrient management.
- Foster collaborative initiatives where farmers and stakeholders can share challenges and best practices for managing organic matter locally. Promote regional and cross-sector cooperation to develop local business models for organic matter valorization.
- Adopt a holistic and value chain approach: ensure that policies consider the entire value chain, from production to processing and reuse of organic matter. Address regional gaps where organic matter cycling businesses are lacking, supporting new circular economy initiatives.
- Improve biomass transport and storage efficiency: Support long-term composting to reduce organic matter water content, minimizing transport costs and inefficiencies.
- Align CRCF with organic matter cycling: Ensure that livestock and biomass considerations are integrated into carbon farming certification frameworks, addressing current gaps.

To whom: Decision makers, researchers, land managers and planners

9.4. How does the implementation of biodiversity measures affect farm profitability? How to improve it at the EU level

- Farmers are willing to move towards carbon farming if there is a demand for regenerative agriculture products. Carbon credits will also help, but farmers do not want their efforts to be sold to the same companies that cause damage to the environment.
- Biodiversity increases profitability in the context of disturbance, strengthens functional redundancy, and reduces risk. The CRCF methodologies should be designed such that they maximise biodiversity gains through carbon farming practices.
- Promote the diversification of farm production to increase agricultural biodiversity and help stabilize profitability. Biodiversity in crop types is the best way to have a buffer.
- Seek out policy coherence to enhance synergies between nature conservation and restoration and farm profitability: adapt the legal framework, reinforce CAP measures addressing integrated Ecoschemes.
- Coordinated efforts of the scientific community should be stimulated in order to find measurable indicators applicable to the farm scale.

To whom: Decision makers, land managers and planners

3.10 Session 10: The future of regional small-scale carbon farming projects: Discuss bottom-up experiences and align farmer and market perspectives

Main organisers: Boerenbond, ZLTO, Bax Company

Session description

While the rules and regulations on carbon farming are still taking shape (EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification (CRCF) Regulation), there are already many different certificates and certification methodologies in place. Each with their own set of rules and prices. Since 2020 farmers organisations, Boerenbond and ZLTO, are in lead or involved in local carbon farming rewarding mechanisms in Belgium and the Netherlands. They shared their field experience from 2 running examples of carbon farming projects and collected experience, concerns and solutions from the audience. With a new European certification regulation in development, the results of this workshop aimed to give small-scale initiatives a voice.

Issues

1. Experience sharing in the business model for small scale carbon farming projects with special attention for the point of view of participating and potential participating farmers as well as the buyers point of view
2. Policy recommendations necessary to convince both more farmers and buyers to participate in carbon farming (Ensure that CRCF will boost this market, provide clarity about (potential) interfering policies and make sure that first movers are involved and rewarded).

3. Concerns and recommendations in regard to CRCF MRV high costs and administration: Make sure that carbon farming remains financially feasible by keeping MRV costs low and make it feasible for farmers to meet the reporting demands. Clear recommendation: CRCF should foresee a separate, less heavy (and thus costly) certification system for these local initiatives

Recommendations

10. 1. Lessons learnt

FOR FARMERS

Be aware that farmers that are currently active in business cases for carbon farming are in it due to different reasons. Foremost due the intrinsic motivation of the benefits for their soils and thus farms. Next to this, farmers that participate in local small-scale collaborations value the one on one connection with their buyer(s), which creates a better mutual understanding and also a social appreciation. The financial incentive for CF is nonetheless crucial in order to be able to take their actions to the next level and in order to feel supported in their efforts.

In order to scale up the small-cases and to involve more local farmers, the financial incentive might take a bigger role in their consideration.

There is a big question mark and uncertainty in what is the best way to go forward: insetting vs. offsetting. For insetting cases, farmers have the fear that the financial incentive will be only available on a very short term basis and might also be lower in price setting.

FOR BUYERS

Participating buyers have a big appreciation for the local and personal aspect in small-scale carbon farming cases. They participate due to the contact they have with the farmers as well as it feels less risky because it is more tangible and nearby.

To whom: Regional and European policy makers and stakeholders in the agri-food chain and abroad.

10.2. Proposals to improve CRCF

1) Ensure that CRCF will boost this market:

CRCF is very welcome to create trust among potential buyers of carbon farming credits. If Europe creates this framework, it shows them that Europe believes in this potential. Yet, communication and clarity about the possibilities of CRCF to the industry will be of essence to make CF succeed.

2) Provide clarity about (potential) interfering policies:

Yet, both farmers as potential buyers have many questions regarding (climate) policy. How do the following policy actions and goals interfere with each other and how do we prevent future mistakes and potential penalties?

- Climate target goals for farmers
- AFOLU
- CRCF
- CSRD

Is there a difference in potential risk between insetting vs. offsetting?

3) Make sure that first movers are involved and rewarded

CRCF will also need to provide an answer to the following concern at farm level: Will farmers that have already worked on their soils and pioneered be able to participate in carbon farming? This will be very important in order to show to farmers that Europe also values the stored carbon and their past efforts.

To whom: CRCF and European policy makers that work on climate target goals, green deal, CSRD and AFOLU

10.3. Concrete steps for implementation

- Make sure that carbon farming remains financially feasible by keeping MRV costs low and make it feasible for farmers to meet the reporting demands
- Many small-scale cases have a big fear that CRCF will lead to high demands in regard to MRV, which will then result in both high costs as well as specific software to report. This will lead to the quitting of small-scale and local examples. Possible solution:
- CRCF should foresee a separate, less heavy (and thus costly) certification system for these local initiatives
- These small-scale initiatives are very valuable and we must prevent them from not being able to continue due to too high costs for MRV and too much administration.
- This separate system should focus on integrity and more room for frontrunners. In small-scale cases farmer and buyer know each other, so there is more transparency and less risk.

To whom: CRCF policy makers/developers and expert group

3.11 Session 11: The role of advisors in climate action in Europe

Main organisers: Teagasc, Consulai, Intiasa, ILVO

Session description

Farm advisors are positioned to play a crucial role in the agricultural transition, acting as the vital link between farmers, researchers and policymakers by translating policies and strategies into actionable practices while also providing valuable feedback from farmers to inform policy making and guide new research.

However, they require support and training to effectively fulfil this role, particularly in

emerging areas like carbon farming and carbon markets, where their current expertise is limited. Trusted by farmers, advisors already recommend climate smart practices but face challenges such as varying levels of knowledge across regions and the need to minimize the burden of data collection by reusing existing data effectively.

This session provided a comprehensive overview of the current role of farm advisors in climate action, while also identifying areas for future development, including advisor capacity building and the availability of user friendly decision support tools.

Issues

1. What motivates farmers to climate action?
2. How can advisors successfully engage and motivate EU farmers to climate action? What advisory skills are required and what are the training needs of EU farm advisors?
3. How can user-friendly, practical and accessible decision support tools be used by advisors and farmers? What are the key requirements of such tools?
4. What climate action rewarding mechanisms are currently available? How are these being promoted by farm advisors and used by farmers?

Recommendations

11.1. Lessons learnt

Understanding and Leveraging Farmer Motivation for Climate Action

Understanding the diverse motivations of farmers is key to effective advisory in promoting climate action. Farmers are motivated by a variety of factors, including financial incentives, autonomy, trusted sources of information, firsthand experience, emotional and cultural factors, and social proof through peer learning. Advisors must be trained to recognise and engage with these motivations, tailoring their advice to align with what drives each farmer. By addressing these motivations, advisors can encourage greater adoption of climate-smart practices and help build long-term sustainability on farms.

To whom: Advisory Services

11.2. Lessons learnt

Strengthening the Role of Farm Advisors in Promoting Climate Action

Farm advisors are key agents in the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) for promoting carbon farming.

To whom: National/Regional Governments

11.3 Concrete steps for implementation

Strengthening the Role of Farm Advisors in Promoting Climate Action

Advisors need structured training on the Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF) and relevant regulations.

To whom: National/Regional Governments

11.4. Lessons learnt

What do farm advisors need in order to support farmers with rewarding mechanisms?

- Farm advisors need access to knowledge and capacity building on carbon removal certification and carbon market tools, as well as on other rewarding mechanisms or incentives available to farmers.
- The level of awareness of rewarding mechanisms, the level of economic advisory skills, and the way farm advisors engage with farmers on financial topics vary across EU countries. As a result, the level of investment in capacity building needs to be adapted. In some cases, communication from rewarding entities (governments or value chain actors) should also be improved to make sure farmers and farm advisors are aware of potential funding and support.
- Clarity, transparency, credibility, and fairness are key for farm advisors and farmers to engage with rewarding mechanisms.
- Farm advisors need to be able to explain requirements, risks, and potential benefits linked to each rewarding mechanism, as well as how to use different mechanisms in combination. To do this, they need practical examples and rationales demonstrating clear added value to motivate farmers. They should also facilitate demonstration and peer-to-peer learning.
- In general, farm advisors need to be better equipped to help farmers calculate the cost of inaction, and to assess the economic effects (both positive and negative) of climate adaptation or mitigation measures in the long run, in their local context.

To whom: Advisory services, Governments, Value chain actors

11.5. Concrete steps for implementation

Developing and Deploying Practical Decision Support Tools: Advisors and farmers need user-friendly, practical, and accessible decision support tools.

To whom: Advisory services, National/Regional Governments

3.12 Session 12: Ensuring sustainability outcomes from carbon farming: Recommendations for the CRCF and voluntary carbon markets.

Main organisers: Ecologic Institute

Session description

This session discussed how the carbon farming certification can best ensure broader sustainability benefits, including climate adaptation and biodiversity conservation.

Carbon farming has significant potential to support the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices that contribute not only to climate change mitigation but also other sustainability objectives. The Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) aims to establish a new high standard for voluntary carbon farming actions, including minimum sustainability requirements.

In this session, these minimum sustainability requirements were discussed and recommendations were prepared on how they can best be put into action through the CRCF and in voluntary carbon markets.

Issues

- Enhancing sustainability through certification: How the carbon farming certification can best ensure broader sustainability benefits
- Increasing demand for sustainable farming: Is there demand for sustainability outcomes from carbon farming and where does it come from
- Supporting farmers through certification: How can certification enable farmers to deliver sustainability benefits alongside mitigation?

Recommendations

12.1. Proposals to improve CRCF

Carbon farming certification must support broad sustainability objectives. Carbon farming practices do not just affect the climate, they also impact other sustainability outcomes, including biodiversity, soil health, and water.

To whom: Policy makers

12.2. Concrete steps for implementation

To meet CRCF minimum sustainability requirements, farmers should complete a “farm environment plan,” which should be supported by a farm advisor, be low-cost for farmers, and support adoption of sustainable farming practices – without requiring it. In addition, a negative list of excluded high-risk actions could avoid carbon farming actions that pose high risks to sustainability.

To whom: Policy makers

12.3. Proposal to improve CRCF

To incentivise co-benefits beyond minimum requirements, the CRCF should support market price premiums by **creating a voluntary “CRCF Sustainability+” label**, based on farmer self-assessment of sustainability indicators, supported by random third-party audits. Additionally, the CRCF should support the development of robust and low-cost methods for voluntary quantification of sustainability impacts.

To whom: Policy makers

12.4. Proposals to improve CRCF

Consider the six principles for ensuring sustainability in the context of carbon farming:

1. **Holistic approach:** Carbon farming should incentivise a holistic and context-specific approach to farm management that promotes sustainable outcomes and avoids unintended negative sustainability impacts, whilst prioritising climate mitigation.
2. **Accessibility:** Participation costs for farmers must be minimised to ensure that it is financially attractive for farmers to implement sustainable measures. Financial support should be provided to early adopters of carbon farming practices, e.g. for advisory services and MRV, or in the form of offtake agreements.
3. **Pragmatism:** A pragmatic approach should be taken to ensuring sustainability through carbon farming certification to reduce the barriers to farmer participation and promote farmer uptake, e.g. integrating existing management and monitoring systems.
4. **Incentives:** Farmers should be rewarded for the sustainability impacts of carbon farming, which will be enabled by robust monitoring of impacts.
5. **Consistency:** Carbon farming certification approaches to sustainability should be consistent and comparable to facilitate market demand.
6. **Integrity:** Certification must deliver buyers robust sustainability impact information, using metrics and indicators that are valuable to them. The CRCF must also manage buyer claims, to ensure they align with the sustainability impacts delivered.

To whom: Policy makers

3.13 Session 13: Session 13: Global or local? Carbon certification centralisation level: what implications for stakeholders?

Main Organisers: Institute for Climate Economics (I4CE), AC3A

Session description

Numerous carbon farming certification schemes are already operating in Europe with stakeholders involved in certified projects. The CRCF is a great opportunity to gather funding for climate-compatible practices in the land-use sector and contribute to the agriculture sector transition. It will help harmonize and improve practices and create a larger market to reward farmers' actions. However, it raises the question of how to bring coherence and improvement at the EU level, while building on what already exists and keep involving the stakeholders who are already implementing carbon farming?

This session discussed the results of a survey by AC3A and I4CE to gather feedback from stakeholders on the implications of different scenarios of governance for the future carbon farming certification framework. The survey gathered their inputs on what would be the strengths and challenges of different centralisation options (very centralized at EU level, or relying on existing standards at national level or local level), for several certification steps: methodology creation, methodology validation, project validation, audits, GHG assessment tools, registry... It also asked for their general feedback on the conditions on which the CRCF would be attractive to farmers and buyers in those different scenarios.

Issues

Implications of different scenarios of governance for the future carbon farming certification framework.

Recommendations

13.1. Proposals to improve CRCF

RECOMMENDATIONS ON METHODOLOGIES

1. Set as many rules as possible in the common European methodologies to have them consistent across the EU and to make economies of scale: highly prescriptive methodologies reduce project development and auditing costs and limit the risk of bias and information asymmetry between the regulator and the project developer.

2. To be adapted to local issues/specificities and to have more room for innovation, specific protocols can be proposed by certification schemes but:

- The methodology developer must demonstrate the value of proposing this specific protocol
- Where the schemes operate, Member States have to be involved to ensure the credibility/robustness/independence/coherence with national regulations of the protocols.
- Protocols of different schemes operating in the same Member State must have the same level of requirement to ensure that operators do not play with the rule by choosing the most favorable one.

3. As UNFCCC reporting methodology differs among Member States, allow MS to refine methodologies with models or emission factors that are used in their LULUCF reporting to promote consistency between regulations.

4. As it is not possible to have everything right from the first time, ensure to have frequent review processes of the methodologies, involving independent researchers/consultants/experts.

13.2. Proposals to improve CRCF

RECOMMENDATIONS ON GHG ASSESSMENT TOOLS

GHG emission tools : Emission reduction calculator using models and parameters provided by methodologies and protocols.

- Tools are regularly audited to ensure that they take account of changes in methodologies and remain consistent.
- Tools are validated by the commission (equity between MS), on condition that sufficient resources and expertise are made available (economies of scale should make this possible), and after consulting the member states (especially for local tools).

13.3. Proposals to improve CRCF

RECOMMENDATIONS ON PROJECT VALIDATION

1. The more precise the rules, the lower the validation costs.
2. In this respect, more precise recommendations at the level of methodologies and protocols seem necessary to gain in precision, avoid any confusion and “gaming” and to lower transaction cost by facilitating project development.
3. Case of specific baselines : In the case where standardised baselines could not be implemented in the first years, project developers will use specific baselines and will need to demonstrate the choice of the baseline additionality. This needs more scrutiny from certification bodies. MS could play a role here to define parameters for additionality tests or to provide a list of credible specific scenarios within the country.

13.4. Proposal to improve CRCF

RECOMMENDATION ON THE REGISTRY

1. A unique European registry fully managed by the EC would allow economies of scale, avoid risk of double counting and facilitate the purchase of carbon credits by trans-EU companies.

13.5. Proposals to improve CRCF

1. It is crucial to dedicate a sufficient budget to remunerate independent experts and consultants who will have to scrutinize methodologies, perform checks on projects and certification bodies (=auditors)
0. There is a need to clarify the different possible processes from the methodology development to certification of removals emission reductions in detail in order to evaluate the feasibility, risk and cost of these options. But also to define the final governance scenario to bring visibility to existing standard

Recommendation 13.6. Proposals to improve CRCF

There is a need to consider the business model of the CRCF in order to refine the governance rules. Assessing the transaction costs of different governance scenarios and certification processes could help to find the right balance between robustness and

reasonable administrative burden. Identifying how each stakeholder in the process is remunerated will help to avoid conflicts of interest. Assessing the critical size of a group of farmers, for example, will also help to ensure that group certification is a good option for reducing the administrative burden.

3.14 Session 14: The Value Chain Challenge: Scaling Scope 3 Solutions

Main organisers: Mars Inc., Friesland Campinas, Lakeland Dairies, Soil Capital

Session description

It is increasingly clear that unlocking the potential of carbon farming will be key for the agri-food value chain to achieve their Science Based Targets initiative (SBTi) goals. Carbon farming contributes to compensating greenhouse gas emissions at farm level by removing CO₂ from the atmosphere and reducing GHG emissions from soils and hence will be part of the solution to achieve those targets. Yet there are still challenges for carbon farming and practices contributing to greenhouse gas reduction at farm level to scale.

This session brought together stakeholders from the dairy and cereal value chains that have committed to reduce their scope 3 emissions and are already taking actions to support farmers to achieve their reductions. Its aim was to discuss how a robust policy framework could contribute to further unlock the potential of carbon farming in the EU.

Issues

- What are the financial needs and available options for farmers to adopt carbon farming, and how can CRCF support this transition?
- What are the additional requirements and benefits from carbon farming, including soil health, biodiversity and environmental impacts, and how can these be reported and communicated transparently?
- How can existing and potential new policies and schemes contribute to scaling carbon farming (CAP, Green Claims Directive, CSRD, new policies to incentivize climate-change mitigation across the agri-food value chain)?

Recommendations

14.1. Funding of Carbon Farming

- Funding is key for scope 3 solutions to scale: whilst CRCF could help bring additional trust to private funding, it won't be sufficient. Considering public funding, by strategically leveraging CAP's budget from eco-schemes, EIB budget, public procurement will be key.
- Public funding should be designed and deployed to further attract private funding for instance by unlocking public-private partnerships to encourage value chain partnerships
- Moreover, public funds could support farmers in overcoming barriers to access the private market by making MRV and/or advisory services as a public service.

- Private funding would then complement those public fundings by rewarding the outcome.
- It will also be important to expand CRCF to other GHG to address other supply chains (e.g. dairy).

14.2. Improve CRCF and clarify use of certificates

- For carbon farming a value-chain approach should be prioritized, aligned with the GHG Protocol.
- Incorporation of the CRCF into existing legislations is needed:
 - CSRD – need to clarify rules for carbon sequestration achieved within value-chain/scope 3, aligning rules with international standard like GHG-Protocol
 - CAP – CRCF could be used as a standard under eco-schemes
 - Green Claims Directive – need to ensure rules are EU harmonized, simple and clear to keep incentivizing the private sector to invest into carbon farming.
 - Potentially future legislations (agriETS, mandatory scope 3 targets) should also consider CRCF
- For the purpose of CRCF and Green Claims it will also be important to consider international schemes from outside the EU, beyond CRCF.

3.15 Session 15: Insetting for Carbon Farming: Turning Challenges into Opportunities for Farmers, Food Companies and Policy Makers

Main organisers: Friesland Campinas, ILVO, Rabobank, UCLouvain, ZLTO

Session description

Insetting offers a credible alternative for scaling up carbon farming by enabling farmers to adopt practices that enhance soil organic carbon (SOC) sequestration. Offtakers integrate the sequestered carbon into the carbon footprint of products within the value chain. While insetting provides income opportunities for farmers, it also faces challenges like financial burden and administrative burdens for farmers and food value chain companies, and lack of market regulation. The European Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF) could establish essential standards for insetting, but must address all stakeholders' needs.

This session examined the implications of insetting for SOC sequestration in agriculture, providing a platform to share experiences and understand its practical application. Expert presentations explained insetting, how to engage, and explore the impact of available protocols, policies and MRV systems. It concluded by identifying stakeholder needs, highlighting gaps in the CRCF framework and Scope 3 protocol, and proposing actionable policy recommendations

Issues

Recommendations

15.1 Concrete steps for implementation

Companies should set targets and allocate budgets to achieve them, including mechanisms to reward farmers. Companies with voluntary commitments should implement these targets and budgets before project implementation. Standards and protocols could incorporate these criteria as part of the project description document.

To whom: Companies, policy by providing framework and guidelines, accounting standards setting like GHG Protocol

15.2. Proposal to improve CRCF

CRCF could represent an overarching scheme to support Insetting

- Establishing a unified framework for carbon farming, integrating offsetting, insetting, and CAP schemes.
- Creating a single registry to prevent double counting and improve claim tracking.
- Enhancing sustainability reporting with standardised and transparent methodologies.
- Leveraging public-private funding mechanisms to scale up insetting initiatives.

To do so, the panel session identified the following recommendations:

- Developing a universal benchmarking system for farm sustainability reporting.
- Clarifying insetting's role within the CRCF with clear rules on allocation and inventory accounting.
- Adopting a holistic sustainability approach that incorporates soil health, water conservation, and biodiversity.
- Defining the market demand for the CRCF and its role in emissions reduction efforts.

To whom: Companies, policy by providing framework and guidelines, accounting standards setting like GHG Protocol

15.3. Lessons learnt

Reduce financial and administrative burden by designing CRCF protocols based on evidence and ground-level realities.

The session highlighted key pathways to achieve this:

1. Designing CRCF protocols based on evidence and ground-level realities

2. Digital MRV Systems – The need for automated digital Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) systems to simplify processes and reduce time requirements.
3. Standardized Reporting – A unified reporting system where CRCF-associated certificates could serve as a foundation for other nature-based solutions.
4. Single Benchmarking System – A harmonized benchmarking system with standardized sustainability indicators for farms, aligning with the EU Commission’s new [Vision for Food and Agriculture](#).

To whom: Farmer unions, companies, policy maker, accounting standards

15.4. Open questions

Establish clear rules for insetting, including definitions, perimeters, allocation protocols, and climate benefit claims.

Currently, there are no established rules for Scope 3 emissions and SBTi regarding insetting, particularly for rotational and multiple cropping systems. This lack of regulation leads to transparency issues.

To whom: Companies, farmer union, policymaker, standard developer

15.5. Concrete steps for implementation

Ensure Insetting Includes a Binding Reward Mechanism Between Farmers and Agri-Food Companies Insetting should establish a binding reward mechanism, such as the ‘right to report,’ to ensure fair compensation for farmers. Some protocols, like the GHG Protocol, do not specify how companies should reward farmers or on what basis, leading to transparency gaps. Key considerations include who has the right to report emissions within the value chain and how farmers are rewarded for their contributions. While some regulations already address this issue, the CRCF could serve as a framework to formalize agreements, ensuring that carbon credits are either sold from farmers to companies or structured through clear contractual arrangements

To whom: Farmer union, policymaker, agrifood-companies

15.6. Concrete steps for implementation

Mitigation of Costs & Risks for Farmers before the Start of a Project:

First, conduct an ex-ante assessment of insetting projects to evaluate risks and costs for farmers. Insetting initiatives should be financially viable for farmers, ensuring that the risks and costs they bear are properly accounted for and that they can secure a margin. An ex-ante assessment is essential to evaluate key factors such as how farmers can achieve profitability, potential risks related to carbon emission reductions should be identified in advance, and the consequences if emissions are claimed but ultimately released. Clear guidelines should be established to protect farmers from financial or regulatory liabilities.

Ensure public mechanism to support upfront costs for farmers: To ensure farmers can capture value from the inseting market, mechanisms using public funding should be established to cover the costs farmers will incur to access private sector schemes under the CRCF, such as appropriate soil analysis, GHG baselining, or benefiting from necessary technical support, all of which should be covered upfront.

To whom: Farmer unions, policy makers, companies

3.16 Session 16: Unlocking the Potential of Soil Biodiversity: Sustainable Land Management, Restoration, and Revenue Generation

Main organisers: Cà Colonna srl, Carboneg, Land Life

Session description

In the evolving landscape of carbon farming, soil biodiversity represents an untapped opportunity to amplify ecosystem resilience, climate adaptability, and overall environmental health. Restoring and leveraging soil biodiversity offers a transformative opportunity to enhance ecosystem services, improve land productivity, and unlock new revenue streams. This session explored how soil biodiversity can drive sustainable practices while delivering tangible economic and environmental benefits.

The session discussed how soil biodiversity underpins critical ecosystem functions such as nutrient cycling, organic matter decomposition, carbon sequestration, and plant productivity. Using real-world examples, including Land Life's biodiversity pilot in the Iberian Peninsula, it highlighted the importance of setting baselines and using innovative tools like environmental DNA (eDNA) for measuring biodiversity impact. It also examined how rewards of biodiversity-enhancing practices can support carbon sequestration.

Finally, it delved into the policy and financial mechanisms essential for scaling biodiversity restoration. By examining emerging regulatory frameworks such as the EU's Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Regulation (CRCF) and Verra's Nature Framework pilot, the session explored how biodiversity metrics can complement carbon markets to create verified, qualified assets that align with market and policy demands.

Issues

- Soil biodiversity enhances ecosystem services and should be a key consideration to avoid a narrow focus on carbon. Both climate and nature need to be improved to restore planetary health.
- Biodiversity measurement is local and multifaceted, whereas carbon is global and measured with a single metric.
- Integrating biodiversity activities into carbon projects demands resources, which can reduce efficiencies and lower the return on investment.

- Current carbon credit pricing inadequately reflects biodiversity benefits, failing to sufficiently incentivize farmers, foresters, and project developers. The biodiversity market is currently too underdeveloped to offer these incentives.
- Given the rapid loss of biodiversity and its impact on ecosystem services, immediate, pragmatic action is crucial to incentivize biodiversity practices effectively.

Recommendations

16.1. Lessons learnt

1. Standardize biodiversity measurement and verification through scientifically rigorous indicators such as eDNA and site-specific baseline assessments. The practical insights gained from the Land Life Biodiversity pilot project in the Iberian Peninsula demonstrates how biodiversity initiatives can complement and elevate carbon strategies.
2. EU CRCF should recognize the unique role that carbon sequestration via reforestation plays in biodiversity and structurally support it.

To whom: EU policymakers & regulatory bodies – To integrate biodiversity metrics into regulations, Carbon credit certifiers & standard-setters – To enhance biodiversity verification and Nature Credit methodologies, Carbon credit buyers

16.2. Concrete step for implementation

Establish integrated biodiversity and carbon credit incentives to financially reward farmers for implementing biodiversity-positive agricultural practices. This should be supported by scalable programs that link biodiversity gains to economic benefits through biodiversity credit markets.

To whom: EU Commission & National Governments – To incorporate biodiversity incentives into agricultural policies, Farmers & agricultural cooperatives – To adopt biodiversity-enhancing practices and participate in credit programs.

16.3. Open questions

Create economic valuation models for soil biodiversity to support the development of biodiversity credits and sustainable finance mechanisms. This will help integrate soil biodiversity restoration into the EU Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Regulation (CRCF) while ensuring market-driven incentives for conservation.

To whom: EU Commission & Agricultural Policymakers – To incorporate soil biodiversity valuation into CRCF policies, Research Institutions & Agronomic Experts – To refine valuation models and identify high-risk ecosystems, Farmers, Landowners & Private Sector Investors – To implement soil biodiversity restoration strategies and engage in biodiversity-linked financial programs.

16.4. On biodiversity in CRCF

- Integrating carbon and biodiversity credits into a unified framework would make it simpler for customers and developers, potentially kickstarting the biodiversity market. However, this integration must uphold integrity to ensure biodiversity is appropriately valued and not diluted. For instance, consider a multi-credit bundle with separate carbon and biodiversity credits, rather than a carbon credit that superficially claims biodiversity co-benefits without adhering to specific practices, providing measurement nor confirmed impact.
- Recognizing different degrees of biodiversity impact —ranging from minor enhancements within productive contexts to significant improvements within natural ecosystem contexts — to encourage going beyond the minimum "do no harm" standard outlined by the EU CRCF.
- Farming, timber, and natural ecosystem restoration are distinct activities that should be treated separately.

16.5. On Nature-based solutions in CRCF

- Adopting a like-for-like approach risks fragmenting the carbon market between engineered solutions (eligible for fuel-based and biogenic emissions) and nature-based solutions (limited to biogenic emissions only). This would severely limit the capital available for essential nature-based carbon projects in the EU, especially as there is no biodiversity market nor compliance framework at the moment. It is recommended not to mandate like-for-like or to do so only for a portion of fuel-based emissions.
- Clarifying the connection between the EU CRCF and the EU NRL would improve understanding among stakeholders regarding their collaborative function.
- Establishing an EU compliance framework for biodiversity restoration, targeting sectors with negative land impacts, could channel necessary capital into nature restoration. The UK's Biodiversity Net Gain, along with programs in Australia and California, could serve as models.

3.17 Session 17: Multi-stakeholder networks and participatory approaches for successful carbon farming and soil health monitoring - Opportunities and challenges

Main organisers: Commonland Foundation, EIT Food South, Wetlands international

Session description

This session aimed to support the ongoing development of the EU Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Certification (CRCF) Regulation by addressing key questions about how to effectively implement carbon farming across landscapes involving multiple stakeholders and with a focus on different ecosystems (wetlands ecosystems and agro-ecosystems in semi-arid regions).

Three real-world case studies supported the discussion, showcasing multi-stakeholder initiatives in carbon farming from Southern Europe in these ecosystems.

The session explored lessons learned, challenges faced by on-the-ground actors, and the potential for carbon farming projects to deliver multiple benefits for both nature and local communities. In addition, the session identified knowledge gaps and offered concrete recommendations to advance the operationalisation of the CRCF framework, aiming at laying the foundation for actionable solutions that can be considered in the next stages of CRCF implementation.

Issues

- multi-stakeholder networks for scaling carbon farming and achieving co-benefits
- blended finance for carbon farming
- the role of Mediterranean wetlands as carbon sinks

Recommendations

17.1. Lessons learnt

Framing carbon credits within the broader context of holistic restoration of landscapes and regions, while combining them with other mechanisms, contributes to establishing an effective and inclusive process towards climate resilience, rather than constituting barely a standalone solution for climate mitigation.

- Multistakeholder partnerships can facilitate scaling through a strong network, and previous stakeholder alignment having reached consensus on a common vision for the development of a landscape or region; this also facilitates conflict mitigation.
- This also enables co-benefits on a wider scale, such as community benefits, biodiversity conservation on habitat and landscape level, social benefits, such as job creation.
- Multistakeholder projects lower transition barriers by showcasing successes and sharing learnings from failures. A leverage effect is created when carbon farming projects are conducted as a group that shares common interests.
- Ideally this should be connected to a community or regional facility that financially supports the initial investment phase of a carbon project – the most crucial phase of a project.
- Financial risks such as high initial investments and ongoing operational costs during a carbon farming project may be mitigated as sharing investments in machinery and agricultural inputs lowers individual investment costs.
- EU support for regional network development can accelerate project scaling by providing capacity-building, facilitating cross-border cooperation, and ensuring fair benefit distribution. Strengthening these networks will enhance resilience, stakeholder engagement, and the effectiveness of landscape-scale carbon farming.

An effective multi-stakeholder network should be inclusive, transparent, and adaptive, integrating landowners, farmers, local communities, investors,

policymakers, scientists, and NGOs. It should foster long-term collaboration through shared governance structures, ensuring all actors have a role in decision-making. The network should facilitate knowledge exchange, capacity-building, and technical support, aligning diverse interests with a common landscape vision. Regional coordination bodies can enhance efficiency by connecting local initiatives with national and EU-level policies. A multi-tiered governance model, integrating public and private stakeholders, ensures accountability, conflict resolution, and sustainable financing. Clear benefit-sharing mechanisms and long-term incentives, such as carbon revenues reinvested into local development, are essential to maintaining engagement and ensuring project scalability from local to landscape levels.

Create more networking opportunities for farmers on community and regional level to engage interested land owners, land users and other stakeholders in the carbon discourse

- Provide a platform for EU-wide accessible workshops on carbon farming projects
- This will bring practitioners, land managers, investors and other parties together
- The ideal network should consist of stakeholders along the entire carbon farming project value chain, including private and public stakeholders

A flexible, science-based approach is needed to account for ecosystem heterogeneity while maintaining the integrity of carbon methodologies. Multi-stakeholder networks can facilitate locally adapted methodologies by integrating regional ecological knowledge with standardized carbon accounting frameworks. Incentivizing research, pilot projects, and participatory monitoring ensures methodologies reflect diverse land-use systems. Carbon credit frameworks should incorporate ecosystem-specific baselines, rewarding multifunctional landscapes that provide biodiversity and resilience benefits. Blended financing models combining carbon revenues with conservation payments can ensure viability across land types. Regional governance structures should guide the alignment of carbon standards with local land management needs, ensuring fair access to carbon markets while safeguarding ecological integrity. EU support for adaptive methodologies can enhance credibility and facilitate cross-border project scaling.

Stakeholder networks help to account for heterogeneity of agro-ecosystems, land use and management practices when using existing carbon farming practices or methodologies. Methodology developers should consider the following to ease MS network projects

- Heterogeneity in terms of different ecosystems (arable/grasslands/forestry/wetlands, etc.) require different methodologies to be combined to scale a project from single plots to landscape/regional level. A first guidance for this already exists and will be continuously improved (Commonland carbon finance chapter in the 4R guidebook, refer to online link).
- A more component-based approach vs. an activity-based approach can help to quantify elements of the carbon cycle in a more practical and ecosystem-agnostic manner. This approach is supported by current developments of quantification models involving remote sensing for which

considerations should be made to be included in the current versions of methodologies as one type of quantification approach.

Multistakeholder networks help improve the accuracy of MRV and mitigate increased costs of MRV. It is beneficial to include co-benefits in a participatory MRV system on landscape or regional level

- Variability determines sample sizes, and not the size of an area. Thus, designing sampling schemes that involve a larger area can have a positive effect on sample sizes per participating land user in a larger MS project.
- Landscape or regional networks can facilitate the selection of baseline plots for dynamic baselining, by allowing stakeholders to choose a plot together instead of individual ones.
- A reduction of sampling sizes per hectare reduces costs for MRV substantially.
- Costs of sampling can also be reduced by sharing sampling efforts and costs for sampling tools.
- Co-benefits often are created on a larger scale (the positive externalities of a carbon farming project) and thus can be allocated more efficiently on a community level than for the individual context.

Testing grounds for refining carbon methodologies. Pilot projects serve as testing grounds for refining carbon methodologies, demonstrating real-world feasibility, and informing policy frameworks. Multi-stakeholder networks play a key role in scaling pilot findings by fostering cross-sector collaboration and ensuring practical implementation insights reach policymakers. EU-supported pilot initiatives can validate financial models, risk-sharing mechanisms, and co-benefit measurement frameworks, helping to shape future incentive structures. Regulatory flexibility should be built into early-stage pilots to allow experimentation with innovative carbon farming approaches. A structured feedback loop between pilot projects and EU institutions can accelerate policy adjustments, ensuring alignment between field experience and legislative frameworks. Establishing formal channels for pilot project results to influence EU directives would enhance scalability, credibility, and investment attractiveness of carbon farming policies.

17.2. Lessons learnt

Funding carbon farming projects within the voluntary carbon market in the EU remains a challenge due to high costs and investment risks. Blended finance emerges as a strategic solution, leveraging both public and private capital to facilitate sustainable investments in the early stage of development.

- Public funding at the EU level is necessary to bridge the investment gap in the early stages.
- Strengthen public funding for early-stage development as public funds plays a critical role for R&D activities, project development, and piloting new methodologies which is critical when initiating carbon farming projects across different landscapes.
- Leverage CAP, State Aid, and other EU Funds to overcome barriers. Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) budget, State aid, and other EU funding mechanisms that help in covering upfront costs such as investments in technology, advisory services, and MRV (Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification) tools. These costs often act as barriers to participation, especially for small-scale farmers.

- De-risk investments by increased use of guarantees - public financing can absorb early-stage risks thus increasing the amount of private sector investments available within support of wider nature restoration or regeneration efforts.
- Supporting pan-European research to collect data also on the carbon farming market size, volume and market potential alongside to promotion of networks and training of the carbon farming through EU grants (e.g. Natura 2000 payments or within EU funds calls).
- Enhanced coordination of transition funds to ensure public and private investments are implemented with robust financial risk mitigation strategies.
- Enable public funds in the form of unrestricted and flexible grant funding should be available to support multi-stakeholder landscape partnership and governance processes to catalyse development of overall nature restoration.
- Redirect environmentally harming subsidies, enhance coordination of transition funds, align public and private investments.

Currently, in the EU there are multiple funding sources and scale of incentives for the green transition within Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) 2021–2027, including the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) budget (Pillar 1 eco-schemes and Pillar 2 rural development measures), LIFE Programme, Horizon Europe (Cluster 5, 6 including Mission Soil) and others, e.g. EAFRD, ERDF. New greener and fairer CAP envisioned a substantial allocation of budget for eco-schemes (including carbon farming among others) with at least 25% of the budget for direct payments to be allocated to eco-schemes to incentivize climate and environment friendly carbon farming practices with a spending on eco-schemes in the period 2023-2027 of 48,5 billion Euros. Additionally, at least 35% of EAFRD funds under Pillar 2 is allocated to initiatives addressing numerous environmental and climate challenges.

- Accelerating implementation of greener and fairer Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).
- Effectively implement financial allocations for eco-schemes including carbon farming initiatives within national level CAP Strategic Plans.
- Foster systemic public-private investment alignment in design of dedicated blended finance mechanisms and financial instruments.
- Strengthen collaboration between government institutions, development finance institutions (DFIs), private investors and non-profit organizations within multi-stakeholder landscape partnership framework to maximize blended finance potential.
- Leverage public development banks potential, for instance EIB Group announced commitment of €3 billion in loans for agriculture and other bioeconomy activities across Europe with focus on young farmers, gender equality and green investments.
- Implement incentives that encourage nature-positive actions and efficiently support just transition within the agricultural sector.

To scale up carbon projects, develop suitable financial instruments with longer time horizons aligned with large, holistic restoration initiatives that harness diverse stakeholders that can support long-term project viability and de-risk investment for private investors.

- Support multi-stakeholder partnerships to effectively blend different financial instruments at various stages of landscape interventions over a longer time horizon.
- Enhance policy and regulatory frameworks to facilitate blended finance models and create incentives for private sector participation.
- Develop enabling platforms to streamline the implementation of national and regional development plans, ensuring vertical and horizontal policy coherence and integrating spatial planning and budgeting.
- Allocate resources to strengthen landscape partnerships that drive comprehensive and sustainable landscape restoration efforts.
- Support learning, training and knowledge-sharing and with adequate funding allocation.

Measure social and environmental impact and more process-based funding for organizations that develop standardized impact assessment frameworks to track and demonstrate the co-benefits of blended finance in carbon projects.

- Adapting a holistic landscape approach can reduce or overcome many of the barriers for successful green transition and provide numerous co-benefits. Using blended finance mechanisms, different financial instruments including ecosystem payment services, 4Return approach values environment, social and inspirational returns alongside financial returns, recognizing true value of an investment and interconnectedness aspects of a landscape to address multiple challenges regarding climate change mitigation and adaptation.
- Co-benefit is that one financed intervention is not isolated as a one-time funded project as various capital providers and revenue streams are strategically aligned with a long capital continuum time horizon.

17.3. Lessons learnt

The management and restoration of Mediterranean Wetlands have proven to be effective strategies for mitigating climate change. These wetlands naturally act as carbon sinks, storing significant carbon stocks in their sediment. Restoration and management actions further enhance their mitigation capacity, ensuring additionality, as demonstrated by the LIFE Wetlands4Climate project.

However, the high operational costs of small-scale projects present a major challenge. To improve cost-effectiveness, these initiatives need to be upscaled. Additionally, carbon credits prices remain high in the market – pilot projects in Spain indicate costs around €400 per ton of CO₂ equivalent. One of the key cost drivers is the monitoring and verification process, which requires on-site fieldwork on an annual basis. This includes defining plots and measuring carbon fluxes for every hectare of restored wetland.

To make wetland-based carbon farming more viable, scaling up projects and optimizing monitoring methods will be essential for reducing costs and improving accessibility to carbon markets.

17.4 Open questions

The ideal stakeholder network for scaling carbon farming and achieving co-benefits should be a multi-actor platform integrating: farmers/Landowners/authorities with competencies on the land, scientists, NGOs, private investors, policymakers (Regional or national Authorities), and certification bodies. Farmers or landowners need financial and technical support, while scientists ensure robust monitoring and verification. NGOs facilitate implementation and safeguard biodiversity, and private investors help scale solutions through carbon markets. Policymakers (Regional and National Authorities) must align regulations with the Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF), ensuring incentives and funding mechanisms. Lessons from LIFE Wetlands4Climate show that nature-based solutions, transparent carbon accounting, and multi-stakeholder collaboration are key to success. Policy support should focus on creating stable financial incentives, regulatory clarity, and streamlined MRV (Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification) processes. Blended finance mechanisms should be promoted to de-risk investments, attracting private capital into carbon farming. Additionally, harmonized carbon accounting standards are essential to ensure credibility across different ecosystems. Policy frameworks should also support regional pilot projects, knowledge-sharing networks, and digital tools for cost-effective carbon monitoring, fostering long-term stakeholder engagement and scalability.

- Developing Biodiversity Credits – Establishing biodiversity credit systems to properly value wetland restoration co-benefits is essential. Policymakers, conservation organizations, and financial institutions must collaborate to create marketable, science-based credit mechanisms that integrate carbon sequestration with biodiversity conservation.
- Blended Finance for Carbon Farming – A mix of public grants (CAP eco-schemes, LIFE Program) and private investment (carbon markets, green bonds) is needed to de-risk early-stage projects and attract long-term financing. Public funding should support research, baseline assessments, and MRV, while private capital scales up validated projects.
- Reducing MRV Costs – LIFE Wetlands4Climate highlights the need for investment in cost-effective MRV methodologies, including scientific research to validate proxy-based monitoring methods. Lowering MRV costs will improve scalability and investor confidence.
- Valuing Co-Benefits in Carbon Markets – Current carbon pricing undervalues ecosystem services. Recognizing biodiversity, water retention, and resilience co-benefits in carbon markets and EU climate funding would enhance financial viability and attract more investment in wetland-based carbon farming.

17.5 Open questions

Enhancing Monitoring and Verification Methods: The LIFE Wetlands4Climate methodology relies on direct, on-site measurements of carbon fluxes, as no proxies currently exist to scale results. The lack of scientific studies on Mediterranean wetlands and their role in climate change mitigation prevents the development of alternative verification approaches. Addressing this gap requires scientific research institutions, environmental agencies, and carbon credit certifiers to collaborate on expanding datasets and validating proxy-based monitoring approaches, and standardize methodologies, ultimately reducing MRV costs and improving accuracy.

From the LIFE Wetlands4Climate perspective, scaling carbon projects through multi-stakeholder networks can increase investment attractiveness by improving cost efficiency, data reliability, and market access. Larger-scale projects reduce MRV costs per unit by enabling shared resources, standardized methodologies, and collaborative research across multiple sites.

However, Mediterranean wetlands lack validated proxy-based MRV methods, making monitoring expensive and limiting scalability. Addressing this requires investment in scientific research, data standardization, and the development of alternative verification approaches. Public funding is crucial to bridge early-stage investment gaps, while private sector engagement can drive long-term financing through carbon markets. Strengthening policy alignment, certification frameworks, and co-benefit valuation (biodiversity, water resilience) will further enhance investor confidence and project viability.

Establish a Clear Legal and Certification Framework: The lack of an approved methodology for Mediterranean wetlands under certification standards, coupled with administrative barriers (as seen in LIFE Wetlands4Climate), has slowed progress. The CRCF should provide a clear, flexible legal framework that accommodates diverse ecosystems, including wetlands, by recognizing regional variations in carbon sequestration potential. It must also streamline approval processes for new methodologies, ensuring faster validation and adoption while reducing bureaucratic hurdles.

Improve the CRCF Approach and Methodologies: The CRCF should explicitly recognize Mediterranean wetlands as a carbon farming solution, integrating hydrology-based carbon accounting to reflect their unique sequestration dynamics. The framework must set clear guidelines for methodology approval, incentivize scientific research to fill knowledge gaps, and facilitate integration with national carbon registries and EU climate policies. A more adaptive, science-driven approach will enable large-scale wetland restoration to play a key role in achieving EU climate targets while unlocking carbon market opportunities.

3.18 Session 18: Co-designing future services and a policy framework on carbon farming

Main organisers: ICOS

Session description

This session provided a collaborative space for participants to co-design future services aimed at supporting policymakers in carbon removal efforts. Organizers shared comparative insights on existing services related to carbon farming, drawing from the IRISCC (Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change Risks) project. Additionally, a taxonomy of key features and essential data requirements for current services was presented which can serve as a foundation for developing next-generation services.

The central question guiding this session was: What future services can we envision to more effectively meet policymakers' needs using research infrastructure data?

Designed specifically for policymakers and researchers in the field of carbon removal, this session focused on leveraging research infrastructures—facilities and systems dedicated to environmental management, protection, and improvement, supported by a range of technologies addressing various ecological challenges. The goal was to foster innovative service(s) that directly respond to the evolving needs of policymakers.

Issues

- 1) what kind of services are needed,
- 2) how they need to be implemented and
- 3) who are the key actors in the development of the services.

Recommendations

18.1. What kind of services are needed ?

Even though we identified many stakeholders and drew a map on how they relate to each other and to the future services, a common vision is that **Farmers should be at heart** in the development of new services. A consistent theme across all scenarios is the need to place farmers at the center of the agricultural system. Currently, farmers often feel marginalized, burdened by regulations, and disconnected from the policy-making processes that directly impact their livelihoods. The utopian vision flips this dynamic. Whether it's Ireland's focus on keeping farmers on the land or Portugal/Flanders highlighting farmers as key decision-makers, the message is clear: a sustainable future requires empowering farmers. Farmers in Europe are aging, with the average age nearing 60 years. This raises an important question: how can we make farming an attractive career choice for younger generations? To ensure the future of agriculture, we need to inspire and support a new generation of enthusiastic farmers.

The potential for fraud and conflicts of interest emerged as a significant concern. From the role of assessors in the Central Europe scenario, potentially enabling fraudulent reporting to the discussion of brokers in Portugal/Flanders, it's clear that robust oversight mechanisms are essential. Independent bodies are needed to ensure that carbon credit schemes are not exploited, and that the integrity of the system is maintained.

The Irish scenario brought up an interesting point about balancing local and global markets. While the emphasis is on "insetting" – reducing emissions within the farm and food industry itself – the reality is that Ireland is a major exporter. The utopian vision must therefore create a system that is both beneficial to local communities and credible on the international stage. This may involve a multi-layered approach where farms prioritize local sales before selling carbon credits externally.

While financial compensation is undoubtedly important, the scenarios also emphasized the need to incentivize farmers through other means. Farmer networks, knowledge sharing, and recognition within their profession can all play a crucial role in motivating

sustainable practices. It's about creating a culture of excellence and innovation in agriculture, where farmers are proud to be stewards of the land.

To whom: Developers of the future services

18.2. Concrete steps for implementation

The implementation needs to follow a co-design approach. This is why the first step is to identify the stakeholders that need to be involved in this process. This workshop is part of our co-design approach. This work of identifying the stakeholders is conducted during the session. We do this work as part of the EU project IRISCC, Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change Risks.

We have developed a card game that helps us to co-design with various stakeholders in our workshop. This tool has been key in organising the discussion in the workshop. We are aiming to play this card game together with other stakeholders and in other forums (conferences, meetings or summits) in order to get comparable results.

To whom: Stakeholders identified: EU policy makers, National and local policy makers, farmers, private sector involved in the MRV and in the voluntary carbon market, research infrastructures and researchers.

18.3. Lesson learnt

The path towards the implementation of the carbon farming framework for Europe is complex, but the discussions on Future Utopian scenarios offer a roadmap. By prioritizing farmers, fostering transparency and trust, addressing fraud, balancing local and global markets, and confronting monopolies, Europe can create a good implementation of the carbon removal and harmonized carbon farming (CRCF) framework that is both environmentally sustainable and economically viable. It's a vision that requires collaboration, innovation, and a commitment to creating a better future for all.

To whom: Policy makers, researchers, farmers, public and private sector representatives and service developers.

18.4. How to use data to ensure transparency and trust?

Another key element is data. The Central European scenario highlights the importance of centralized data management for carbon credit systems, while the Irish scenario stresses the need for long-term monitoring and research to ensure the credibility of food labeling schemes. Across the board, transparency is paramount. Farmers need to trust that systems are fair, that they are compensated adequately, and that oversight bodies are accountable. Data, when managed effectively and transparently, can be a powerful tool for building this trust.

For different MRV (Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification) systems, these systems must comply with international standards, link carbon sequestration ("carbon farming") to agronomic strategies, and be tailored to regional contexts. They should also be developed through international collaboration involving public research institutions, the private sector, and farmers. Additionally, it is crucial to integrate this data with national

greenhouse gas (GHG) inventories and establish clear rules for managing farm-level data. These rules must address who owns the data, who can access it, and how it can be used effectively.

3.19 Session 19: Overcoming barriers to carbon farming projects financing: bridging the gap between farmers and buyers through adequate framework and MRV tools

Main organisers: Association des Chambres d'agriculture de l'Arc Atlantique (AC3A)AC3A, Agrifood, Agrosolutions, CNRS-CESBIO, Earth Observation Association, I4CE, IETA, Nataïs, Netcarbon, Regeneratio

Session description

The Carbon Removals Certification Framework (CRCF) is aiming to make a meaningful contribution to the EU's climate mitigation targets while appealing to both land users and certificates' buyers. This is not an easy match, especially for the agriculture sector where the economic model for the agriculture transition still needs to be found. In this context, this session built on real use cases to dive into the potential cases for agriculture-based CRCF certificates. It discussed the various sources of funding that should be unlocked, and to some extent stacked at farm level: voluntary private funding outside the value chain, voluntary funding from the value chain, compliance demand, public funds.

Today, the main private funding sources are voluntary: offsetting, and insetting.. Both options barely allow to cover the full cost of the transition at farm level. Solutions are needed to both stack and scale them. The main barriers to financing are the carbon farming costs and the lack of clarity around the claims buyers can make in an MRV context, especially the risk of double-counting. Bridging the gap between farmers and certificates' buyers, this session discussed these difficulties and barriers, and explored how CRCF can solve them, to ensure that adequate funding effectively reaches the farms.

Issues

- Challenges observed for agriculture projects' financing : confusion in claims and double-counting issues, environmental integrity and project's attractiveness, cost of MRV and cost of practices vs market price, non-permanence and uncertainty of nature-based credits
- Issues for buyers in terms of claims clarity and need for precise SCOPE 3 reporting
- Opportunities provided by new MRV tools to help solve the above-mentioned issues (reporting, traceability, uncertainty...)

Recommendations

19.1. Lesson learnt

In countries like France which already have carbon certification mechanisms in place, we notice carbon farming projects from the agriculture sector have more difficulties than others (e.g. forestry) to access voluntary funding. Among the potential reasons for this, stakeholders bring up the attractiveness of the projects' narrative, the carbon price, but also the perceived risk of double-claiming, which is considered by many as one of the main deterrents for agriculture projects' funding. The current rules promoted by standards like the GHG Protocol or SBTi Flag require a strict allocation of carbon benefits that is hard to implement yet, which slows down the agrifood industries' commitment and prevents farmers from accessing sufficient funding. More specifically, two main issues are being reported: 1) there still is uncertainty regarding the claims around Scope3 reporting, and 2) farmers can be prevented from combining different sources of funding from within and outside the value chain.

19.2. Proposal to improve CRCF

Ensure the Green Claims Directive provides clear and common rules for carbon farming projects related claims. Those rules will need to allow for coherent and transparent claims (be precise about who can claim what with such a certificate), while still being pragmatic on traceability and the need to combine different sources of funding for a unique farm in numerous situations.

More generally, clarity is needed on the end-uses for nature-based carbon removal credits. This includes rules for the use of credits in corporate environmental claims, including CSRD, but also clear views from the Commission on a potential emissions trading system for agriculture, potential recognition under CORSIA... There is also a need for clear guidance on the articulation of the CRCF with the existing voluntary carbon market standards to keep investment flowing in the sector.

The claims should transparently address buyers' expectations towards permanence, and allow CRC-F credits to compete with international private carbon farming supply standards. The EU CRCF's proposed durations for carbon farming activity (5 years) and monitoring period (another 5 years) are very short and 30 years less than the recommendation of the Integrity Council for the Voluntary Carbon Market (ICVCM), currently implemented by leading international Voluntary Carbon Market (VCM) standards' methodologies.

To whom: CRCF and European Commission

19.3. Proposal to improve CRCF

Create funding mechanisms associated with the CRCF which allows the combination of different sources of funding (private-private, public-private) to cover the whole project's costs (practices, investment, risk +MRV). The rules about claims should allow for this possibility, especially when the carbon price on the voluntary market is not high enough to cover the costs. Of course, clear rules about how to deal with

additionality should be established and made transparent when combining different sources of funding (especially public-private combinations). One major feedback of our audience was the call for unified MRV for Inset and Offsetting needs such that both can be combined. Only the combination of both allows for a whole-farm transition as this is the only way to credible, long-term SOC sequestration. Funding sources that focus only on some crops or some years do not provide sufficient incentives for farmers to transform their farming system credibly.

To whom: CRCF and European Commission

19.4. Proposal to improve CRCF

Set clear rules for delimiting what falls within agrofood scope 3 perimeter in carbon farming, especially for rotational crops, and **define allocation rules** for carbon removals, among the different crops of a crop rotation.

To whom: CRCF and European Commission

19.5. Proposal to improve CRCF

Ensure the CRCF reaches beyond voluntary demand, all while protecting and incentivizing existing voluntary initiatives. Most carbon funding today is voluntary (offsetting or insetting): in a complicated political context, we need to find ways to ensure the additionality and sustainability of private commitments, but also develop other sources of funding which can unlock greater volumes: public funds directed to certified projects, or compliance demand for those certificates.

To whom: CRCF and European Commission

19.6. Proposal to improve CRCF

Implementing a yearly/field scale common database (C registry) for ongoing and previous projects should also be a priority to address double counting. In addition, a solution would be to rely on a common tool for the different MRV contexts (CAP, VCM offsetting & insetting) and on blockchains to ensure traceability.

To whom: CRCF and European Commission

19.7. Proposal to improve CRCF

Rely on geospatial data including remote sensing to reduce the cost and increase the reliability/transparency/objectivity of the C stock change assessment for the carbon farming project. Define standards to associate to the quality of carbon credits.

To whom: CRCF and European Commission

3.20 Session 20: Financing Models for a Sustainable Future

Main organisers: Heavy Finance, Rabobank

Session description

This session explored the financial challenges faced by farmers transitioning to regenerative agriculture, focusing on innovative financing solutions and the role of public institutions in unlocking capital. Given the urgency of addressing climate change, understanding these barriers is critical for promoting sustainable agricultural practices.

As Europe accelerates its transition to a sustainable agricultural sector, access to capital remains a significant barrier for farmers adopting regenerative practices like reduced tillage, incorporation of cover crops etc. This session addressed the financing gap, highlighting innovative solutions such as GreenLoans, which provide zero-interest loans funded by future carbon credit sales. It discussed how carbon credits can serve as collateral for financing, the need for structured and transparent carbon markets, and the transformative role of public institutions in catalyzing private investment.

Issues

- Capital barriers in regenerative farming
- Innovative Financing models
- Use of carbon credits as collateral for financing
- Importance of structured carbon markets
- Role of public institutions in unlocking capital

Recommendations

Not provided

3.21 Session 21: Paving the way for cohesive action on soil carbon sequestration: The role of International Initiatives in the development of MRV frameworks that meet European Carbon Farming challenges

Main organisers: 4per 1000, INRAE

Session description

The key role of increasing and protecting soil carbon stocks for climate change mitigation and adaptation, biodiversity protection and food security is increasingly being recognized in international negotiations. While the EU with its Soil Monitoring Law, the Mission Soil and the upcoming CRCF framework is a strong global leader in the field, the topic has gained prominence all around the globe. International initiatives, like the “4 per

1000” Initiative and the Soil Carbon International Research Consortium (IRC), have been playing a crucial role to build momentum, increase collaboration and foster peer-to-peer learning. This session reflected on current political processes supporting soil carbon sequestration and explored opportunities for support for cohesive policymaking, research design and multi-stakeholder action.

Looking back at the first decade of the **“4 per 1000” Initiative**, the session reflected on how the global outreach of the Initiative **has paved the way for current political and scientific developments around soil health and carbon sequestration in the EU and beyond. It introduced** successful approaches to **multi-stakeholder action** and presented **key findings of the regional roadmaps for Northern Europe and the Mediterranean Region.**

Finally, the session reflected on existing **MRV tools and systems and presented a harmonized approach** developed under the ORCaSa project.

Issues

- Approaches to cohesive policy making across international conventions and beyond departments at European and national Scale
- Priorities for most effective policy support and multi-stakeholder action for international Initiatives
- Priorities for policy support concerning MRV frameworks and associated methodologies
- Requirements for a harmonized MRV system

Recommendations

21.1. Recommendation for action

Strengthen international multi-stakeholder cooperation and dialogue, by supporting the actions of initiatives like "4 per 1000" and the Soil Carbon International Research Consortium, to ensure the feasibility of MRV frameworks along the value chain and across regions and to improve harmonization.

21.2. Recommendation for action

Integrate environmental and social co-benefits of soil carbon sequestration into a holistic carbon farming approach via premiums on credits.

21.3. Recommendation for action

Improve the accessibility of carbon markets and facilitate informed decision making on carbon farming activities, by providing aggregated and easily accessible information on carbon market mechanisms, scientific findings and technical developments related to soil carbon sequestration, MRV, environmental and social effects, as well as benefits and risks related to different approaches.

21.4. Recommendation for action

Create a monitoring committee for existing carbon farming practices, their implementation and impacts, to feed decision making on the evolution of directives at European level.

21.5. Recommendation for action

Provide international guidance on the use of cost effective monitoring tools across the MRV frameworks by combining observation technologies (e.g. remote sensing, spectral measurements and automated sampling) adapted to different contexts of application and regional constraints.

3.22 Session 22: Monitoring and verification of peatland condition and improvement: remote sensing, AI and beyond

Main organisers: AECO, National Parks and Wildlife Service, Peatland Finance Ireland, Trinity College Dublin, University College Dublin

Session description:

In order to achieve efficiencies of scale, there is a need for semi-automated methods to monitor peatland condition at scale to infer ecosystem service delivery such as carbon flux, water retention or biodiversity uplift. Remote Sensing (RS), Artificial Intelligence (AI), remote monitoring systems and data science/engineering can play a pivotal role, as processing pipelines can be deployed to continually fetch data to feed AI models for further inference. However, the accuracy of these outputs rely on effective ground-truthing. This leads to a series of multi-scale and multi-modal questions: how could different RS sources - e.g. satellites and unmanned aerial vehicles - be integrated for better inference, if their spatial extent greatly varies? How can these methods be used to monitor, report and validate ecosystem service delivery in a manner which ensures that sources of finance can economically support restoration? What are the most cost-effective strategies for on-the-ground monitoring to deliver credible short-term results, while generating robust datasets for training algorithms in the long term? Do these approaches comfortably sit with emergent mandatory and voluntary markets?

This session highlighted advances in remote sensing (RS), artificial intelligence (AI), and remote monitoring systems (incl. water table), emphasizing their role in peatland restoration. It addressed challenges in standardization, showcased best practices in MRV, and explored their applications to emerging standards across Europe. Importantly, by fostering dialogue among experts, practitioners, and stakeholders, it aimed to catalyze standardization, innovation and to drive the adoption of advanced technologies.

Issues

- Monitoring and quantifying peatland condition
- Remote Sensing (RS), Artificial Intelligence (AI) to support this
- MRV to support emerging standards across Europe

Recommendations

22.1 Proposal to improve CRCF

Remote sensing and artificial intelligence, increasingly, can be used effectively to derive reliable, cost-effective and scalable monitoring of peatland conditions. An approach to integrating this into CRCF methodologies should therefore be formulated.

To whom: DG CLIMA, ENV and Expert Working Group on CRCF

22.2. Recommendation for action

Delivery of quantified ecosystem services requires cost-effective and scalable monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV), supporting emergent Standards in Europe (e.g. Ireland) which can offer a bundle of ecosystem services. **These bundled certificates need to be more actively included within the CRCF and nature finance more broadly.**

To whom: National responsible bodies, EU Commission DGs

22.3. Open question

How can we pragmatically apply remote sensing, artificial intelligence and other state-of-the-art monitoring techniques (especially water table depth) to existing and emergent certification systems?

To whom: DG CLIMA and National Restoration Plan national contact points.

3.23 Session 23: MRV Agroforestry

Main organisers: Climate Cleanup, DEAFAL, DeFAF, ELO, EURAF, INRAE, Scave World, University of Pisa

Session description

“Soil carbon in mineral soils and agroforestry” is one of the three carbon farming activities being developed in the Carbon Farming Delegated Act of the Carbon Removals Certification Framework. Agroforestry has long been recommended by the IPCC for both climate mitigation and climate adaptation - e.g. IPCC Special Report on Climate Change and Land ([IPCC 2019](#)). It was also prominent in reports commissioned by DG Clima on operationalising carbon farming (see EURAF [Policy Briefing #8](#)).

This session focused on **monitoring, reporting and verification** of agroforestry carbon farming schemes, including environmental and social issues. It built on the EURAF typology for agroforestry practices - identifying 8 types of agroforestry (see EURAF [Policy Briefing #1](#)), and focused on agricultural land.

Recommendations were prepared to support the role of agroforestry in future voluntary carbon-farming schemes. CAP eco-schemes, investment measures and agri-environment-climate measures during the first 5 years of agroforestry plantations can kick-start their adoption into voluntary carbon farming schemes and help close the growing gap between GHG emissions and sequestration in rural Europe. It is suggested that Member States should register and map lines and groups of trees as “landscape features”, and this will give them a protected status and good guarantees of “permanence”.

Issues

- Access to smallholder farmers,
- Leakage,
- Liability and Insurance,
- Implementation hurdles

Recommendations

23.1. Definitions

Agroforestry should be defined in the CRCF as “**Cropland or permanent pasture parcels**, including boundaries, with more than [x%] tree-cover-density (TCD), or with a management plan where tree cover will exceed this density. The threshold TCD shall be set by Member States. **Permanent crop parcels** can be classed as agroforestry if a secondary crop or grazing is noted in the IACS-LPIS system” **Notes:** a) Member states are recommended to choose either **5%** (FAO threshold for “other wooded land”) or **10%** (FAO threshold for “forest”) for the TCD threshold; d) IACS-LPIS “forest parcels” will not count as CRCF agroforestry, although forest grazing is a valuable management practice to reduce the risk of wildfires; c) Member States already use tree cover thresholds between 10% and 30% in their national definitions of “forest” (see EURAF [Policy Briefing #15](#)).

Landscape features are quoted in the DGCLIMA draft methodology for carbon farming as “high diversity landscape features”, and are listed in Annex IV of the *Nature Restoration Regulation* as indicators of agricultural biodiversity. Unfortunately, DGENV uses a different definition of landscape features to that used in the CAP. *CAP Implementing Regulation (L/458/463)* Article 3.1 defines **landscape features** as “hedgerows, individual or groups of trees, trees rows, field margins, patches, buffer strips, ditches, streams, small ponds, small wetlands, stonewalls, cairns, terraces, cultural features”. The NRR includes these categories but also adds “land lying fallow”. It uses the prefix “high diversity” without clarifying what this means! DGAGRI and DGENV, with the help of JRC and their recent *Classification of Farming Practices (2024)*, should resolve the differences in definitions urgently. The authors recommend that the **DGAGRI definition is preferred**, since it has existed for much longer and because Member States already provide detailed dimensions and rules for landscape features in their CAP Strategic Plans (EURAF [Policy Briefing #21](#)).

Forest is defined as in Annex II of the EU LULUCF Regulation [2018/841](#), amended for ES, SL and FI by Regulation [2023/839](#). The national thresholds conform with the UNFCCC Marrakesh Accords ([2021](#)) and are used by all Member States for their annual

Greenhouse Gas Inventory Reports to the UNFCCC. The single definition of forest contained in the draft Forest Monitoring Regulation ([Nov 2023](#)) is **not appropriate** for CRCF reporting, except in the 3 MS where it matches the national definition.

Agroforestation is a shorthand term for the creation of agroforestry systems. It is the parallel of afforestation, but the land remains defined as “agriculture” rather than “forest” in national cadastres and IACS systems.

23.2. Improvement of CRCF

The Carbon Farming Delegated Act should include an indicative list of carbon farming practices, based on the *Carbon Farming Technical Guidance Handbook* ([2021](#)) and the *JRC Classification of Farming Practices* ([2024](#)).

A standardised baseline of zero for agroforestry trees younger than 6 years, suggested by DG Clima, is appropriate since the modest growth of young trees in widely-spaced tree rows will be balanced by the small emissions caused by initial ground preparation and planting. Even tree-plantations with fast growth, such as poplars in the Po valley or eucalyptus in Galicia will fix less than 5% of their total biomass during the first 5 years. This availability of CAP funding for the baseline soil measurements, tree-planting and initial maintenance will “kick-start” accounting and greatly incentivise landowners.

Another type of agroforestation is protected natural regeneration of degraded wood pastures (e.g. Dehesas, Montados and Streuobst). There may be as much as 20.3 Mha of wood pastures in Europe ([Pleininger et al 2015](#)) and most are heavily degraded. Their restoration would be enhanced by a combination of CAP funding and carbon-farming certification. “Restoration of wood pastures” as a type of agroforestry will require establishment of a “project baseline” rather than a “standardised baseline” because of the presence of both mature and juvenile trees.

The second carbon farming methodology recommended by DG Clima is “*Tree planting on degraded and abandoned land*”. EURAF recommend that this be called “*Afforestation of degraded and abandoned land*” to avoid confusion with agroforestry (which remains as “agriculture” in CAP statistics), and to align better with existing UNFCCC and VCM methodologies for “*afforestation, reforestation and restoration*” (ARR).

23.3. Improvement of CRCF: eligible activities

In the DG Clima first MRV draft ([Nov 2024](#)), the discussion of carbon-sequestration should be completed with the statement “*or which reduce emissions from soils*”. This is particularly relevant to agroforestry – since agricultural trees can both limit N₂O emissions from the soil by uptake of surplus NO_x in reducing conditions, and reduce volatilized ammonia (NH₃) through its absorption on tree foliage. These processes should, ideally, be included in biophysical agroforestry models.

The DG Clima draft states that “*all farm activities must be monitored in case of leakage to non-certified parcels*”. EURAF feels this may dissuade farmers from applying for certification and could complicate use of the DGCLIMA geospatial carbon certification registry.

23.4. Improvement of CRCF: activity period and monitoring period

The minimum **activity period** proposed by DG Clima of 10 years is acceptable. This is the shortest period possible for an agroforestry rotation (e.g. for poplars in the Po Valley). Most rotations will be 20-50 years.

The minimum **monitoring period** for agroforestry should also be 10 years. Again, if trees are 5 years old when monitoring starts they will be 20 when monitoring stops. This is too old for some fast-growing agroforestry.

23.5. Improvement of CRCF: Total carbon removals and/or soil emission reduction

DG Clima should maintain a list of “approved” agroforestry models/tools for certification. The DigitAF project has a provisional list of list such tools in its page on Tools, Data and Projects

Agroforestry projects should make projections using at least 3 different “approved” models/tools to gain an estimate of “uncertainty”.

23.6. Addressing uncertainties in conservative manner

Measure-Remeasure techniques may be unreliable in agroforestry for below ground biomass and fine root turnover because of 3-dimensional spatial variability. A modelling approach is inevitable and some existing models were recommended in the Dublin workshop ([Thissen 2025](#))

Almost all crop-management methods suggested in the *Carbon Farming Technical Guidance Handbook (2021)* can be used in the crop-alleys of agroforestry systems. One exception is a 100% no till system, where a subsoiler of chisel plough will need to pass close to the tree-lines, at least every second year, to ensure that tree roots do not compete excessively with crops in the surface soil horizons.

Branch pruning increases fine root turnover in proportion to the loss of above ground living biomass and should be included in biophysical and statistical models of agroforestry.

Strong links are needed with research projects like DigitAF, Reforest, MARVIC and MRV4SOC. These can help develop allometric equations to convert tree height and diameter to above and below-ground biomass. Allometry derived from forest stands will be inaccurate because trees have different form factors and less below ground biomass. Existing databases like BAAD, GlobAllomeTree, and FigShare, Mendeley therefore need to be extended for open-grown trees.

23.7. Additionality - Financial test

In the CAP 2014-2022, across the EU, only around 5k hectares of agroforestry were planted from a target of 89k.

In the CAP 2023-2028 only 9 countries have agroforestry measures, often with very low support rates and implementation in only a few regions (IT, ES, DE). The measures include financial support for afforestation. The agroforestry component is a small part of the total, but breakdowns are not available on the DG Agri portal. No Member State provides a complete package of support: i.e. including each of Article 31, Article 73 and Article 70.

For agroforestry-carbon-farming to succeed it is vital that 4 linked interventions are offered in all Member States:

- **Initial soil sampling and planning** - year 0, CAP Article 31 Eco Scheme
- **Planting and protection of trees** - year 1, CAP Article 73 investment Measure - possibly also Article 74 for irrigation.
- **Early years maintenance support** - years 2-5, CAP Article 70 - Agri Environment Climate annual payment
- **Adoption into a registered agroforestry carbon farming scheme** - from year 6 onwards, following satisfactory tree and soil monitoring.

23.8. Guarantee of permanence – Landscape features

Most carbon farming schemes approach the need for "permanence" of carbon removals by requiring operators to guarantee that carbon sequestration practices will be maintained for a minimum period. For afforestation (ARR) certification this assumes a given rotation period. In most countries, afforestation projects involve permanent change in land use, and carbon certification operators are required to maintain the forested areas in perpetuity. At the end of a plantation rotation, operators are required to obtain a felling licence from the forest authorities, and must regenerate the felled area, or in exceptional circumstances they can establish a similar area of forest nearby. This degree of permanence also applies to trees, lines of trees and small groups of trees which are recognised and mapped as **GAEC8 landscape features** on agricultural land.

Thus, in the LPIS systems of Member States it is important to distinguish agroforestry-carbon-farming systems where lines of trees have been formally mapped as woody landscape features (using PMEF Result Indicator 17.4) from those where trees are not mapped in this way (e.g. parkland areas with scattered trees). This legal "guarantee of permanence" could be reflected in the carbon price offered in the same way as with carbon in afforestation and reforestation projects.

Some Member States don't implement or map "Landscape Features" (e.g. FI, SE, MT). Further discussions with these Member States will be appropriate if agroforestry-carbon-farming is to be encouraged across Europe

Those Member States which map landscape features in their IACS-GSAA-LPIS systems do so in different ways.. In the CAP 2007-2014 they were recorded in a separate Ecological Focus Area layer of the LPIS as polygons or polylines (ref to Wimé paper on layers). The EFA layer (Van der Weldle, pers comm) is now being integrated in the main GSAA layer, but it is very unclear how much progress Member States are making with this.

Also unclear is the degree to which Member States make their GSAA and LPIS data available openly through their INSPIRE portals, although openness of this data has improved markedly in the past year (Table 2), and is being exploited in the Regenfarmer/DigitAF "**LPIS aggregator**"

The [DigitAF](#) project is seeking to superimpose Copernicus % Tree Cover Density onto LPIS data for a range of countries in the EU ([Milestone 6 Report](#)). This will give an indication of the current extent of agroforestry and allow future planting to focus on the

[detailed areas](#) and [NUTS3 provinces](#) which have the highest proportion of “tree deserts”.

The IACS-GSAA-LPIS data only contains “active farmers” whose minimum payments range between €100 and €500 and/or have minimum holding areas ranging from 0.3 ha to 4 ha (depending on the Member States). The DG CLIMA Register of Carbon Farming, which is [due to be developed by 2028](#), will need to include codes for parcels owned by smaller farmers and also forest parcels. Some form of link to cadastral codes is also possible.

Governments could underwrite the risk of accidental loss of carbon by fire or other damage to trees. This insurance option requires further investigation. An advantage of agroforestry compared to conventional afforestation is that fires are much less likely, and less damaging if they do occur ([Wolpert et al 2022](#)).

23.9. Calculation of standardized baselines

CAP GSAA and LPIS systems show the location of agroforestry parcels and woody landscape features: the latter usually in a separate Ecological Focus Area (EFA) layer. Member states vary significantly in the access they provide to this data and in the classifications used. Greater harmonisation and open data access is needed for the DG Clima geospatial parcel register of carbon farming parcels which is promised by 2028. Sentinel 2 data gives Tree Crown Density data at 10m resolution. This is useful for broad summaries, but agroforestry carbon farming needs access to <50cm resolution Orthophotos, and probably also lidar data.

Standardised baselines in the CRCF are intended to calculate the average carbon capture in an area given knowledge of local climate, soil type and cropping patterns. They could be used to measure the sequestration and emission reduction impact of a farmer against peers in similar areas. Ideally, the comparisons should be carried out using **pedoclimatic zones** (e.g. [Toth 2016](#)) rather than political areas like NUTS2 or NUTS3, but these it is not certain that these classifications exist in sufficient details. The authors initially thought that standardised baselines could be based on GSAA-LPIS Municipality (NUTS4) data, but the areas of these seem too small and variable to be of practical use in most Member States (Table 3). **Another option would be to fix a 10x10 km “bounding box” around each farm applying for carbon certification and calculate a “standardised baseline” using the average land use and soil information derived from GSAA-LPIS for the whole 10 kha box.**

23.10. Suggested agroforestry management plan

EURAF suggested in a submission to DG FISMA (EURAF [Policy Briefing #28](#)) that Climate Delegated Act of the EU Sustainable Finance Taxonomy Regulation should reinsert the initially proposed section on sustainable agriculture. The Delegated Act should contain sustainable management criteria for agroforestry, alongside the existing sections on forestry and paludiculture. The structure suggested for an agroforestry carbon-farming management plan was as follows.

- Location of the parcels and boundaries using codes from the national IACS/LPIS system (or equivalent);

- Location of neighbouring forest and agricultural blocks, showing habitat linkages between wooded areas and the role of ACF parcels in fire-management plans for adjacent forests;
- Baseline estimates of carbon-stocks in each certified parcel including soils and above-ground biomass;
- Management goals, design, species and predicted carbon sequestration of areas covered by trees;
- Management goals and predicted carbon sequestration of the intercropped or grazed alleys;
- Environmental context of the farm(s), including main existing and intended tree species;
- Details of access, environmental constraints, registered landscape-features and legal restrictions on land-use change;
- Details of engagement with neighbours and local stakeholders, in accordance best practice nationally;
- Assessment of agroforestry related risks, including fires, pests and diseases outbreaks and plans to mitigate these;
- Assessment of impact on food production of the farm(s) included in the plan;
- Evaluation of “co-benefits” for biodiversity

- Evaluation of “do no significant harm” (DNSH) criteria for other areas of “sustainability”.

3.24 Session 24: Carbon farming challenges in Mediterranean agriculture: resilient project solutions and certification pathways

Main organisers: Agri Marketplace, BETA Technological Centre, CREA-AA, SLM Partners, Tetis Institute S.r.l, Università degli Studi di Genova

Session description

Carbon farming can represent a resilient, sustainable agricultural production system offering a new green business model to generate additional revenues through regenerative agriculture and agroforestry practices. It also facilitates the adoption of carbon credits' schemes. This is extremely relevant for the Mediterranean area, marked by unique pedoclimatic conditions and low SOC content. Proper management can transform the area into a significant carbon sink, as the most carbon-depleted soils have the greatest capacity to store carbon. Mediterranean crops often face challenges from carbon-depleted soils, exacerbated by hot, dry climates and water scarcity, requiring significant efforts to restore SOC while addressing farmers' economic barriers and knowledge gaps. This session will explore solutions from Carbon Farming initiatives and their potential to harmonize CRCF at regional and European levels. These initiatives focus on increasing carbon removal and reducing GHG emissions in agricultural systems through scientifically grounded practices, aimed at evaluating and improving

methods for quantifying carbon stored in agricultural soils and monitoring carbon removals.

This session shared lessons learned in project experiences, highlighting strong synergies that could be established among scientific and academic communities, consultancy experts, farmers' associations and certification bodies, despite challenges, thereby fostering an integrated approach addressing existing knowledge gaps. The establishment of a methodological and certification framework of carbon farming in the Mediterranean area is fundamental to producing concrete field-applicable outcomes that can guide the European Commission and stakeholders towards Europe's 2050 carbon neutrality goals.

Issues

1. Carbon Farming in the Mediterranean
2. Sustainable business model
3. Standardisation and harmonisation of the certification framework

Recommendations

24.1. Open Question

The promotion and support of sustainable land management practices is extremely relevant for the Mediterranean, as this region is characterized by low soil organic carbon content and has a large potential to become a carbon sink if appropriately managed. Establishing a theoretical framework of carbon farming in the Mediterranean, quantifying both carbon sequestration in the soil and avoiding GHG emissions is very important.

To whom: Scientists, Land managers

24.2. Concrete step for implementation

Carbon farming efforts should directly relate to the business model of the agricultural economy having a substantial impact, leading to a capitalisation based on existing models and best practices. Promoting a Mediterranean market of carbon credits generated by regenerative agriculture requires developing effective tools for the market adoption of carbon farming as a business model, and to bring Mediterranean carbon buyers and sellers together to benefit from a common market of carbon credits. A tailored techno-economic model is crucial for estimating the investment costs needed to transition from conventional production to a carbon farming model. This model should also evaluate land requirements and project the payback period, enabling key stakeholders to make informed decisions, design effective public policies, and foster engagement from the primary sector.

To whom: Business operators, Policy makers

24.3. Open Question

Carbon certification schemes for carbon farming practices have to be harmonized by the EC to provide trustability in the voluntary carbon market. The CRFC is trying to tackle this problem by developing a regulatory framework, but it has not yet been implemented. Perhaps, given the agro- and pedoclimatic complexity of the Mediterranean, one of the interesting questions for those responsible is “is it necessary to develop methodologies adapted to the region?”

To whom: Developers of carbon schemes certifications, Policy makers, Scientists, Business operators

24.4. Open Question

Establishing reliable baselines and appropriate permanence periods is crucial for carbon farming in agriculture. Baselines provide a reference to measure improvements in carbon sequestration, ensuring accurate assessment of climate benefits. It is important to define a protocol for agriculture to standardize the methods. Adequate permanence periods guarantee that sequestered carbon remains stored in the soil long enough to contribute to long-term climate mitigation, preventing short-term reversals and ensuring the effectiveness of carbon farming initiatives. To date, permanence periods are based mainly on forests, are too long for agricultural crops, and make it difficult for farmers to approach selling carbon credits. Specific procedures should be thought of for agriculture, also based on pedo-climatic areas.

To whom: Developers of carbon schemes certifications, Policy makers, Scientists, Business operators

24.5. Proposal to improve CRCF

The issue of additionality in agriculture for carbon farming lies in ensuring that carbon sequestration practices lead to genuine, new reductions in greenhouse gas emissions beyond business-as-usual activities. If farmers are already implementing sustainable practices, it is important to reward them without requiring further improvements or monitoring the increase of carbon stock. Additionality must be assessed in a double procedure, if best practices are already implemented or if they are not. Moreover, the criteria for additionality in various certification standards can differ and may often be unclear. Therefore, it is essential to harmonize these criteria as much as possible, including the methodologies and indicators to be used. Finally, it is important to establish a timeframe for the permanence of these additional effects to maintain eligibility within a certification scheme.

To whom: Developers of carbon schemes certifications, Policy makers, Scientists, Business operators

24.6. Concrete steps for implementation

Social acceptance of carbon farming practices by farmers is fundamental to their correct implementation. However, perceptions of these production practices vary widely. Social factors influencing the adoption of carbon farming practices need to be assessed, to tailor recommendations and promote their adoption. One of the key issues is the lack of

knowledge among farmers about what carbon farming entails and its implications. In this respect, knowledge exchange processes and support networks are crucial for scaling up these practices. In addition, the diversity of farmers' motivations, values and professional identities leads to different positions and predispositions towards sustainable farm management. Since farmers are not a homogeneous group, understanding the values and preferences that shape their practices is essential to effectively promote carbon farming.

To whom: Policy makers, Scientists, Business operators

3.25 Session 25: Opportunities and challenges in proximal sensing–based monitoring for carbon farming

Main organisers: University of Helsinki, Wageningen University, Yard Stick PBC

Session description:

Proximal sensing technologies hold great potential for advancing carbon farming practices across Europe by enabling accurate, cost-effective monitoring of carbon (C) dynamics. These technologies offer significant support for the Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) of carbon sequestration. In this session, organized by CREDIBLE Focus Group 3.2 (FG3.2), we will explore how proximal sensing can enhance sustainable agriculture, particularly through precise measurement of carbon storage in soils and vegetation. By providing reliable data on soil carbon dynamics, these technologies can help land managers make informed decisions in carbon farming initiatives and provide the rigorous MRV required if carbon farming efforts will provide real economic value to land managers and project developers alike. However, challenges remain, especially around digitalization, user-friendliness, and cost-effectiveness for land managers.

The session explored various related aspects of proximal sensing for soil C and carbon farming from other leading soil C market stakeholders. Its aim was to foster a deeper understanding of the opportunities proximal sensing offers for carbon farming while addressing concepts and bottlenecks of (automated) monitoring and verification processes via proximal sensing tools.

Issues

Advancing carbon farming through proximal sensing technologies

- How proximal sensing tools can enable accurate and cost-effective monitoring of soil and vegetation carbon dynamics, enhancing sustainable agriculture and carbon sequestration efforts?

Challenges in implementation and adoption

- Critical challenges, including the need for improved digitalization, user-friendliness, and cost-effectiveness of proximal sensing technologies to ensure broader acceptance and usability among land managers.

Strengthening MRV protocols and economic viability

- The role of proximal sensing in strengthening MRV protocols to ensure the economic value of carbon farming initiatives, while addressing the bottlenecks in technology integration and market alignment.

Recommendations

25.1. Concrete steps for implementation

Proximal sensing technologies (e.g., VIS-NIR-MIR spectroscopy) provide a cost-effective and scalable measurement method for MRV (Measurement, Reporting, and Verification) of soil organic carbon (SOC), enabling more frequent, yet still accurate monitoring for carbon farming initiatives. Hence, relevant EU legislation (e.g., under delegated acts and implementing acts) should ensure that MRV strategies incorporate proximal sensing technologies alongside laboratory chemical analysis (used for calibration and validation).

To whom: European policymakers, Carbon Market regulators, and certification bodies

25.2. Concrete steps for implementation

EU funding should be increased to support research and innovation in proximal sensing technologies. For example, funding aimed at enhancing the accuracy of proximal sensing technologies would accelerate their adoption in MRV. Such funding could focus on building or extending open-source proximal sensing data libraries, such as those developed by ISRIC, which are required to estimate TOC. At present, most extensive libraries are privately owned.

To whom: European policymakers, Carbon Market regulators, and certification bodies

25.3. Lesson learnt

A good-but-not-perfect methodological framework should be prioritized over delayed perfection to avoid stalling progress. Verra VM0042 is an example of a well-developed rounded methodology. However, VM0042 has detailed guidelines on bulk density (BD) which potentially hinder proximal sensing-focused projects. To support carbon farming, a more flexible methodology could be developed to prevent valuable projects from being sidelined due to overly restrictive criteria. When an approach is peer-reviewed and published in a scientific journal this can be seen as an indicator of the quality of the approach.

To whom: European policymakers, Carbon Market regulators, and certification bodies.

3.26 Session 26: Integrating MRV methodologies and Incentives to Reduce N₂O Emissions in Carbon Farming

Main organisers: i-BEC, Proba

Session description:

This session explored how integrating advanced tools of remote proximal sensing, with sustainable agricultural interventions can enhance monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) efforts, enabling carbon finance mechanisms.

Reducing N₂O emissions requires the adoption of practices like Enhanced Efficiency Fertilizers (EEFs), which optimize nitrogen use efficiency and reduce emissions at the source. Complementary approaches, such as incorporating biostimulants and biochar, further support emission reductions while improving soil health and crop productivity. However, these advanced practices often present financial barriers for farmers. To overcome this, incentivization mechanisms like voluntary carbon market (VCM) credits and insetting frameworks within agri-food supply chains are essential. These mechanisms align corporate climate goals with sustainable agricultural practices, creating financial rewards for farmers while ensuring compliance with international carbon standards.

The session discussed a pathway for integrating state of the art MRV methodologies, innovative agricultural practices such as EEF, and robust incentivization mechanisms into carbon farming. By doing so, it aims to reduce N₂O emissions, enhance soil health, and deliver measurable, verifiable climate benefits that align with both farmer livelihoods and corporate sustainability objectives.

Issues

1. Adoption of enhanced efficiency fertilizers to reduce fertilizer related emissions
2. Standards and Baselines
3. Adoption of new MRV technologies for related quantifications

Recommendations

26.1. Proposals to improve CRCF

As agriculture relies heavily on fertilizer use, which significantly contributes to global emissions, carbon farming must go beyond carbon sequestration to include targeted strategies for reducing N₂O emissions. Reducing N₂O emissions requires the adoption of practices like Enhanced Efficiency Fertilizers (EEFs), which optimize nitrogen use efficiency and reduce emissions at the source. However, these advanced practices often present financial barriers for farmers. To overcome this, incentivization mechanisms like voluntary carbon market (VCM) credits and insetting frameworks within agrifood supply chains are essential. These mechanisms align corporate climate goals with sustainable agricultural practices, creating financial rewards for farmers while ensuring compliance with international carbon standards.

How to get the upstream industries to play along:

Most agricultural decarbonization projects target reductions in the range of 20–30% for fertilizer-related emissions. Achieving over 50% reduction is rare and noteworthy.

Large-scale adoption of advanced technologies like CRF, nitrification inhibitors, or green ammonia-based fertilizers is still emerging, especially in coordinated efforts across supply chains.

To whom: farmers, food processors/retailers, policy-makers, MRV technologies providers

26.2. Open questions

Climate resilience, particularly in the context of carbon farming, requires the adoption of interdisciplinary research and technological advancements to address open issues related to accuracy and scalability. These challenges directly impact the credibility, effectiveness, and operational feasibility of carbon farming initiatives. Current methods for measuring nitrous oxide, carbon dioxide, and methane emissions lack standardization and scalability, making it difficult to ensure reliable monitoring across different landscapes. Further work is needed to establish robust protocols that integrate advanced MRV technologies, including remote sensing, in-field sensors, and AI-supported process-based modeling.

The widespread adoption is hindered by the absence of universal frameworks for assessing the effectiveness of new technologies and practices aimed at emission reduction and soil carbon sequestration. Without standardized methodologies, stakeholders struggle to verify the impact of climate-smart agricultural practices, limiting their integration into policy and market-based mechanisms.

To whom: policy-makers, businesses, government, academia

26.3. Concrete steps for implementation

The integration of low-cost, portable field-deployable sensors as part of an advanced N₂O toolkit for Monitoring and Reporting (MR) can support carbon monitoring, expanding the capabilities of traditional wet-lab approaches, enabling real-time, on-site measurement of nitrous oxide emissions, offering a scalable and cost-effective method of tracking emissions directly in the field. By complementing wet-lab testing, immediate, actionable data can be acquired to optimize agricultural practices for carbon sequestration and emissions reduction. This technology not only enhances the accuracy of environmental assessments but also facilitates more efficient, decentralized monitoring, supporting the compliance with carbon market standards and incentive schemes.

In parallel, these tools can be integrated with Nature-Based Solutions (NBSs) to orchestrate a synchronized effort. NBSs are recognized as effective tools for carbon sequestration, as they mimic natural processes to address land use and management,

promote human health, and enhance biodiversity. The CARBONICA HORIZON project exemplifies how such innovations can support end-users in transitioning to sustainable agricultural practices, creating a comprehensive system that links real-time data collection with sustainable land management strategies.

To whom: policy-makers, businesses, government, academia

26.4. Lessons learnt

Establishing project-based baselines is essential to ensure that carbon claims are based on accurate, localized baselines and new data acquisitions, which helps prevent overestimation and ensures credibility. The use of Earth Observation technologies enables reliable monitoring of land use changes and carbon sequestration at scale, providing data necessary for verifying carbon credits. Additionally, standardized approaches are crucial for validating innovations in climate-resilient testing. Developing clear standards for assessing new agricultural practices and technologies ensures consistent evaluation, allowing for better investment and policy making. The financial viability of carbon farming also remains a critical challenge, as farmers and land managers often face high upfront costs with uncertain economic returns, discouraging investment in sustainable practices. To address this, new incentive mechanisms—such as VCMs—must be developed, and should be supported by reliable, scalable methodologies and cost-effective solutions that ensure accessibility and economic feasibility for all stakeholders.

To whom: Policy makers (who will be responsible for the definition of the standardized baseline) and project developers and farmers (who will be responsible for carbon farming implementation).

3.27 Session 27: Unlocking data for MRV: Data sharing for effective carbon farming

Main organisers: Agrosolutions, ELGO-DIMITRA, Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture,, Fisheries and Food (ILVO), Soil Capital

Session description

The digitization and automation of robust Measurement, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) systems within the CRCF framework are critical to scaling carbon removal activities effectively. Accurate MRV systems rely on high-quality soil carbon (meta)data and associated farm activity data, which are crucial for calibrating and validating models. However, soil carbon (meta) data is often scattered across various platforms and initiatives.

Building upon insights from the Credible FG3.4 discussion, we emphasize the critical role of long-term monitoring site (LTM) data in i) calibration, validation, and simplification of models, ii) validation of MRV approach, iii) upscaling results from local to regional level and iv) support for digitalization. One major challenge highlighted in our earlier

analysis was the limited access to open data and the lack of effective data-sharing mechanisms. Similar issues were observed from the 1st European Carbon Farming Summit that soil databases that are not shared for broader application—particularly by the private sector. This highlights the urgent need for greater inter-sector transparency and collaboration.

This session expanded the scope of discussion beyond LTM data to include both public and private datasets and seek to address the challenges of data quality and accessibility. Potential solutions include promoting open access and exploring dual licensing for data sharing. Federated Learning approaches and Data-sharing platforms also present promising solutions for addressing privacy and competitive concerns.

Issues

- What data is required for farmers to claim public subsidies (e.g., under the Common Agricultural Policy) and to participate in voluntary carbon markets?
- How can we reduce the burden on farmers when reporting and collecting data for multiple purposes?
- What business models or reward systems could incentivize effective data sharing in public and private sectors?
- How do companies enable trust in data sharing along the value chain?

Recommendations

27.1. Recommendation for action

Adopt “**Collect Once, Use Many Times**” principle by utilizing user-friendly software connecting with data-sharing platforms

- Farmers face repetitive data requests from CAP, carbon farming projects, and scope 3 emissions, leading to fatigue and errors.
- Invest in **interoperable digital platforms** to connect existing systems via **APIs**, so that data entered once can serve multiple reporting needs.
- **Goal:** reduce administrative burden and improve data accuracy

27.2. Recommendation for action

Implement clear data sharing agreements & incentivize data exchange

- Researchers and private companies often mistrust each other over data ownership and usage rights.
- Create **standard data sharing agreement templates** (e.g., dual licensing for LTM data or including third parties in case of joint ownership of data) that

define commercial vs. non-commercial use, ensure proper citations, and offer federated modelling without sharing raw data.

- o Introduce a “**research commenting period**” where project developers share relevant documents with data contributors for review (e.g., within 30 days); install procedures for transparent publication of the reviews.
- o Enhance trust and incentivize data exchange for maintaining LTM. A transparent environment where stakeholders feel confident about the fact that their data is used ethically and effectively.

27.3. Recommendation for action

Extend LTM networks to **on-farm monitoring networks**

- o Current LTM sites were not specifically designed for carbon farming, resulting in limited representation across pedoclimatic regions, lack of certain management practices, and smaller plot sizes.
- o Establish on-farm monitoring networks, including commercial farms, to capture real-life conditions relevant to carbon farming.
- o Expand LTM design to an on-farm monitoring network with real-life data can help validate MRV tools at field scale and improve overall accuracy.

27.4. Recommendation for action

Enhance trust in **data sharing along the value chain**

- With diverse stakeholder interests, data-sharing arrangements must prioritize **transparency, accountability, and mutual benefits**.
- For the 3rd ECFS, we will dive deeper into secure infrastructures and privacy regulations to engage all stakeholders along the value chain for a sustainable transition.

3.28 Session 28: Baseline approaches for monitoring soil carbon removals: public – private synergies

Main organisers: GMV, ILVO, INRAE, JRC

Session description

In the voluntary carbon markets, an activity should generate carbon removals or soil emission reductions in excess of a baseline to respect the ‘additionality’ principle. In mineral agricultural soils, the baseline represents the change of the soil carbon stock in time under the business as usual (BAU) scenario, as if farming activities under a carbon farming project would not have occurred. When calculating net carbon removals by

farming activities, the carbon removal (or reduced emissions) achieved should then be subtracted from the baseline—a key component in carbon farming projects.

Existing MRV methodologies in the Voluntary Carbon Market mostly adopt baselines that are specific for a field or farm. The Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Regulation (CRCF), however, requires a standardised baseline rather than activity-specific baselines. These standardised baselines should be highly representative of the standard performance of comparable practices and processes in similar social, economic, environmental, regulatory and technological circumstances and take into account the geographical context, including local pedoclimatic and regulatory conditions. The Joint Research Centre (JRC) and the EU-funded research projects MARVIC, MRV4SOC and ORCaSa proposed several options to calculate the standardised baseline for carbon removals in mineral soil. In the Annex I of the Draft CRCF methodology for mineral soils and agroforestry that was presented to the CRCF expert group in October 2024, these options were summarised into two major groups: (a) an average change in soil carbon stocks, for example by a combination of inventory-based (LUCAS) and large scale modelling downscaled by machine learning and (b) the modelled standard practice in a region with similar pedo-climatic circumstances. The first approach provides a mean delta SOC (ton C/ha/year) for a given area under similar conditions. For the modelled practice-driven option, a hybrid “specific-standardised” approach is proposed, where the baseline is modelled using farm-specific soil data and standard regional practices as input. While those approaches underlie different interpretations of the standardised baseline concept and explore some possible methods, several others approaches are possible. These encompass the scale of applicability (EU or regional), calculation ex-ante or re-calculated ex-post, types of models and model combinations used, with or without remote sensing data assimilation.

This session reflected on the different options to calculate standardised baselines and to reflect on what the public sector can provide and what private sectors need related to their experiences in practice. Through open dialogue, the session aimed to identify differences in our methodologies, and to find collaborative solutions. Additionally, this session highlighted the importance of regional contexts and the role of pedo-climatic and regulatory circumstances in establishing accurate and reliable baselines.

Issues

1. Will the Standardised Baseline (SB) serve CRCF objectives?
2. Will the SB encourage farmers to implement new sustainable farming practices?
3. How can we ensure that the EU 2050 Target will fully recognise CRCF efforts?
4. Will farmers that are engaged in a carbon program shift to CRCF?
5. Can SB values be treated as a range (corridor) to verify the project-specific baseline?
6. How can the SB serve all use cases and meet all stakeholders’ objectives?
7. How to ensure that the SB is properly defined so that it provides real environmental benefits?

Recommendations

28.1. Specific versus standardised baseline

Activity specific baseline:

Advantages:

- More specific for each farm
- Possible to reward reduced decomposition of OM

Disadvantages:

- Time consuming to calculate individual CO₂-plans
- Expensive soil samples
- Sensitive to interpretation
- Difficult to reward front runners who are already applying measures

Standardised baseline:

Advantages:

- Less time consuming to calculate individual CO₂-plans
- Easy to automate calculations
- Front runners can be rewarded

Suggestions:

- Choose regional standard based on modelling and soil sampling
- Go for activity-based rewarding: no need for time consuming calculations and expensive soil samples
- Focus on insetting

Challenge:

- How to set regional baselines that motivate a big group of farmers?

To choose a baseline, the discussion is: What is more important: having a strict and very reliable methodology but no farmers participating; or having a methodology that better fits farmers' practice and have more farmers participating. We should aim at the highest participation possible, because then most carbon is fixed.

28.2. Choosing multiple baselines

- Should multiple baseline types be considered, with clear guidelines on which is best suited for the MRV approach, project objectives, or farm profiles?
- Key baseline definitions and selection criteria should align on:
 - Temporal framework – Static vs. dynamic baselines.

- o Reference system – Rotational, harvest-to-harvest, or crop-specific.
- o Baseline approach – Counterfactual modelling vs. witness-site comparisons (as used in forestry and measure-and-remeasure methodologies).

28.3. A mixed approach

To address these challenges, we propose an alternative crop-specific counterfactual baseline approach. Under this method, each project year is compared to the same crop in the baseline scenario. The baseline is modelled using the same crop as in the project scenario for that year, while applying historical management practices specific to that crop. These practices are aggregated at the regional level, enabling standardization of common management practices prior to the practice change.

This approach retains field specificity by using crop-, soil-, and climate-specific data for each field while also introducing standardization through the application of regional-level management practices. The key advantage is that it provides the most accurate representation of how practice changes affect soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by eliminating the confounding effects of crop rotation inherent in the field-specific rotational baseline. Additionally, this approach aligns more closely with farmer decision-making, as practice changes are typically implemented at the crop level rather than the field level, which may encourage broader adoption. Finally, this methodology supports the implementation of Scope 3 emissions reduction projects by emphasizing practice changes at the crop level, facilitating integration into corporate sustainability frameworks.

3.29 Session 29: (Non)-permanence and time dependency of carbon sequestration in carbon farming – current accounting approaches and ways ahead

Main organisers: Agroscope, Agrosolutions, Thuenen Institute, Wageningen Environmental Research

Session description

Accrual of organic carbon in mineral soils and changes in GHG fluxes with peatland rewetting are often characterised by variable rates over time. For example, soil organic carbon sequestration tends to follow a hyperbolic shape with new steady states often reached after only a few decades. This has implications for the calculated climate effect. Perhaps even more importantly, both carbon uptake and emission savings are reversible.

Carbon certification frameworks currently address the risk of non-permanence by applying financial buffers to the amount of carbon credits calculated. This approach has limitations, especially as it does not use a scientific basis to establish the size of the buffers. In the end, the constraints emerging from the need to compare permanent and

temporary carbon removals may impose excessive administrative constraints on farmers and carbon farming projects, hindering their implementation at scale.

This session focused on the impact of this (non) permanency issues for the carbon removal market and monitoring with the overall aim of analysing and improving existing approaches.

Issues

Main issues addressed were:

- What are the climate impacts of permanent vs. non-permanent sinks or removals?
- What are the implications for monitoring beyond the project period?
- How do current certification schemes deal (or not deal) with the issues of changing rates, non-permanence and additionality?
- how relevant is the “CO₂ equivalent” unit to account for climate benefit of non-permanent removals?
- Are current payment schemes and incentives suitable for dealing with non-linearities and non-permanence?

Recommendations

29.1. Proposal to improve CRCF

If the issue of non-permanence is addressed through permanency discounts, these should be based on a physics-based equivalence between the climate impacts of non-permanent and permanent removal. The absolute global warming potential based on cumulative radiative forcing could be used to calculate this equivalence on the basis of project activity and monitoring duration, and of a time horizon longer than 500 years or even 1000 years.

To whom: CRCF

29.2. Proposal to improve CRCF

If the issue of non-permanence is addressed through permanency discounts using the methodology in Recommendation 1, one should note that almost no cooling effect remains after all sequestered carbon is released. For temporary removals to be beneficial in terms of temperature change, the temporary removals must be maintained at least until global mean temperature is peaking.

To whom: CRCF

29.3. Proposals to improve CRCF

If temporary units are used to address the issue of non-permanence, a framework ensuring that **removals are constantly renewed** if the units expire (“stacking of removals”) is needed.

To whom: CRCF

29.4. Open question

Further research is needed to better characterize the amount of sequestered carbon that remains for decades/centuries if (i) the practice is stopped, (ii) the soil is disturbed, and under (iii) climate change, and combinations of all three (= what durability can we expect from carbon sequestration in soils?).

To whom: Research

29.5. Lesson learnt

The fact that carbon sequestering is a non-permanent climate mitigation option should not be a reason not to start with Carbon Farming. The radiative forcing method shows that at least a period of one or two decades of carbon removal is needed to diminish emission of CO₂ from the soil.

Land Use Change has a big influence on the carbon removal rate.

To whom: farmers, companies

3.30 Session 30: Addressing uncertainties and model benchmarking in Earth Observation-based MRV systems for carbon farming

Main organisers: CinSOIL GmbH, EARSC

Session description:

The objective of this session was to identify the key requirements and priorities for addressing uncertainties and model benchmarking for Earth Observation-based MRV for carbon removals. This is a critical issue in light of new regulations and schemes, particularly since uncertainty in organic carbon measurements can often exceed the actual changes. Meanwhile, multiple models are emerging, and there is a pressing need for consistent, fair benchmarking across varied soils, climates, and farming practices.

Participants shared lessons on how best to engage in understanding how to validate and compare different models, leading to more credible carbon removal assessments in carbon farming practices. This discussion is especially timely as organizations seek reliable proof of soil carbon gains, which support both climate goals and sustainable agriculture strategies.

Issues

Uncertainty in EO-based MRV impacts credibility and adoption

- Carbon removal schemes require reliable, transparent MRV. However, uncertainty in soil organic carbon measurements often exceeds actual expectations, creating challenges for verification and market credibility. (See Recommendation 30.1)

Benchmarking MRV models across diverse landscapes is essential

- Without standardized benchmarking, MRV models produce inconsistent results across different soils, climates, and farming practices, limiting comparability and trust. (See Recommendation 30.2)

Data governance is a key barrier to EO-based MRV adoption

- The lack of clear policies on data access, ownership, and interoperability limits the ability to integrate diverse datasets into MRV models. (See Recommendation 30.3)

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Data governance is a key barrier to EO-based MRV adoption

- The lack of clear policies on data access, ownership, and interoperability limits the ability to integrate diverse datasets into MRV models. (See Recommendation 30.3)

Recommendations

30.1. Proposals to improve CRCF

Establishing reasonable uncertainty thresholds and harmonized protocols to reduce them. Aligning policy and market expectations is critical to ensure acceptance and scaling of EO-based MRV systems.

Proposed steps:

- Develop sector-specific guidelines on acceptable uncertainty thresholds that balance scientific rigor with policy and market feasibility.
- Establish best practices for integrating EO data with in-situ measurements to enhance MRV accuracy.
- Align uncertainty thresholds with global carbon market requirements and regulatory frameworks to support investment in carbon farming.
- Promote transparency in uncertainty reporting to build trust among carbon credit buyers, farmers, land owners and policymakers.

To whom: Policy makers, researchers, MRV service providers, experts

30.2. Recommendations for action

Developing a structured EU-wide benchmarking framework with harmonized validation datasets is necessary to ensure fair and consistent assessments.

- Create a centralized platform with dedicated funding to enable fair benchmark of MRV models across different agro-ecological zones.
- Develop harmonized validation datasets covering varied soils, climates, and land-use practices to improve model comparability.
- Ensure that benchmarking methodologies align with international standards to enhance market acceptance and regulatory compliance.
- Engage industry, research institutions, and policymakers in the co-design of the platform to ensure practical implementation and usability.

To whom: Policy makers, researchers, MRV service providers, experts

30.3. Open questions

Stronger data-sharing frameworks, balancing privacy and accessibility, are needed to facilitate cross-sector collaboration and improve MRV performance.

- Establish clear policies on data ownership, sharing, and interoperability to facilitate the integration of public and private datasets into MRV systems.
- Promote EU-wide standardization of carbon farming data formats to enhance usability across MRV platforms.
- Develop guidelines on ethical data use and privacy protection, ensuring farmers and landowners rights are respected.
- Foster partnerships between policymakers, researchers, and industry to create an open-access data ecosystem for carbon farming.
- Promote the effort of harmonizing scattered data sources, for example collaborating with EEA Copernicus in-situ program.

To whom: Policy makers, researchers, MRV service providers, experts, EU agencies

3.31 Session 31: Earth Observation for Carbon Farming: exploring existing solutions and future user needs

Main organisers: ESA SEF

Session description:

This session aimed to raise awareness of Earth Observation (EO)-based tools that support Carbon Measurement, Reporting, and Verification (MRV), providing practical insights for end-users such as land managers, farmers, and policymakers. It introduced participants to existing EO solutions and highlighted their benefits and limitations. It gathered feedback from participants to identify short-term needs, such as training, and longer-term requirements that could inform future European Space Agency (ESA) projects.

Issues

- Understanding existing EO capabilities for carbon farming, more specifically for MRV
- Mapping the capabilities to the different “value chain” actors (e.g. carbon farming projects, certification/rating agencies, farmers/land managers)
- Identifying user needs (e.g. EO products or training)

Recommendations

31.1. Lessons learned

EO is being used by actors across the carbon farming value chain, from carbon credit certification/standardisation bodies and carbon rating agencies, to project developers and farmers.

These actors are using EO in several different ways, for example:

- Monitor among others: crop cover and tillage, deforestation rates, burn event analysis, wetland/forest detection, land use/land cover change, vegetation indices, soil vitality and soil parameters.
- Input for baseline establishment (e.g. historical data, input for SOC assessment) in combination with in-situ data.
- Assessing risk factors before, during and after the project, on the project parcels and around the project parcels.

This helps improve MRV methodologies, leading to a more transparent and robust carbon crediting process and ultimately enhancing the credibility and efficiency of carbon markets.

Whilst using EO brings added-value, some challenges remain, among others:

- Significant computational resources and expertise are needed to handle and integrate EO data, which stakeholders may not always have access to (e.g., project developers, VVBs, etc.)
- EO data quality varies due to sensor limitations, cloud cover, and differing resolutions, impacting the precision of carbon stock assessments.
- On-the-ground measurements remain essential to validate EO/satellite data which can make the process resource-intensive.

It is important to understand the added-value EO can bring to carbon farming, and especially MRV methodologies, encouraging its use in the CRCF and any carbon-farming related framework and practices. However, this should be done in a realistic manner, understanding the limitations of EO/satellite data, and not as the exclusive source of data.

To whom: Actors across the value chain

31.2. Concrete steps for implementation

It is necessary to continue to foster exchanges and interactions on the use of EO throughout the value chain to identify where the needs and gaps lie, and how to address them - whether this be an issue of capacity-building or an issue of capability development on the technical side.

For the technical side, the key discussion was around what EO is useful for, and for what not. EO is very useful for many parameters, but monitoring soil organic carbon (SOC) remains difficult. Technologies on this could be key and bring significant benefits. The other technical shortcoming mentioned is a lack of in-situ data, as EO technologies cannot exist without these data to ensure accuracy and reliability.

On the capacity-building and training side, there is a lack of awareness to be addressed when it comes to farmers. To work systematically on uptake of EO solutions in the carbon farming domain, there must be co-design, with the users involved in development. Additionally, a key stakeholder group identified is agronomists, who are often introducing farmers to new technologies and supporting them in the uptake and integration into their activities. Additionally, the importance of a regional or local approach was highlighted. It is important to work together with local and regional associations that represent farmers or land owners.

To whom: 1) Earth observation community, i.e., ESA and other EO experts who seek to increase the uptake of EO in carbon farming.

3.32 Session 32: Real-life MRV challenges and solutions for the EU CRCF

Main organisers: Agreeena, Seqana, Space4Good

Session description

This session aimed at sharing the real-world experiences of quantifying carbon sequestration in mineral soil and agroforestry projects. The consortium shared its collective experiences of implementing MRV across carbon removal projects under various methodologies and offered best practices for upcoming projects in the context of the EU CRCF methodology for mineral soils and agroforestry.

In particular, the session focused on three topics around (i) Quantification as discussed in the EU CRCF draft: smart soil sampling design, (ii) the quantification approach “Measure and Model”, and (iii) above-ground biomass modelling with remote sensing. It offered best practices for the EU CRCF based on industry experience.

Issues

- The current approach to MRV in EU CRCF is not scalable, as it prevents innovative high-quality approaches and technologies from being leveraged and raises too high demands for ground sampling.
- To allow the use of innovative approaches a simple yet precise and consistent approach to uncertainty estimation and deduction is needed, which is currently lacking.
- Sampling design requirements are confusing and must be simplified.

Recommendations

32.1. Proposals to improve CRCF

Uncertainty Estimation and Deduction must be aligned with best practices from IPCC and existing soil carbon markets:

- a. All quantification of carbon removals via carbon farming must account for uncertainty and only credit conservative estimates subjected to uncertainty deductions.
- b. Project proponents shall clearly and transparently report the overall uncertainty deduction of their project, including the breakdown into its components and how they were calculated.
- c. These conservative estimates and uncertainty deductions should be based on one-sided confidence intervals (aligned with IPCC and soil carbon market standards).
- d. A minimum confidence level (e.g. 67%) must be prescribed by the policy-makers to balance the risks of under-crediting (borne by operators) and over-crediting (borne by society).
- e. When a valid and objective uncertainty estimation and deduction process (as above) is prescribed, the choice of the quantification approach and technology can be left to the project proponent to use the best

technology/approach for the specific context under the condition that it complies with the uncertainty estimation and deduction to meet and document minimum requirements.

To whom: CRCF methodology authors

32.2. Proposals to improve CRCF

Sampling Design guidance must be simplified and aligned with uncertainty estimation/deduction. The only hard requirements, which must be implemented and documented are:

- Sampling design shall be design-unbiased (i.e. variant of a probability sample)
- The sample size must be at minimum large enough to allow for quantification of a conservative estimate (lower bound of one-sided Confidence Interval) with a tolerable error calculated as half of the expected SOC sequestration.

This requires ex-ante estimation of the SOC stock change and SOC Stock (change) variance, which must be well documented. In practical terms, this bare minimum sample size will allow crediting even with an uncertainty deduction as high as 99% as long as the actual SOC sequestration minus the tolerable error is greater than 0. However, project proponents are economically incentivized to take more samples than that to reduce their uncertainty deductions.

An example of one commonly used Sampling Design approach should be provided (e.g. Stratified random sampling with some guidance on how to do it). Project proponents can follow that example approach but can also deviate as long as they meet the hard requirements listed above.

To whom: CRCF methodology authors/operators/MRV providers implementing sampling designs/campaigns

32.3. Proposals to improve CRCF

Agroforestry systems require distinct MRV from forests

Agroforestry-specific and tree-species specific allometric equations or biomass conversion and expansion factors (BCEF) are needed to ensure correct calculations of carbon storage in aboveground and below-ground biomass. With this information currently lacking, certification methods often only provide guidelines based on experience from forestry, whilst tree allometry is very different in forests than in agroforestry systems. This could give huge discrepancies in the expected stored carbon and the true stored carbon. Certification schemes should critically assess the proposed biomass calculation methods by comparing the outcomes of different calculation methods.

Field data collection protocols for agroforestry should be based on random stratified sampling, meaning that a sufficient sample size is required per predefined strata based

on tree age, tree management, soil type, groundwater level, and other relevant differentiators. Previous datasets and the level of variation found in them should inform the sample size per stratum based on the standard deviation, alpha, power, and relevant difference.

To whom: to CRCF methodology authors

32.4. Lessons learnt

Allowing for innovative measurement technology (to CRCF methodology authors/operators/MRV providers):

The uptake of emerging technologies such as NIR field scanners for SOC or mobile laser scanning (MLS) for agroforestry should be stimulated since the cost-effectiveness of these techniques for estimating tree volume is likely to improve greatly within the next 5 to 10 years. Farmers could easily collect data with a mobile application/device, meaning low MRV costs, whilst also safeguarding the validity and coherence of the data. Current apps for measuring the diameter at breast height (DBH), such as ForestScanner, demonstrate the future potential of this technology.

To whom: CRCF Team

32.5. Lesson learnt: High Integrity Baseline

Use **multiple data sources** (historical records, field observations, primary data, remote sensing) to set the baseline. Prioritize **additionality & conservatism** in the baseline setting. Avoid “one-size-fits-all” standardization that dilutes on-farm, real change.

To whom: CRCF Team

32.6. Lesson learnt: Effective Monitoring at Scale

Integrate **satellite** with **ground truthing data collection** to ensure scalability of carbon farming monitoring initiatives. Automate field detection to manage broad geographic regions. What is the minimum we need to ensure we know what is happening on the field. Multiple sources for data checks. Integration of data sources will be important.

To whom: CRCF Team

32.7. Lesson learnt: Avoiding Double counting through data management

Establish **clear protocols** for data custody from field to credit issuance to avoid double counting. Incorporate **independent third-party audits** to reduce risks of fraud and guarantee the scientific rigour of applied methods. Verification tools already exist for checking field boundaries to ensure farmers or landowners are not participating. One big challenge is that auditors are not readily available - the market is small for on-the-field audits on a project level - certifying more auditors.

To whom: CRCF Team

32.8. Lesson learnt: Measure and model as a way to demonstrate constant improvements.

Combine **process-based models (e.g., RothC)** with **advanced remote sensing**. Measure and model support **annual credit issuance**. Enhance **economic viability** (better cash flow) and **scientific rigor over time**. Errors are already strong - so what you feed the model is important and how it is improved over time is also important.

To whom: CRCF Team

32.9. Lesson learnt

Use a combination of field data, remote sensing, and machine learning models to minimize manual labour for collecting field data, while keeping the local accuracy high. Labor is currently a high-cost factor for agroforestry carbon farming MRV. Current tools like CarboCatch demonstrate the potential to reduce field data. At some point, field data is expected to merely serve as a validation of model predictions, whilst the need for field data to train models will be minimised.

To: CRCF team

32.10. Lesson learnt

When using remote sensing for monitoring carbon sequestration in Agroforestry, a more detailed approach to account for mixed tree-crop structures, smaller-scale variations, and dynamic land use patterns, ensuring high model accuracy is required. While using mid-resolution satellite data (e.g., 10m of Copernicus) for carbon monitoring may suffice for forestry, it lacks the fine-scale detail necessary for agroforestry monitoring. Integrating very high-resolution satellite imagery (e.g., Pleiades Neo) and LiDAR data into MRV solutions will significantly enhance the precision of agroforestry carbon accounting. In addition, it has been found that locally trained models (on the same types of systems) outperform more generalized models.

To: CRCF team

32.11. Concrete steps for implementation

Advocating for freely available or partially open very high-resolution (e.g. 1.3meter resolution) data is essential to improve measurement accuracy, reduce uncertainty, and enhance the credibility of carbon farming. This will lower costs for project developers, increase financial returns for farmers, and support broader adoption of agroforestry as a recognized climate solution. Currently, these are available in some countries, but not in all, which creates an inequality in the access to affordable, accurate models. These high-resolution satellite images will not only benefit carbon farming measurements to be more accurate and more affordable, it will also support member states in monitoring other environmental/ social indicators, for climate resilience and other regulation compliance. For example, to report to the nature restoration law, improve flood and drought defense, generate insights for CAP and more. Advocating for higher-resolution

data will enhance compliance with EU regulations by making monitoring more accurate, affordable, and transparent, ultimately improving trust and traceability.

To: Copernicus/ EU Commission

3.33 Session 33: How technology and AI is supporting the growth of efficient, high-integrity carbon farming markets.

Main organisers: GreenO, SAS, Social Carbon Foundation, Walton Institute

Session description:

The evolving landscape of carbon farming projects demands processes that are rigorous, transparent, inexpensive and adaptable to meet growing market needs. This interactive session explored recent advancements in the use of AI and technology to address the major challenges to rapidly scaling high integrity carbon and environmental asset markets.

Leading practitioners addressed the market challenges, what they see as possible in the future and provided tangible examples of best practice they are involved with now. The session also addressed the system blockers and enablers that should be targeted to support rapid scaling of high-integrity markets.

The aim of the session was to provide practical insights into how digital tools and AI are setting new benchmarks in streamlining processes, cutting costs, and supporting the global expansion of high-integrity carbon markets.

Issues

- **Digitization of certification methodologies:** helping project developers access, apply, and comply with standards more effectively.
- **Documentation review:** Use of AI-powered tools that enable an automated pre-screening phase to check for accuracy, completeness, and compliance to help identify potential issues early in the process, reducing human error, providing faster feedback, and preserving data integrity.
- **Real-time Monitoring:** Using AI-powered tools to automatically track and analyse farming practices, soil health, and crop performance, ensuring precise data collection on carbon sequestration.
- **Data Validation and Credibility Checks:** Data validation by cross-referencing reported practices with satellite imagery, sensor data, and weather patterns to make it possible to detect inconsistencies and flag areas requiring further investigation, all while reducing manual efforts.
- **Automated Verification:** processes that significantly reduce the time and resources required for third-party audits, ensuring that farming initiatives comply with regulatory standards and market requirements.

- **Transparent Reporting:** Built-in reporting mechanisms make the entire process - from data capture to verification - auditable, providing full transparency to regulators, investors, and buyers of carbon credits.

Recommendations

33.1. Concrete steps for implementation

Participate in digital platforms that provide transparent access to carbon credit markets, ensuring fair pricing and reducing reliance on intermediaries.

To whom: Land Owners & Project Developers

33.2. Concrete steps for implementation

Leverage remote sensing & AI for real-time monitoring to enhance accuracy in measuring carbon sequestration and reduce verification costs.

To whom: Land Owners & Project Developers

Recommendation 33.3: Proposals to improve CRCF

Standardize digital verification and data protocols to ensure interoperability across different AI tools, fostering trust and comparability in the market.

To whom: Policy Makers & Regulators

Recommendation 33.4. Proposals to improve CRCF

Ensure AI models are transparent and explainable to avoid black-box algorithms

To whom: Technology companies

33.5. Proposals to improve CRCF

Invest in tech infrastructure that accelerates verification and reduces risks of over-crediting or fraud in voluntary carbon markets.

To whom: Investors and Credit Buyers

3.34 Session 34: Rewarding mechanisms: insights from farmers, agri-food companies and researchers for a successful approach

Main organisers: Climate KIC, DELOITTE, European Alliance for regenerative Agriculture, INRAE

Session description

This session aimed to contribute to the critical component of the CRCF directive: what financial incentive mechanisms would be most relevant for concrete advances in carbon farming? For these mechanisms to be effective, they must be adapted to the contexts and challenges of the main stakeholders.

To achieve this, the session discussed the current state of knowledge on existing rewarding mechanisms to provide key elements to the European carbon farming community and help identify challenges and opportunities for rewarding mechanisms.

Issues

- Who finances what in the transition and how much financing is available and is it sufficient to achieve the objective?
- How can we move from monoculture funding mechanisms that target greenhouse gases to a carbon farming type mechanism that covers greenhouse gases and removal?
- How can public and private funding be wisely combined to get traction within value chains from agrifood companies to farmers?

Recommendations

34.1. Lessons learnt

- There are diverse rewarding mechanism types, but limited incentives to finance the transition towards economically, ecologically, and socially sustainable agricultural systems.
- Most mechanisms focus primarily on large farm structures; regional strategies should support the adoption of more sustainable farming practices, aiming to include small farmers with limited scope.
- Current supportive measures to engage farmers in the transition (both on-farm and in policies) are still insufficient.
- There is limited articulation between funding instruments (due to double counting and additionality concerns).
- Most rewarding mechanisms focus on carbon removals and emission reductions. There are limited examples that consider climate adaptation.
- There is a need for rewards that support pioneer farmers who have implemented sustainable farming practices before the development of the CRCF.

To whom: Policymakers

34.2. Recommendations for action

- All stakeholders in the food chain need clarity on objectives, methodologies, frameworks, and reporting requirements. As with the concept of Regenerative Agriculture, there is currently no clear definition for Carbon Farming.

- To succeed, future regulations must foster the convergence of all forces. These forces include food chain actors such as farmers, industrials, retailers, policymakers, and solutions providers.
- To get traction at the European level, food chain actors need a supportive context: clarity, information sharing, training, solution access, and financial resources.
- It is essential to reward not only outcomes but also efforts, especially in the agricultural sector, which is influenced by pedoclimatic conditions.

To whom: Policymakers

3.35 Session 35: Learning from research and feedback from the field: how to put in place carbon farming on a farm? What levers and barriers?

Main organisers: Agrosolutions, Arvalis, Climate-KIC, IDELE, INRAE, Teagasc, Terre Inovia

Session description:

Several European projects (Climate Farm Demo, ClieNFarms, ORCaSa, LIFE Carbon Farming) are currently working on the topic of carbon farming. These projects have in common the fact of working with farmers putting in place low carbon practices. Therefore, it is interesting to give feedback from the field to illustrate the challenges that occur when talking about carbon farming implementation. Moreover, some of these projects can provide information on the types of practices put in place on farms.

Issues

- Assessing the feasibility and performance of carbon farming practices
- Ensuring access to knowledge on carbon farming practices
- Supporting multi-stakeholder collaboration to empower farmers in the climate transition

Recommendations

35.1. Lessons learnt

Context: There is a lot of information available on different carbon farming practices and carbon assessment tools, but farmers and advisors need additional skills to better understand and use these tools.

Recommendation: A structured capacity-building programme is essential to equip farmers and advisors with the skills needed to engage in carbon farming effectively. This program should:

- Cover both practical implementation and economic aspects (rewards, taxes, synergies between implementing carbon farming measures and farm profitability) as well as audit, MRV, and planning tools.
- Take a systemic and context-specific approach, integrating farm-level tools (there are no one-size-fits-all solution packages).
- Be designed with pedagogical best practices, offering flexible,
- time-efficient, and modular learning options to fit farmers' and advisors' schedules. Training should be accessible, both in terms of pedagogical design and in terms of costs (time and money).
- Begin at the educational level, integrating carbon farming into high school and agricultural school curricula.
- Be publicly funded or supported through policy frameworks to ensure accessibility.

If costs are involved, they should be accounted for in the cost-benefit assessment of carbon farming projects.

To whom: EU and national governments (Ministries of agriculture, environment, education)

35.2. Lessons learnt

Context: There is already a lot of information available on different carbon farming practices and carbon assessment tools, but this information is scattered across different platforms in Europe. It is difficult to find a full, clear, and up-to-date knowledge repository.

Recommendation: It is important to develop a permanent and dynamic repository of trusted information on Carbon Farming practices (for example Impact4Soil, Farming For Climate), advisory tools and carbon audit tools consolidated across all European projects. Each new project dealing with this topic should feed its insights and results to the common repository, preventing duplication of efforts and fostering knowledge exchange. Permanent funding to manage the repository is then needed.

To whom: EU Farmbook, EU Commission

35.3. Proposal to improve CRCF

Context: Farmers already have a lot of data to upload to different accounting or regulatory systems in order to get EU funds or other certificates

Recommendation: Simplify systems to lighten the administrative burden for farmers. The CRCF could help harmonise and simplify these processes. If the administrative burden is too heavy (or as heavy as for regulatory requirements), it will prevent farmers from engaging in voluntary projects.

To whom: CRCF

35.4. Proposal to improve CRCF

Context: So far the CRCF is mainly dealing with Carbon Storage and a bit with GHG emissions from soil management. However, “Greenhouse Gas” and “Carbon Storage” Emission Reductions are sometimes antagonistic: improving one may degrade the other.

Recommendation: It is necessary to address Carbon Storage and GHG emission together in order to improve the full carbon balance of farms.

Furthermore, a multicriteria sustainability assessment should be performed, without increasing data requirements too much, in order to have a systemic view of the impact of the different practices. This should integrate economic criteria but also social ones like additional workload as it can be unacceptable for some farmers. This should not be an eligible criteria to get the certification.

To whom: Research, CRCF

35.5. Proposal to improve CRCF

Context: There are many existing tools across Europe to assess GHG emissions and carbon storage on farms. These tools are adapted to national contexts and have been used by advisors for many years.

Recommendation: It is essential to base carbon farming projects on robust tools, on one hand to assess carbon footprints, and on the other hand to evaluate the potential credits generated under different transition scenarios that can actually be implemented by farmers.

Carbon audit tools: there should be several tools (robust) proposed to carry out carbon audits on farms, and not one unique tool for all Europe. Indeed, many advisors have already used tools, adapted to the local contexts.

MRV support tools are essential for implementing carbon farming projects, assessing the potential credits and also to evaluate possible different scenarios and then select the “best” one. There is a need for user friendly tools to help in comparison and choice.

To whom : CRCF

35.6. Proposal to improve CRCF

Context: In France, the current carbon market does not cover the break-even costs of a significant proportion of projects. Today, it can only encourage or help implement levers for the low-carbon transition.

Recommendation: It is necessary to either have a higher selling price for Carbon Credit, or supplement them with other sources of financing such as sector premium in cash crops sector.

CRCF should be aligned with the GHG protocol for carbon credits evaluation.

CRCF should allow farms to sell carbon credits and in the meantime to receive fundings from companies following SBTI rules. → Need clarification regarding double-counting.

To whom: Companies purchasing carbon credits, CRCF to allow diversified sources of fundings for the same farm.

35.7. Proposals to improve CRCF

Context: changing practices is not only a question of costs It is also a question of skills, workload, and risk.

Recommendation: regarding the Additionality aspect of the CRCF: it should not be restrained to an economic evaluation. Even if a low carbon project is cost-saving, it will not necessarily be implemented. There are potentially heavy initial investments, but also a risk taken by the farmers and that should be taken into account.

To whom: CRCF

3.36 Session 36: What is the farmer's opinion on carbon farming?

Main organisers: Bioeconomy Cluster, Carbery farmers cooperative, CoopsAgroES, French Agricultural Chambers, ICOS

Session description

This session presented the work carried out within the framework of the Credible project. This included a survey of around 40 experts on farmers' current perceptions of carbon farming.

The results of this work were used in the farmers' panel, moderated by John Brosnan from the Irish Co-operative Organisation Society (ICOS). A French farmer, a Slovak farmer, an Irish farmer, and a representative from Carbery Co-operative shared their views and proposed solutions to improve the image of carbon farming within the sector.

Issues

- Barriers to farmers joining the carbon farming journey?
- How is integrated carbon farming aligned with the broader challenges and trends in the farming community?
- What role should cooperatives and farmers' associations play in enhancing benefits for farmers?

Recommendations

36.1. Concrete steps for implementation

Develop local pilot projects and success stories and network of demo farms - establishment of demonstration farms and small-scale projects in each country to showcase real-world benefits and build trust among farmers.

To whom: Policy makers through CAP measures, or LIFE Program or Horizon Program

36.2. Concrete steps for implementation

To seek synergies with eco-schemes within the CAP by promoting best practices.

This applies in both, 1) economic terms: ensuring complementary payments—within the CAP for the voluntary implementation of best practices, and within the CFCR for achieving specific results in carbon sequestration 2) technical alignment of the practices proposed

To whom: DG Agri with DG Clima

36.3. Lessons learnt

Synergies should be sought with other relevant trends that also focus on SSM sustainable soil management, such as regenerative agriculture, carbon farming, precision agriculture, conservation agriculture, organic farming

To whom: Big farmers, International food corporations, Farmer cooperatives

36.4. Lessons learnt

Encourage farmer cooperation and collective strategies. For small and medium-sized farmers to feel that they are meaningfully part of the benefits of carbon farming, they can maximise these benefits through cooperation with their peers. Cooperatives in European countries where they are established, as well as other farmer groups elsewhere, can help channel positive opinions from their members by defining joint and shared strategies, leveraging economies of scale, and providing support through technical advisors

To whom: Farmer cooperatives

3.37 Session 37: Ireland: An Innovative, Context Specific, Approach to Carbon Farming...?

Main organisers: DAFM Ireland, Climate-KIC, Department of Environment, Climate and Communications (DECC), Irish Cooperative Organisation Society, Bord Bia, National Economic and Social Council, Environmental Protection Agency, Teagasc, Irish Strategic Investment Fund

Session description

This session brought together several farmers and experts from Ireland with the following aims:

- Highlight the approach being taken in Ireland to develop a national carbon farming framework.
- Identify barriers, opportunities and key stakeholder requirements for the development of a context specific national Carbon Farming framework.
- Identify key recommendations for the practical implementation of the CRCF and for the team in Ireland working on developing the national framework.

Challenges around soil health, water quality and biodiversity loss are inextricably linked to the emissions and removals challenge. Focusing solely on carbon farming (i.e. carbon removals in soil and above ground biomass) misses the interdependence between these ecological challenges, all of which are managed together within the farm system. This farm system operates in a broader social and ecological landscape, which is again part of a larger global food system.

Issues

- Barriers and Opportunities of a holistic approach e.g. including emissions, removals in a farm balance sheet approach with biodiversity and water quality as additional parameters
- Understanding stakeholder requirements: what are the priorities from a national carbon farming framework for each of these key stakeholder groups?

Recommendations

No recommendations

3.38 Session 38: From peatlands to policy: How praxis can guide EU CRCF certification

Main organisers: Aeco, DG Clima, Greifswald University, IUCN Peatland Programme, MoorFutures, UK Carbon Code

Session description

As the EU moves toward implementing the Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF), peatlands are envisaged to be the first land use category in the Land Use, Land-use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) sector with a published certification methodology. Even though certification for peatlands / organic soils is assumed to be easier and the process further elaborated compared to other LULUCF categories, ensuring its robustness, practicality and climatic justness remains a challenge.

This session explored how CRCF methodologies are being developed, providing insights relevant for peatlands specifically and for the evolution of the broader framework in general. It offered a platform to discuss region-specific barriers to certification and to explore potential solutions.

Issues

1. Peatlands as a model for CRCF certification
 - Peatlands are expected to be the first land category with a defined certification methodology under the CRCF, making them a key test case for the framework's effectiveness.
 - As one of the most carbon-dense ecosystems, peatlands play a crucial role in climate mitigation.
2. Communication strategies for CRCF policy implementation
 - Communication strategies are expected to be of major importance for the CRCF implementation success. Involvement of actors at all levels will help shape the implementation and stakeholder perceptions.
3. Ensuring alignment with EU and national policies
 - For CRCF certification to be effective, it must be compatible with and its units convertible into those of national GHG inventories and voluntary carbon markets.
 - Several European countries already have carbon credit initiatives for peatlands in place (e.g., Germany's MoorFutures, the UK Peatland Code), and their experience should inform the development of the CRCF methodology.
 - The quality (a ton is a ton) and additionality of peatland emission reductions and carbon removals must be ensured to attain confidence of carbon markets and policy frameworks.
4. Data availability and sufficiency
 - The impact of data on CRCF implementation and development.

Recommendations

38.1. Proposals to improve CRCF

Use the experiences from completed and ongoing peatland carbon credit projects to develop clear, standardized criteria for CRCF peatland carbon credit certification. CRCF certification must be transparent and consistent, scientifically robust and precise, and compatible with existing LULUCF reporting frameworks and the voluntary carbon market; certified reduction units must be fully fungible with, or at least convertible into, the units of these frameworks and markets.

To whom: European Commission (DG CLIMA, DG ENV), National Governments, Certification Bodies

38.2. Stakeholder Engagement & Capacity Building

Facilitate structured multi-stakeholder dialogue, ensuring that the knowledge and experiences from completed and ongoing peatland restoration and carbon certification projects are acknowledged and actively integrated into CRCF development.

To whom: EU Institutions, Member States, NGOs, Peatland Restoration Initiatives, Private Sector Players in the Carbon Market, Farmers

38.3. Clear and transparent communication

For an effective CRCF scheme implementation, we recommend prioritizing clear communication. Keep it simple, honest, and transparent—acknowledging uncertainties is key. Adopt a regional rather than a generalized EU-wide approach, emphasizing a bottom-up strategy that empowers local stakeholders. Foster trust as a foundation and ensure early and continuous engagement throughout the process.

To whom: EU Institutions, Member States, NGOs, Peatland Restoration Initiatives, Private Sector Players in the Carbon Market

38.4. Action-Oriented CRCF Implementation

Prioritize rewetting peatlands as soon as possible. While we might not have all the data, the overall need is clear. Begin with simple, smart strategies, then learn and adapt as needed. Avoid delays by striving for perfection—practical progress is better than inaction.

To whom: EU Institutions, European Commission (DG CLIMA, DG ENV), Member States, NGOs, Peatland Restoration Initiatives, Private Sector Players in the Carbon Market

3.39 Session 39: Legal opportunities for carbon farming: from creation of a registry to the necessary streamlining of the applicable environmental law framework

Main organisers: Philp Lee

Session description

This session proposed a discussion on the legal opportunities and issues relating to carbon farming, including the creation of registries and the streamlining of the applicable environmental law framework to enhance climate ambition.

Issues

- The necessity of streamlining EU environmental laws to successfully implement the CRCF
- Creation of a CRCF registry

Recommendations

39.1. Policy coherence

The AGRI team in DG Clima should proactively seek to work with the ENVI team in DG Enviro in order to reconcile carbon farming regulation with the existing environmental laws that underpin project authorisation. At present, the two regimes apply distinct,

difficult to reconcile requirements that will impede the authorisation of carbon farming projects.

39.2. Lesson learnt

The development of the Renewable Energy industry as provided for within RED III has demonstrated that under the existing European environmental law framework, tension arises between climate mitigation measures and traditional means of environmental protection as provided for in the environmental Directives including the Birds, Habitats, EIA and Water Framework Directives.

39.3. Open questions

To facilitate project authorisation, it is crucial that EU environmental laws impacting carbon farming projects are streamlined. At present, the CRCF Regulation does not recognise that it overlaps with such laws as the Birds Directive, Habitats Directive, Strategic Environmental Assessment Directive, Environmental Impact Assessment Directive and the Nature Restoration Law. All these laws contain different tests, definitions and obligations.

Article 7 of the CRCF provides that ‘an activity shall do no significant harm to the environment’. This test, borrowed from the EU Taxonomy Regulation, does not correlate with the tests for environmental assessment in the Directives listed above. These include ‘likely to have a significant effect’ and ‘negatively impact the integrity of the site’, for instance. Because the requirement for environmental assessment underpins project authorisation, this incompatibility under the law will inevitably lead to legal challenges.

The Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) can only interpret the law and as such EU Commission guidance – while it would be welcomed as an interim measure – is not sufficient where the wording of the law itself is not fit for purpose. Both the definition of ‘activity’ and that of ‘no environmental harm’ need to be equated with tests in the other environmental laws. Otherwise, carbon farming projects will be delayed and stopped on the basis of the wording in a Regulation that was in fact designed to ‘facilitate and encourage’ such projects. Unlike traditional means of environmental protection through conservation and limitations on development, climate mitigation measures require facilities for adaptive management and provision for pilot projects in the absence of complete data.

The test of ‘shall do no environmental harm’ cannot be achieved where precise data remains unknown. Yet, postponement of these projects until such data has been gathered precludes the necessary climate mitigation.

39.4. Lessons learnt

The constraining effect of the Birds Directive as currently drafted is evident as it is sought to develop renewable energy infrastructure. This will also arise in relation to carbon farming. The impact of well designed, well mitigated windfarms cannot be aligned with the obligations under the Birds Directive to prohibit killing or disturbance of all wild birds. No building, in fact, can comply with this. The obligation arises because of the

interaction of Article 1 and Article 5 of the Birds Directive as interpreted by the CJEU in the Swedish Logging and Finnish Wolves cases, for instance.

Similarly, where peatlands are regenerated their habitats will change, causing some birds to leave (they will be ‘disturbed’) and many others to arrive. Technically, this is a breach of the Birds Directive. Again, this illustrates tensions between climate mitigation measures and existing environmental protection laws that predate the era of required climate action.

39.5. Recommendation for action

EU Commission Guidance prepared by DG Clima (AGRI) and DG Enviro (ENVI) working together is required in order to inform Member States and prospective developers as to how these legal frameworks should be applied. Given the nature of carbon farming and the areas within which it can be most effectively deployed, this must encompass interplay with the Nature Restoration Law, the Natura 2000 network and wild birds in particular. How can projects be legitimately authorised in the absence of scientific certainty and complete data?

In conjunction, an update of the environmental protection directives to provide for climate mitigation should be advocated for. Adaptive management and pilot projects are an urgent necessity for effective climate mitigation. Lessons should be learned from the approach in RED III where incomplete ‘fixes’ were inserted. The involvement of ENVI is crucial in this regard.

39.6. Recommendation for action

In conjunction with the development of interim EU Commission guidance, an update of the environmental protection directives to provide for climate mitigation should be advocated for and developed.

Adaptive management and pilot projects are an urgent necessity for effective climate mitigation. Lessons should be learned from the approach in RED III where incomplete ‘fixes’ were inserted. The involvement of ENVI is crucial in this regard to ensure that a full understanding of the environmental Directives is brought to any amendments made.

39.7. Lessons learnt

The scale of the voluntary carbon market (VCM) has been limited by registry design.

The VCM registries do not recognise ownership of credits but rather rely on deeds of representation and warranties to evidence title. Further, the VCM registries do not recognise security interests. The impact of these design decisions has been to limit institutional capital and project finance.

For the CRCF to scale, debt financiers and ‘forward’ buyers must be able to take, and enforce, security interests.

39.8. Recommendation for action

The EU's report entitled "Scoping of the CRCF registry and minimum requirements for certification scheme registries" recommends the CRCF registry operate as a central repository rather than a fully operational registry. Future decisions on designing the CRCF registry should engage with the reasons for limited participation of institutional capital and project finance that have limited the VCM's scale.

39.9. Recommendation for action

The Supervisory Body for the Paris Agreement Crediting Mechanism (PACM) is considering the implementation of a pledge system for Article 6.4 emission reductions within the PACM registry. This is an important example of designing a cross-jurisdictional registry.

The design of the CRCF registry should consider the analysis of the Supervisory Body in February, which considered the legal, technical and financial implications of providing functionality for the treatment of financial security interests in Article 6.4 emission reductions within the PACM registry. This involved analysing the approaches taken in the VCM (e.g. Verra) and compliance markets (e.g. New Zealand Emissions Trading Scheme).

3.40 Session 40: Why do we need Direct Measurement to secure Europe's Carbon Farming Future?

Main organisers: AgriCarbon

Session description

In this engaging session, attendees discussed 'why direct measurement of soil carbon is essential to deliver carbon farming in Europe and how integration of different measurement approaches can optimise cost and confidence in carbon claims'

Issues

- Why direct measurement of soil carbon is essential to deliver carbon farming in Europe
- How integration of different measurement approaches can optimise cost and confidence in carbon claims'

Recommendations

40.1. Direct measurement at scale is feasible and cost-effective

The session clearly demonstrated that direct measurement of soil carbon stocks to depth has been done at scale and affordably throughout Europe. This, in effect, removes barriers to including direct measurement in soil carbon MRV to ensure carbon removal claims are real.

This capability has been made possible via recent financial investment and technological innovation, which have revolutionised soil sampling and laboratory analyses to make soil MRV affordable, rapid, and consistently high-quality. Thus, the often quoted barriers of poor quality, inconsistent soil data that are slow to produce have been removed.

40.2. A vast wealth of contemporary soil data is being generated

Various carbon-farming projects, both in the voluntary carbon market and in Scope 3 supply chains, produce substantial soil data. There is tremendous potential to harness these data sets to inform the EU's emerging carbon-removal certification framework (CRCF), enabling robust and farmer-relevant soil carbon MRV.

More research partnerships associated with CRCF are needed to continue developing accurate, affordable, and farmer-relevant soil carbon MRV.

40.3. Modelling alone risks greenwashing

The Regenerate Outcomes team's experiences illustrated the importance of having enough direct scale measurement to support reliable soil carbon changes modelling. Sufficient data is also required to demonstrate to farmers that their management practices result in real changes.

Sampling numbers (and hence costs) can be refined to reduce modelling uncertainty and support modelling predictions of soil carbon removals over time – a solely modelling-focused approach does not generate sufficient baseline or resampling direct measurement data to be confident that real (measurable) change has occurred. Therefore, a significant risk of greenwashing exists through over-reliance on modelling outcomes. Regenerate Outcomes works directly with farmers to deliver VCM and other benefit schemes to support the transition to regenerative/low-carbon farming.

40.4. Remote sensing is supportive but cannot replace ground truth

Remote sensing helps with qualitative assessments to support soil carbon MRV, e.g. in helping to validate claims using remote sensing tools. However, remote sensing tools are (as yet) unable to reliably predict absolute amounts or changes in soil carbon stocks for baselines or over time. Therefore, they are not reliable for use in baselining or resampling of soil carbon stocks.

3.41 Session 41: Setting the Gold Standard: Delivering shared value from reduced agricultural emissions

Main organisers: BASF

Session description

This session discussed the need and approach to develop a Gold Standard Verification Model.

Issues

- Creating a Gold Standard Model for monitoring, reporting, and verifying emission reductions
- Opportunities and challenges faced in implementing carbon farming projects at scale
- Identify potential areas of improvement in both implementation and certification.

Recommendations

No recommendation

4. Communications, dissemination and visibility

4.1 Introduction

The communications strategy for the 2nd Carbon Farming Summit followed a clear, structured, and phased approach designed to maximise visibility, encourage stakeholder engagement, and ensure wide-reaching outreach across platforms and audiences. This approach was organised around four core stages: strategic planning, tactical execution, content engagement, and post-event communications.

The process began with the development of a robust communications strategy and a detailed implementation plan to ensure coordinated efforts across channels, audiences, and consortium partners. Early preparatory steps included finalising and distributing a save-the-date, refining the Carbon Farming Summit concept note to anchor all messaging, and establishing submission and registration systems, including the integration of communication tools across email, the summit website, social media, and newsletters via the Eventtia platform.

The tactical phase was structured around key summit milestones – call for sessions, call for submissions, registration launch, sponsor promotion, and lead-up to the event. This included a strong multichannel communication push with over 30 LinkedIn posts, regular features in Project Credible, Climate KIC and partner newsletters, targeted email campaigns, and active social media engagement through consortium and partner channels. Direct outreach to key institutions such as DG Agri, DG Clima, EIT Food, the EU CAP Network, and COPA COGECA ensured strategic stakeholder involvement. To support promotion, comprehensive comms kits were developed for each phase, providing visual assets, email templates, and copy for social media and newsletters, all of which were shared with consortium members for wider distribution.

As the event approached, communications shifted to real-time support and on-site content engagement. Photographs, short interviews, and video footage were gathered

throughout the summit, capturing key moments from keynote speeches, breakout sessions, and networking breaks. Media engagement efforts included the preparation and dissemination of press releases and feature articles, supported by monitoring for press coverage. Sponsor visibility was maintained through tailored social media posts, email features, and dedicated presence on the Eventtia platform. Meanwhile, digital programmes, QR codes, banners, and visual displays ensured attendees had easy access to key materials.

Following the summit, the communications focus turned to post-event engagement. A thank you message was shared via the Eventtia app and email, also building momentum for the next summit in 2026. Additionally, session recordings, a summary video, and a wrap-up blog post capturing the summit's key insights and outcomes were published across the Climate-KIC website, and Project Credible's LinkedIn and YouTube channels.

4.2 Thought Leadership

A central component of the communications strategy for the 2nd European Carbon Farming Summit was the production of a series of well-researched, high-impact articles. These articles were not only a way to build anticipation and engagement ahead of the event but also served to position the Credible project and its associated organisations as thought leaders in the evolving field of carbon farming.

The first article, “From Theory to Practice: Leading Europe’s Carbon Farming Transition” (29 January 2025), marked a critical shift in narrative focus – from visionary thinking to actionable implementation. It highlighted Ireland’s pioneering approach to developing national carbon farming principles, underscored the role of financial innovation through mechanisms like the Carbon Removal Fund, and profiled European initiatives scaling climate-smart farming. This piece framed the summit as a platform for operationalising carbon farming, demonstrating how the event is leading the charge through practical, scalable solutions.

From theory to practice: Leading Europe’s carbon farming transition

NEWS | 29 JAN 2025

What is carbon farming?

Carbon farming can be defined as a green business model that rewards the actors of the land sector for taking up improved land management practices resulting in carbon sequestration in living biomass, dead organic matter, and soils by enhancing carbon capture and/or reducing the release of carbon to the atmosphere.

Image: Screenshot of the first article.

The second article, “Carbon Farming in Ireland: A Blueprint for Regenerative Agriculture” (6 February 2025), deepened the conversation by showcasing Ireland’s national framework development. Through interviews with senior representatives from the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine, the article gave insight into how Ireland is integrating environmental, social, and economic considerations into a coherent carbon farming strategy. Notably, it brought to light unique principles such as “just transition” and “learning by doing,” offering an inclusive, forward-thinking model for other European countries to consider.

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Carbon farming in Ireland: a blueprint for regenerative agriculture

NEWS | 06 FEB 2025

Climate KIC, as part of [Project Credible](#), is organising [the 2nd European Carbon Farming Summit](#), due to be held in Dublin, Ireland, from 4 to 6 March 2025. The summit is a partnership with the Government of Ireland's [Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine](#) (DAFM), and aims to shift the field [from theory to practice](#).

Image: Screenshot of the second article.

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The third article, published shortly after the summit (25 March 2025), captured the essence and impact of the three-day gathering. With over 1,000 stakeholders engaged, the summit's key messages, such as the need to go beyond carbon metrics and embed biodiversity, resilience, and social justice into farming models, were synthesised and shared widely. The article also drew out powerful quotes from leaders like Kirsten Dunlop and Minister Martin Heydon, framing carbon farming not just as a policy challenge, but as a cultural and economic transformation grounded in collaboration, trust, and systems thinking.

Beyond sequestration: Insights from the 2nd EU Carbon Farming Summit

NEWS | 25 MAR 2025

The 2nd European Carbon Farming Summit brought together over 1,000 stakeholders to shape the future of regenerative agriculture in Europe. Discussions highlighted the urgent need to move beyond carbon metrics alone – emphasising biodiversity and landscape resilience. With strong backing from the Irish government, the summit made it clear that farmers and foresters

Image: Screenshot of the third article.

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Publishing these articles was a vital move in asserting Credible's role as a convener, influencer, and innovator in the carbon farming landscape. By grounding the communications in real-world examples, policy alignment, and expert insights, the articles helped frame carbon farming as a comprehensive transition toward nature-positive agriculture. They also served as accessible entry points for broader audiences, bridging the gap between technical policy debates and the lived realities of farmers, land stewards, and practitioners.

4.3 Media and On-Site Comms

One month prior to the summit, a press release was disseminated to over 330 targeted journalists across Europe and beyond, focusing on those covering agriculture, climate policy, and carbon markets. The objective was to pique media interest in carbon farming as a timely and important topic ahead of the summit. This outreach contributed to a total of 37 online media mentions between 1 January 2025 and the end of March, helping to amplify the event's visibility and reinforce the summit's role in the broader discourse on sustainable land use and regenerative agriculture.

Mentions were identified in seven countries, with the majority appearing in the UK, US, and Switzerland, alongside several EU countries. A significant share of these mentions came from syndicated republications of CREDIBLE's original blog content, particularly:

- “From Theory to Practice: Leading Europe’s Carbon Farming Transition” – syndicated in 15 publications
- “Carbon Farming in Ireland: A Blueprint for Regenerative Agriculture” – syndicated in 11 publications

These figures underscore the strategic value of publishing original content through CREDIBLE's affiliated platforms, as they not only provide authoritative messaging but also enable wider media pickup and syndication through third-party networks. Two dedicated email campaigns were also conducted as part of media outreach:

- The first, sent to 134 journalists in Ireland from the “Agriculture, Climate, Livestock” beat, achieved an open rate of 40.2% (95 opens) and a click-through rate of 12.4% (29 clicks).
- The second, targeting 204 international media contacts, recorded an open rate of 38.7% (135 opens) and a click-through rate of 4.1% (25 clicks).

While the engagement levels were strong for targeted outreach, one key takeaway is the opportunity to improve on-site media coordination. The lack of dedicated press slots and limited proactive press invitations likely constrained broader media attendance and live coverage. In future editions, issuing more press passes and building structured engagement opportunities for journalists could help ensure greater media presence during the event itself, complementing the strong digital and content-based communications already in place.

Building on the success of previous years, this year's summit placed a strong emphasis on both participant experience and the real-time amplification of key messages and content. Particular attention was given to ensuring that all attendees had seamless access to essential information throughout the three-day event. Through curated materials via the Credible website and the Eventtia summit portal, participants were kept informed about the summit schedule, session topics, and logistical details.

A major enhancement in this year's approach was the contracting of a professional AV team to record key sessions in the main plenary room and select breakout spaces. These sessions were live-streamed via YouTube and made accessible to all registered attendees, significantly expanding the summit's reach and ensuring inclusion for those unable to attend in person. Following the event, these videos were published on the Project Credible YouTube channel for public access.

To capture the full energy and diversity of the event, a comprehensive photographic documentation was undertaken. Every session was photographed, and these images were incorporated into daily LinkedIn updates, which summarised the day's key discussions, themes, and takeaways. These posts achieved high levels of engagement, helping to sustain momentum throughout the summit. In parallel, content from attendees, partners, and consortium members was amplified across channels, reinforcing a spirit of collaboration and shared ownership.

In collaboration with SAE Innova, six roll-up banners were designed, printed and displayed throughout the venue, helping to create a cohesive and professional summit environment. Additionally, digital screens were strategically placed to display real-time session information, incorporating summit branding as well as the logos of affiliated organisations and sponsors, which enhanced both navigation and visibility for partners. To support networking, custom name tags were produced for every attendee, each featuring a scannable QR code that enabled seamless contact detail sharing and follow-up.

Image: A roll-up banner for branding at the venue

4.4 Summit Website and Eventtia Portal

A key part of the communications and participant experience strategy for the 2nd European Carbon Farming Summit was the effective use of digital platforms to support promotion, registration, and information delivery. Two core platforms were used in tandem: the summit website and the Eventtia summit portal.

The Carbon Farming Summit website, managed collaboratively by Climate KIC and SAE Innova, followed a phased content approach. It was regularly updated to reflect the evolving focus of the summit, from the initial save-the-date and call for sessions, to registration launches and programme announcements. This dynamic structure allowed for timely, targeted messaging that responded to the communication needs of each campaign phase, serving as a central destination for stakeholders seeking the latest summit information.

In parallel, the Eventtia summit portal, supported by an external service provider, was used as the main platform for registration management. The summit website directed

users to Eventtia, where they could complete registration and access practical details about attending the event. Beyond its logistical function, the portal also served as a digital hub for attendees, offering updates, venue information, speaker profiles, and session content. It remained live throughout the event, ensuring that both in-person and remote participants had continuous access to essential information.

Together, these platforms underpinned a seamless digital user journey, from discovery and sign-up to attendance and post-event engagement, ensuring that communications were well-crafted and well-delivered.

Image: The Carbon Farming Summit website

4.5 The Carbon Farming Summit Film

A professional short film was commissioned to capture the energy, ambition, and diverse perspectives of the 2025 Carbon Farming Summit. Produced in collaboration with filmmaker Tristan Copley Smith ([Possible Studio](#)), the film was designed to serve both as a storytelling tool and as promotional material for future summits. The production aimed to reflect the summit's central theme – *from theory to practice* – by showcasing real voices from across the carbon farming landscape: farmers, scientists, policymakers, and project partners.

The production process began in the lead-up to the summit, with input gathered from project leads and stakeholders to determine key messages and potential interviewees. During the summit in Dublin, the filmmaker worked closely with the organising team to conduct short, dynamic interviews on site. These were intentionally informal and soundbite-driven to fit into a tight five-minute narrative. Interviews featured speakers such as Doug McMillan (farmer), Sheila Darnos (Farmer), Christian Holzleitner (European Commission), and other key voices across policy, science, and implementation.

Filming took place primarily across the first two days of the summit, capturing interviews, candid interactions, breakout sessions, and plenary moments – including the opening keynote. Two versions of the film were produced:

- A longer, 5-minute version, providing a deeper dive into the purpose and impact of the summit;

Watch: [2nd European Carbon Farming Summit | Full-length](#)

- A shorter, 1-2 minute version, focused on the diversity of stakeholders and the overall importance of the event, ideal for social media sharing.

Watch: [2nd European Carbon Farming Summit | Short cut](#)

The final edits were completed with input from the organising team and key stakeholders. The films serve as a record of what took place, and as a forward-looking asset to communicate the vision of carbon farming to wider audiences.

4.6 Social Media

Social media played a pivotal role in building momentum ahead of the 2nd European Carbon Farming Summit and amplifying key messages during and after the event. Communications were primarily delivered through the Project Credible LinkedIn account, which served as the main channel for updates, engagement, and thought leadership content. To maximise reach, consortium partners were actively encouraged to reshare content via their own platforms, and attendees were invited to use the dedicated hashtag #CarbonFarmingSummit to increase visibility and organise related posts across the platform.

Between September 2024 and April 2025 – the main promotional lifespan of the 2nd European Carbon Farming Summit – the CREDIBLE LinkedIn account saw substantial growth and engagement:

- 79,434 impressions
- 2,045 reactions
- 56 comments
- 80 reposts
- 12,997 total clicks
- 42,470 total members reached
- Engagement rate: 19.1%
- 722 new followers gained in this period

This strong performance reflects a focused effort to publish timely, high-quality content in various formats, including daily summaries, speaker highlights, photographs, and real-time updates. These posts consistently achieved high levels of engagement, helping to build a wider community around the summit and the broader aims of the Credible project.

During the week of the summit itself, performance peaked significantly, reflecting a surge in real-time interest and activity:

- 14,688 impressions (up 193.3%)
- 522 reactions (up 255.1%)
- 11 comments (up 120%)
- 21 reposts (up 200%)
- 196 new followers (up 172.2%)

These metrics underscore the value of a coordinated, high-frequency posting strategy during the event, supported by strong visuals, meaningful storytelling, and cross-promotion by partner organisations and attendees. Together, these efforts extended the summit's reach well beyond the physical venue, and reinforced Project Credible's leadership in carbon farming and engaging a wider European and global audience in the conversation.

4.7 Summary

The communications campaign for the 2nd European Carbon Farming Summit was, on the whole, highly successful. It achieved strong visibility, high levels of engagement, and meaningful stakeholder participation across all phases, from early awareness-raising through to live event coverage and post-summit content delivery. Key assets such as the Credible LinkedIn channel, summit website, Eventtia portal, and a robust content pipeline (including articles, videos, and daily social media updates) worked in concert to position the summit as a major moment in Europe's carbon farming discourse.

A particular strength was the digital infrastructure that supported the campaign. The summit website, managed collaboratively by Climate KIC and SAE Innova, was a central communication tool, carefully updated in phases to reflect the evolving focus of the summit. This approach ensured timely, relevant messaging at every stage. The Eventtia summit portal, provided by an external service, was also essential for managing registrations and providing logistical information. Its dual function as both a registration system and a live information hub helped deliver a seamless attendee experience, which could certainly be better exploited for the third summit.

On-site, the communications strategy excelled in visual storytelling, real-time amplification, and stakeholder engagement. From live-streamed sessions and daily LinkedIn summaries to professional photography and post-summit video production, the communications presence was visible, consistent, and impactful. The use of QR-coded name tags and digital signage also enhanced participant experience and networking.

However, there were some areas for improvement. Media engagement on-site could have been stronger. While visual and digital communications were well executed, there was limited press presence due to reduced coordination with journalists. Addressing this in future editions would enable broader media coverage and help reach new audiences.

Additionally, more could have been done to profile and promote the individual keynote speakers. Although their contributions were central to the summit's content, targeted

content, such as dedicated interviews, speaker spotlights, or social media features, could have helped extend their visibility and attract interest in specific sessions.

Despite these areas of improvement, the campaign succeeded in significantly amplifying the summit's messages and reinforcing Credible's leadership in the field. With modest adjustments, particularly around press coordination and speaker promotion, the third edition is well-positioned to achieve even greater reach, engagement, and strategic impact.

5. 2nd Carbon Farming Summit: Lessons learned

The Second European Carbon Farming Summit was both a platform for dialogue and exchange, but also a learning process in itself – demonstrating what is needed to scale carbon farming from fragmented pilot projects to a credible, equitable, and system-wide solution across Europe.

A key lesson was the value of co-creation and participatory design. The summit's structure – built on two open calls for sessions and contributions – enabled a bottom-up agenda that prioritised high-impact, timely topics. By deliberately merging sessions to foster multi-actor conversations, the summit allowed critical issues such as finance, policy coherence, MRV, and farmer engagement to be addressed from a variety of perspectives. This approach created a rich, cross-sector dialogue that generated tangible insights and recommendations.

One of the most important takeaways was the need to move beyond carbon metrics alone. While carbon sequestration remains a core pillar, the summit affirmed that a narrow, soil-only approach risks missing broader opportunities. A future-proof carbon farming system must embrace landscape-level thinking – integrating biodiversity, water management, and social dimensions such as rural livelihoods and community resilience. There was a strong consensus that carbon farming should serve as a tool for systemic transformation, not just climate accounting.

The role of finance emerged as another central theme. Current carbon markets remain fragmented and poorly regulated, limiting access and impact. Public funding alone is insufficient, and so blended finance – mobilising both public and private investment – was identified as essential to unlock scale. Equally, efforts to scale must be matched by policy and financial alignment, ensuring that long-term visions are supported by accessible incentives, strong governance, and private sector engagement.

In terms of policy design, the summit highlighted the challenge of fragmented EU-level frameworks. While new tools such as the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) are under development, alignment with broader EU agricultural and environmental policies remains a work in progress. The call for greater coherence was clear: carbon farming must be situated within a wider policy ecosystem that supports regenerative agriculture, environmental resilience, and climate neutrality.

A significant implementation gap identified was the lack of adequate advisory support for farmers. Many attendees noted that without accessible, well-trained advisors, farmers

will continue to face barriers in navigating carbon schemes, understanding MRV processes, and accessing funding opportunities. Strengthening farm advisory networks and capacity-building across Member States is essential to ensure the transition is fair, informed, and inclusive.

Perhaps the most important lesson was a cultural one: farmers and land stewards must be seen not as beneficiaries, but as co-designers and leaders of the transition. Many are already adopting regenerative practices – not because of carbon credits, but because they see the climate and ecological risks firsthand. The summit confirmed the importance of valuing this lived expertise, embedding it at the centre of decision-making, and creating policy environments that respond to practical realities on the ground.

As the summit concluded, one clear message emerged: while real progress has begun, the momentum must continue. The insights, strategies, and partnerships developed during these three days must now feed into ongoing policy discussions, market development, and the growing community of practice across Europe. By sharing outcomes via the CREDIBLE consultation platform and through continued engagement, the work initiated in Dublin will carry forward – helping to shape a resilient, climate-positive, and socially just agricultural future.

Appendices

Appendix 1: The 2nd European Carbon Farming Summit Agenda

Carbon farming practices for land managers	Monitoring and verification tools	Rewarding mechanisms for impactful climate actions	Cross-cutting topics
Tuesday 4 March			
8.00-9.00	Registration		
9.00-10.30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opening by the Government of Ireland’s Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM) • Plenary session on the state of affairs in policy related to carbon farming (and beyond) • Organisers: DG Clima/AGRI/JRC 		
10.30-11.00	Coffee/tea break		
11.00-12.30	Parallel sessions		
Printworks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2. Low hanging (tree) fruit – reaping forest-based carbon removal potential, identifying challenges and gaps to open doors to forest management solutions. • Organisers: Anew Climate, Caritas, Climate KIC, I4CE, Cesefor Foundation, Carbon Capture Company, ECS Climate Solutions, BlueBiloba, University of Florence, Preferred by Nature. 		
Poddle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 26. Integrating MRV methodologies, and incentives to reduce N₂O emissions in carbon farming. • Organisers: i-BEC, Proba 		
Courtyard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8. Farmers' and regions' perspectives on carbon farming. • Organisers: BSAG, BEC 		
Bedford 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 32. Real-life MRV challenges and solutions for the EU CRCF. • Organisers: Agreena, Seqana, Space4Good 		
Bedford 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6. Carbon farming – assured profitability? How to ensure long-term sustainability of practices. • Organisers: ECAF, ECAF, University of Cordoba, EURAF, University of Greifswald 		
Rose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 7. CRCF business models. • Organisers: Agroinsider, Carbone farmers, reframe.food, Eleks, Agrosolutions 		
12:30-14:00	Lunch		
14.00-15.30	Parallel sessions		
Printworks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 35. Learnings from research and feedback from the field: How to put in place carbon farming on a farm? What levers and barriers? • Organisers: Agrosolutions, Arvalis, Climate KIC, IDELE, INRAE, Teagasc, Terre Inovia 		
Poddle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 12. Ensuring sustainability outcomes from carbon farming: Recommendations for the CRCF and voluntary carbon markets. • Organisers: Ecologic Institute 		

Courtyard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 18. Co-designing a service on carbon farming based on data from environmental research infrastructures. • Organiser: Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS ERIC)
Bedford 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20. Financing models for a sustainable future. • Organisers: Heavy Finance, Rabobank
Bedford 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 31. Earth observation for carbon farming: Exploring existing solutions and future user needs. • Organiser: ESA SEF
Rose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 23. MRV agroforestry. • Organizers: Climate Cleanup, DEAFAL, DeFAF, ELO, EURAF, INRAE, Scave World, University of Pisa
15.30-16.00	Coffee/tea break
16:00-17:15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plenary session: Technological pathways and user engagement approaches to a European MRV system. • Organizer: UFZ
17:15-18:00	Plenary wrap-up session
18.00-19.00	Poster session

Carbon farming practices for land managers	Monitoring and verification tools	Rewarding mechanisms for impactful climate actions	Cross-cutting topics
Wednesday 5 March			
8.00-9.00	Registration		
8.30-10.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plenary session: Paving the way towards climate positive agriculture: The role of innovating farmers. • Organiser: SAE 		
10.00-10.30	Coffee/tea break		
10.30-12.00	Parallel session		
Printworks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 21. Paving the way for cohesive action on soil carbon sequestration: The role of international initiatives in the development of MRV frameworks that meet European carbon farming challenges. • Organisers: 4per1000, INRAE 		
Poddle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 16. Unlocking the potential of soil biodiversity: Sustainable land management, restoration, and revenue generation. • Organisers: Cà Colonna srl, Carboneg, Land Life 		
Courtyard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 33. How technology and AI is supporting the growth of efficient, high-integrity carbon farming markets. • Organisers: GreenO, SAS, Social Carbon Foundation, Walton Institute 		
Bedford 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 13. Global or local? Carbon certification centralisation level: What implications for stakeholders? • Organisers: I4CE, Association des Chambres d'agriculture de l'Arc Atlantique (AC3A) 		
Bedford 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 11. The role of farm advisors in climate action in Europe. • Organisers: INTIA, Consulai, ILVO, Teagasc 		
Rose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 14. The value chain challenge: Scaling scope 3 solutions. • Organisers: Mars Inc., Friesland Campina, Lakeland Dairies, Soil Capital 		

12.00-13.30	Lunch break
13.30-15.00	Parallel session
Printworks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Scaling up resilient and inclusive agricultural value chains – from policy to financing adoption of new practices. Organisers: Livelihoods Funds, Social Carbon Foundation, Treevaluation
Poddle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 40. Why do we need Direct Measurement to secure Europe’s carbon farming future? Organiser: Agricarbon
Courtyard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 24. Carbon farming challenges in Mediterranean agriculture: Resilient project solutions and certification pathways. Organisers: Agri Marketplace, BETA Technological Centre, CREA-AA, SLM Partners, Tetis Institute S.r.l, Università degli Studi di Genova
Bedford 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 27. Unlocking data for MRV: Data sharing for effective carbon farming. Organisers: Agrosolutions, ELGO-DIMITRA, Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO), Soil Capital
Bedford 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 9. Farmers’ prospect: How does carbon farming affect crop production, farm biodiversity and profitability? Organisers: CREAM
Rose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 28. Baseline approaches for monitoring soil carbon removals: Public-private synergies. Organisers: GMV, ILVO, INRAE, JRC
15.00-15.30	Coffee/tea break
15.30-17.00	Parallel sessions
Printworks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 15. Insetting for carbon farming: Turning challenges into opportunities for farmers, food companies and policy makers. Organisers: Friesland Campina, ILVO, Rabobank, UCLouvain, ZLTO
Poddle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 38. From peatlands to policy: How praxis can guide EU CRCF certification. Organiser: University of Greifswald
Courtyard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 41. Setting the gold standard: Delivering shared value from reduced agricultural emissions. Organiser: BASF
Bedford 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 25. Opportunities and challenges in proximal sensing-based monitoring for carbon farming. Organisers: University of Helsinki, University of Helsinki, Yard Stick PBC
Bedford 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 10. The future of regional small-scale carbon farming projects: Discussing bottom-up experiences and align farmer and market perspectives. Organisers: Boerenbond Projects, Interreg NWE Smart carbon farming project, ZLTO
Rose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 28. Baseline approaches for monitoring soil carbon removals: Public-private synergies. Organisers: GMV, ILVO, INRAE, JRC
17:00-18:00	Plenary wrap-up session
18.00-19.00	Poster session with refreshments
19:30-	Conference dinner

Carbon farming practices	Monitoring and verification tools	Rewarding mechanisms for	Cross-cutting topics
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for land managers	impactful actions	climate
Thursday 6 March		
8.00-9.00	Registration	
9.00-10.30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plenary session: Policy areas relevant to carbon farming: Synergies and trade-offs. • Organiser: EEB 	
10.30-11.00	Coffee/tea break	
11.00-12.30	Parallel session	
Printworks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 19. Overcoming barriers to carbon farming projects financing: Bridging the gap between farmers and buyers through adequate framework and MRV tools. • Organisers: AC3A, Agrifood, Agrosolutions, CNRS-CESBIO, Earth Observation Association, I4CE, IETA, Nataïs, Netcarbon, Regeneration 	
Poddle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 37. Ireland: An innovative, context-specific approach to carbon farming? • Organisers: DAFM Ireland, Climate KIC, Department of Environment, Climate and Communications (DECC), Irish Cooperative Organisation Society, Bord Bia, National Economic and Social Council, Environmental Protection Agency, Teagasc, Irish Strategic Investment Fund 	
Courtyard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 36. What is the farmer's opinion on carbon farming? • Organisers: Bioeconomy Cluster, Carbery Farmers' Cooperative, CoopsAgroES, Farmers, French Agricultural Chambers, ICOS (Irish Co-operative Organisation Society) 	
Bedford 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 30. Addressing uncertainties and model benchmarking in earth observation-based MRV systems for carbon farming. • Organisers: CinSOIL GmbH, EARSC 	
Bedford 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 29. (Non)-permanence and time dependency of carbon sequestration in carbon farming – current accounting approaches and ways ahead. • Organisers: Agroscope, Agrosolutions, Thuenen Institute, Wageningen Environmental Research 	
Rose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3. Income opportunities from peatland rewetting: Carbon credits, ecosystem service payments and paludiculture value chains. • Organisers: Aeco, Association des Chambres d'agriculture de l'Arc Atlantique (AC3A), Eurosite, Green Restoration Ireland, Social Carbon Foundation, University of Greifswald 	
12.30-14.00	Lunch break and poster session	
14.00-15:30	Parallel session	
Printworks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5. Bringing carbon farming from science to organic and regenerative farms: Challenges and solutions across research, markets, farmer-led models and policy. • Organisers: FiBL, ReGeneration, National Association of Producers for Organic and Regenerative Agriculture (Produttori AOR), IFOAM Europe 	
Poddle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 34. Rewarding mechanisms: Insights from farmers, agri-food companies and researchers for a successful approach • Organisers: Climate KIC, DELOITTE, INRAE 	
Courtyard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 39. Legal opportunities for carbon farming: from creation of a registry to the necessary streamlining of the applicable environmental law framework 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organisers: Philip Lee LLP / Hutchins Climate Capital
Bedford 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Exploring carbon farming approaches: Integrating circular solutions from biomass production and treatment to soil health and carbon sequestration. Organisers: Agrimercarb, Tierra Sphere, Re-Cord, TGO AG and ECN
Bedford 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 17. Multi-stakeholder networks and participatory approaches for successful carbon farming and soil health monitoring – opportunities and challenges. Organisers: Commonland Foundation, EIT Food South, Wetlands International
Rose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 22. Monitoring and verification of peatland condition and improvement: Remote sensing, AI and beyond. Organisers: AECO, National Parks and Wildlife Service, Peatland Finance Ireland, Trinity College Dublin, University College Dublin
15.30-16:00	Coffee/tea break
16.00-17:15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plenary session: The way ahead from a systemic transition approach with speakers from science, policy, farmers organisation and industry. Organisers: Climate KIC and BSAG

Appendix 2: Examples of posters during the Summit

Below are some examples of the posters presented during the summit. Around 45 posters were presented over the three days of the summit. Each poster relates to one or more Focus Group question areas (explored during the Breakout Sessions).

Here is a link to explore additional posters presented at the summit:

- [2nd Carbon Farming Summit Posters](#)

Launching large scale carbon farming projects : feedback from the French case using CarbonExtract MRV tool

LABEL BAS CARBONE powered by **carbon extract**

- ✓ Implementing a carbon farming project is complex. MRV tools are essential to simplify data collection and transition scenario calculations.
- ✓ Since 2020 in France, deployment of the Label bas-carbone certification framework through tier 3 MRV tools (Measuring, Reporting and Verification)
- ✓ + More than 5,000 farms involved, including 1,482 using the CarbonExtract tool
- ✓ Baseline calculated from historical farm practices and realistic simulations based on farmers' choices

Process of implementing a carbon farming project

Training and educational challenges

- Farmers need to understand the challenges of the low-carbon transition and the different carbon farming practices. **Technical advisors are the key players in supporting farmers in this transition.**
- MRV tools can be used to test different combinations of realistic carbon farming practices according to the farmer's choices.
- Handling these tools requires training for technical advisors and farmers who work together on each farm's ideal transition pathway.

Agrosolutions designed a specific training program, hybrid remote and presential to train **> 300 farm advisors** in less than 3 years

> 200 input data needed to calculate the carbon footprint of farms

Analysis of the average carbon footprint of french farms and transition potential

Recommendations for the CRCF

- ✓ Based on our experience, a significant proportion of farms could generate soil emission reduction credits rather than net carbon removal credits. Indeed, most of the transition potential is to reduce soil GHG emissions. It would therefore be important to consider these soil emission reduction credits within the CRCF, as they represent a significant transition potential.

In partnership with:

Deep Demonstration partnership of climate-resilient food systems in Ireland

THE DEEP DEMONSTRATION

OBJECTIVES

The Deep Demonstration partnership between Climate KIC and Ireland's Department of Agriculture, Food, and the Marine is supporting the entire Irish land and agri-food value chain to identify and implement sustainable practices, so that farmers and rural communities can thrive and industries can transition to sustainable business models, all while meeting challenging climate targets.

APPROACH

- **Demand-led:** co-designing interventions with key stakeholders.
- Developing and implementing a **portfolio** of large-scale **connected interventions** in the land and agri-food system.
- Embedding rapid **'learning by doing'** to provide intelligence which will enable government and industry to make informed decisions about choices to meet climate goals.

METHODOLOGY

OUR DEEP DEMONSTRATIONS

OUR IMPACT IN IRELAND

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

INSIGHTS

- Map of the Irish land and agri-food system
- 7 high-potential innovation areas
- Policy measures from 12 countries
- Key funding and financing flows
- Analysis of skills needs
- 3 key themes for narrative shift
- Cross-lessons from Slovenia and Spain

Download our reports

7 FLAGSHIP AREAS

of which 4 have been prioritised, underpinned by 275+ project ideas

- 1 FLAGSHIP 1 | Vision 2050: re-imagine Ireland's land and agri-food system | ACTIVE
- 2 FLAGSHIP 2 | Foster innovation and investment in new value chains to diversify the sector
- 3 FLAGSHIP 3 | Promote circular bioeconomy models in regions and multiple value chains | ACTIVE
- 4 FLAGSHIP 4 | Diversify incomes through a carbon farming and nature credit framework | ACTIVE
- 5 FLAGSHIP 5 | Produce and certify climate-neutral beef
- 6 FLAGSHIP 6 | Accelerate emission reduction and sustainability in dairy farms | ACTIVE
- 7 FLAGSHIP 7 | Grow and diversify the tillage sector

DEVELOPING CARBON FARMING PRINCIPLES FOR IRELAND

OBJECTIVE

To support and enable the adoption and scaling of management practices within primary production that will result in Ireland achieving its climate, biodiversity and water quality targets by the end of 2030.

INSIGHTS

Significant stakeholder engagement by the National Carbon Farming Working Group, chaired by DAFM and Climate KIC

- Nation-wide public consultation survey gathering around 400 responses
- Ongoing series of bilateral engagements and workshops with almost 200 individuals

Respondents indicated they want a long-term scheme:

What should be the lifetime funding required for an initiative?

CORE CARBON PRINCIPLES

GOVERNANCE

- 1 Effective governance
- 2 Tracking
- 3 Transparency
- 4 Independent verification

EMISSIONS IMPACT

- 5 Additionality
- 6 Permanence
- 7 Quantification of outcomes
- 8 No double counting

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

- 9 Benefits and safeguards
- 10 Contribution to 2050 goals

SPECIFIC TO IRELAND

- 11 Just transition
- 12 Learning by doing

VISIT OUR WEBSITE FOR MORE INFORMATION
www.climate-kic.org/SustainableFoodIreland

SIGN UP TO OUR NEWSLETTER

Valuing the benefits of carbon farming beyond carbon: indicators to assess soil ecosystem services in three European case studies

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Background

According to the EU Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Regulation, carbon farming practices must generate co-benefits for the protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems, including soil health and the avoidance of land degradation. In addition, "Operators or groups of operators should be able to report co-benefits that contribute to the sustainability objectives beyond the minimum sustainability requirements [...] Certification methodologies should, as much as possible, incentivise the generation of co-benefits for biodiversity going beyond the minimum sustainability requirements, with a view to generating a market premium for the certified units" (CRCF Regulation (EU) 2024/3012). Developing a common methodology is challenging, and joint efforts are needed.

Two Horizon Europe projects aim at ensuring accountability of soil health and biodiversity within the EU carbon farming certification framework.
→ Indicator-based approach, where a wide set of indicators is measured in a large number of case studies, and the most sensitive are identified.

Three representative case studies from InBestSoil

Pedoclimatic regions: Mediterranean (1-2) and Atlantic (3)

Land uses: Agriculture (2-3) and Forestry (1)

Practices:

- 1) Rotational grazing to improve forest (Dehesa) soil quality, since 2019
- 2) Reduced tillage, cover crops and crop rotations, since 2009
- 3) Reduced tillage, cover crops and crop rotations, since 2005

The table below includes the most sensitive indicators to discriminate between managements in the three selected case studies, grouped by ecosystem service and corresponding sustainability objective of the CRCF Regulation. All indicators can be measured based on standardized scientific methodologies and a complete list will be reported as an outcome of the projects. The ones marked with * are satellite-based.

Category	Soil ecosystem service	Sustainability objective (CRCF Regulation (EU) 2024/3012)	Most sensitive indicators		
			CS1 (Mediterranean forest)	CS2 (Mediterranean agricultural)	CS3 (Atlantic agricultural)
Provisioning	Provision of food	Climate change adaptation	-	Crop yield	na
	Provision of fibre, energy or raw materials	Transition to a circular economy	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)*	-	-
Regulating	Climate regulation	Climate change mitigation	Total soil organic carbon; Albedo and land surface temperature	Particulate soil organic carbon; potential soil CO ₂ emissions; Net primary productivity	Total soil organic carbon; particulate soil organic carbon; Net primary productivity
	Water/air purification and soil contaminant reduction	Sustainable use and protection of water; pollution prevention and control	Total mercury; pH	-	-
	Nutrient cycling	Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems, including soil health as well as avoidance of land degradation; pollution prevention and control; sustainable use and protection of water	Available phosphorus; exchangeable magnesium	Total nitrogen; exchangeable ammonium; exchangeable magnesium; exchangeable potassium; cation exchange capacity	Total nitrogen; nitrates; bioavailable zinc; exchangeable magnesium; exchangeable potassium
	Flood regulation and water storage	Climate change adaptation	Bulk density; water content at field capacity	Drought Stress Index (DSI)*; water content at field capacity; mean weight diameter of soil aggregates	Drought Stress Index (DSI)*; clay content; bulk density
	Erosion control	Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems, including soil health as well as avoidance of land degradation	Vegetation cover	Vegetation cover; bare soil index	Vegetation cover; bare soil index
Supporting	Biodiversity	Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems, including soil health as well as avoidance of land degradation	Total PLFAs; Fungal Shannon Index; Fungal Chao1 Index	Total PLFAs; actinomycota biomass; bacterial abundance; Prokaryotic Simpson Index	Firmicutes abundance; bacterial abundance; Fungal Chao1 Index
	Habitat for organisms (landscape heterogeneity)	Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems, including soil health as well as avoidance of land degradation	Soil sealing	Soil sealing	Presence of natural green elements

For more information: <https://inbestsoil.eu/>; <https://bioservices-project.eu/>; <https://soilcommunity.app/>

SOIL COMMUNITY

Opportunities of wet peatland carbon farming

Building paludiculture business cases at scale

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Rewetting Peatlands: A necessity for climate-neutral land use by 2050

- Achieving climate neutrality in the land-use sector by 2050 requires rewetting peatlands and a shift towards zero-drainage peatland use.
- Though covering only 3% of EU agricultural land, drained peat soils contribute 25% of all GHG emissions from EU agricultural sector; in peatland-rich Member States, e.g. in Baltics, even up to 71% (see Fig.1).
- A just transition needs to engage landowners and land users, recognizing their essential role in addressing climate and societal challenges.
- A new paradigm for peatland carbon farmers is needed:
- Cultivating renewable biomass for carbon-neutral or carbon-negative products through paludiculture.
- Preserving soil carbon in wet peat layers, biodiversity, water resources, and essential ecosystem services while contributing to climate change mitigation & adaptation, and human wellbeing.

Upscaling needs:

- 1) Establishing & upscaling best paludiculture practices;
- 2) Building a database on ecosystem services from paludiculture pilots;
- 3) Developing climate-neutral value chains for paludiculture products;
- 4) Developing consistent agricultural policy & remuneration frameworks in line with EU & national frameworks.

Fig. 1: Emissions from drained peatlands in the agricultural sector. Percentage of agricultural land on organic soils (inner circle) and percentage of their greenhouse gas emissions of total agricultural emissions (incl. LU/LUCF) (outer circle). Source: GMC 2020

Financing peatland restoration & paludiculture under the EU CRFC: Key insights & strategies

Ensured additionality and market credibility

Peatland rewetting until now remains far below what is needed. It can therefore be considered to be **additional by default**. Emission reductions from peatland rewetting are **inherently permanent**, because –also in the case of reversal– the CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere remains permanently reduced compared to the baseline.

Scaling up requires blended finance

Peatland restoration through rewetting & paludiculture must overcome key barriers to achieve implementation at scale.

- Blended finance, **combining CAP funding, carbon markets, and national incentives**, should be developed to ensure long-term financial viability
- Paludiculture biomass **demand must be stimulated**.

Adopt a hybrid payment model to ensure viability

- Contractual agreements should **ensure upfront payments for rewetting costs** (before credit issuance), combined with result-based payments for verified emission reductions.
- Ensure security for farmers while maintaining accountability.

Baltic paludiculture experience

Fig. 2: EU Paludiculture Baltics assessed paludiculture potential, model site implementation, and living labs in the Baltics. Sites below will be part of Horizon project PaluWise.

Fig. 2a&b: The Baisrogala paludiculture show case, Lithuania; 5 ha peatland rewetting & establishment of wet reed canary grass production for fodder or energy biomass.

Fig. 2c&d: Living lab on 50 ha Natura2000 wet meadows & pellet production in Rūja river valley in Latvia.

What is paludiculture?

Paludiculture is wet agriculture or silviculture on wet and rewetted peatland that uses spontaneously grown or cultivated above ground biomass under conditions in which peat is conserved or even newly formed. Therefore permanent waterlogging with water levels in or close to the surface (±10 cm) during vegetation periods and avoidance of practices that harm the topsoil and root layer are essential.

Peatlands, Climate, and Paludiculture

How to paludiculture?

Resources

- <https://www.moorwissen.de/index-en.html>
- <https://www.moorwissen.de/paludizentrale.html>
- [Info paper on paludiculture and biodiversity](#)
- [Wetlands and methane](#)
- [Why methane emissions from peatlands should be considered in climate change mitigation?](#)

Upscaling paludiculture tomoor.w

Germany is a forerunner in large-scale, long-term paludiculture pilots with strong business integration. Through the toMOOR initiative, 14 leading companies have formed the "Alliance of Pioneers," committing to developing and scaling paludiculture within their operations.

At the European level, the EU HORIZON-CLG-2024-CLIMATE-01-3 call, "Paludiculture: Large-Scale Demonstrations," builds on this momentum. As a result, three large-scale projects will launch in 2025:

CREDIBLE
EU carbon farming

Funded by
the European Union

CREDIBLE
EU carbon farming